
APPENDIX

What follows is:

1. A list of each Q item (statement), its item number, and a description of the purpose the item is intended to serve for the study.
 2. Q methodology raw data
 3. Interview phrases and how each was coded
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Item No.	Q-item / Statement	Sales logics	Service logics	Compliance logics	Rationale for Statement
Item 1	A focus on planning may sometimes be a way of deflecting client concerns about portfolio performance.	X		X	<p>Financial plans are intended to analyze, in part, the sustainability of assets over a lifetime along with other highly useful information including estate, tax, and retirement planning along with several other topics. Financial planning provides additional value added at no additional cost to investors and can serve a critical service toward the financial wellbeing of investors. However, not all clients need or want financial planning aside from investment management. The firm, though, strongly encourages planning and makes delivering a minimum number of financial plans a part of the compensation structure. PCAs have hard targets for planning beyond the portfolio. The firms' intention is to ensure clients are served well and to retain clients in the offer.</p> <p>However, clients sometimes put pressure on PCAs for portfolio performance. And one common reason clients leave the offer is because of disappointment about portfolio performance. The firm realizes performance is difficult to control. And they believe planning (outside the portfolio) can sometimes deflect investor attention away from focusing solely on performance. A conflict of interest arises by forcing planning conversations, through quota, that some investors do not want or need as a means to serve the firms self-interest in an attempt to show value beyond portfolio management and with the intention of minimizing the importance of portfolio performance.</p> <p>Offering financial planning is a legitimate service to offer. But it could be argued that the practice has a deceptive element because of the intention behind offering planning, which is, in part, to distract investors from, or minimize the importance of the performance of the portfolio. PCAs do not charge a separate fee for planning services, but because of the firms' emphasis, PCAs must sometimes feel forced to 'sell' the idea to investors whose only interest and /or need may be investment management. PCAs should have the autonomy to offer financial planning services at their discretion based on their assessment of client needs rather than because the firm expects a certain percentage of a PCAs practice to have a plan. This issue touches on the ethics of compliance and sales – the tension between the two logics and highlights the drive to keep customers satisfied even at the expense of full transparency.</p>

Item No.	Q-item / Statement	Sales logics	Service logics	Compliance logics	Rationale for Statement
Item 2	Management expresses concern and /or interest about individual PCA investor portfolio performance.	X	X		Supervisors rarely inquire about individual investor portfolio performance; strategies, or investment recommendations beyond what is required to monitor for regulatory compliance purposes. The focus, rather, is on achieving success in certain metrics: high client survey scores; achieving a minimum percentage (currently 50%) of clients having had some kind of financial planning conversation beyond the portfolio, retaining existing clients, and aggregating net new assets into the offer. Each of these activities are reasonable to engage in, notwithstanding quotas. Among the metrics there seems to be one that is glaringly missing, though. If the company wishes to view decisions it makes and the offer as though we were doing so by looking 'through client's eyes' it seems the firm would want to understand how well clients were tracking with their finances. This helps determine the value of the service, of which investment planning is only one part, but critical, nonetheless. The firm is not entirely inward looking. The survey scores tell a story about how clients feel. Yet, with as much concern as investors have over markets and performance, shouldn't the firm have some idea how they are doing in this regard? This dynamic may expose some tension between the drive for sales (sales logics) and how well clients are served (service logic)
Item 3	Because of my workload I sometimes worry about the possibility of important things falling through the cracks.	X	X		If advisors have too many clients to ensure each is provided adequate care portfolio management, financial planning and service issues can go unattended. This demonstrates the tension between, and the dominance of, sales logic over service logic. This has implications for how clients are served as well as the wellbeing of both advisors and clients. It can be argued that the firm may be using people (PCAs) merely as means to achieve their own self-interested ends. If so, this is morally wrong. This highlights the tension between the drive for sales (sales logics) and the importance of providing good service levels (service logics) with implications for wellbeing of advisors and clients.

Item No.	Q-item / Statement	Sales logics	Service logics	Compliance logics	Rationale for Statement
Item 4	I would work with less stress and be more effective if I didn't have specific measurable performance expectations.	X	X	X	<p>Does the effect on motivation from having targets (sales), quotas, or goals detract from an advisor's productivity and feelings of autonomy and relatedness and competence? The influence of targets, etc. on wellbeing and therefore productivity is the dynamic here. According to self-determination theory, some workers are motivated more by intrinsic factors and demotivated by extrinsic factors such as goals, quotas and targets. In a business whose main purpose is (or should be) helping people, having workers with an intrinsic desire to do the work is more powerful and effective than having workers performing job functions mainly for the pay rather than because of a desire to fulfil a personal mission to serve others, notwithstanding compensation being sufficient.</p> <p>If workers are not quite achieving their targets it is sometimes the case that ethical 'corners will be cut' in order to hit those goals. This creates not only sales logics versus service logics tensions, but sales logics versus compliance logics as well depending upon the degree to which corners are cut. The 'stress' aspect of the statement also has implications for advisor wellbeing.</p>
Item 5	My main motivation for working is to help as many investors succeed as possible.	X	X		<p>Are advisors in the role to serve others? Do they hold altruistic beliefs? This statement speaks to how strongly PCAs are committed to be in service to others versus committed to self-interests such as to make as much money for themselves as possible. Hence, this statement measures the tension between service logics and sales logics.</p>
Item 6	My main motivation for working is for me to succeed.	X	X		<p>As in Item #5, Are advisors in the role to serve others? Do they hold altruistic beliefs? Or are they primarily self-interested? This statement speaks to how strongly PCAs are committed to be in service to others versus committed to self-interests such as to make as much money for themselves as possible. Hence this statement measures the tension between service logics and sales logics.</p>

Item No.	Q-item / Statement	Sales logics	Service logics	Compliance logics	Rationale for Statement
Item 7	My main motivation for working is to get praise from my boss.	X		X	To understand as much as possible about the environment, we must ask how important is the relationship with the supervisor? Some employees who lean toward extrinsic motivation require their supervisors' approval more than those motivated by intrinsic factors such as service to others. Getting an "Atta-boy!" from the boss every so often can help reinforce extrinsically motivated workers' commitment and sense of wellbeing. However, sometimes a desire to please the supervisor, or deliver what it is perceived the supervisor wants- perhaps an unchecked desire to 'make the numbers', can create ethical 'blind spots' leading to behavior that can be in conflict with the fiduciary obligation the PCA has for his or her clients. In a fiduciary relationship service to the client comes first. Allegiance to the company or boss and their ubiquitous emphasis on production should be a secondary, or possibly tertiary consideration for a fiduciary. This statement speaks to wellbeing; intrinsic versus extrinsic motivation and the extent to which the sales logic dominates fiduciary (compliance) considerations.
Item 8	My main motivation for working is to help the company succeed.	X	X		How important is the team aspect of working? Do individual employees feel connected to, and personally identify with, the success of the company as a whole? Do they view their personal success being intertwined or dependent on how well the company does? Do they feel they are a part of a team consisting of many members and departments but all being on the same team working toward the same goal? Or do workers work in silos focused only on what their narrowly defined territory or duties entail? Teamwork falls in the category of service to others - the team. The tension lies between teamwork (service logics) and self-interests which are more closely aligned with sales logics.
Item 9	PCAs may be reluctant to 'fire' a client because of the damage it may cause to their relationship with the referring FC.	X		X	This statement is intended to expose or determine if possible conflicts of interest exist because advisors must sometimes pander to referring FCs rather than ensure the offer is suitable for clients. This statement is intended to explore the extent to which sales logics dominate and create an environment where unethical behavior can arise as a result. The tension is between sales logics and compliance logics. Compliance logics would press that only clients for whom the offer is suitable should be in the offer.

Item No.	Q-item / Statement	Sales logics	Service logics	Compliance logics	Rationale for Statement
Item 10	The thing my clients say matters most to them are broad financial planning topics.	X	X		<p>This statement seeks to clarify assumed PCAs views that not everyone wants or needs a plan, beyond investment planning. It is rare that clients ask for a comprehensive financial plan. Most clients come to the offer because they want good performance. Referring FCs often sell the offer as a means of achieving better performance than alternative advice offers. Because of quotas, though, sometimes PCAs feel like they must force planning beyond investment planning on clients.</p> <p>There is a culture of sales that seeks to enforce the notion that everyone needs a plan and if investors knew what was good for them, they would want a plan. But not all referring FCs think of, or position, the offer this way making it difficult for PCAs to lead with planning.</p> <p>Further, because of quotas for planning, PCAs lack autonomy to determine who needs a plan and who does not. There would be less conflicts of interest if the relationship between the advisor and client could drive the decision about what forms of planning are provided.</p> <p>The tension here is between taking a client-centered, (service logics) oriented approach rather than one which is internally driven where there may be an ulterior motive of using planning as a retention tool and as some PCAs have stated, as a way to uncover or identify assets held outside the firm in order to later persuade the investor to transfer those assets to the firm's advisory offer (sales logics). The alternative is to respond to client needs and wants solely (service logics) providing planning as the PCA feels appropriate.</p> <p>While it can be beneficial and in the clients' best interest to consolidate their investments with one firm, making assets easier to manage. It can also be perceived as self-serving for the firm, which in and of itself is not immoral. But it can be argued the firm may use this tactic; uses investors, in part, merely as a means to satisfy its own self-interested ends. This then becomes an issue of ethics.</p>

Item No.	Q-item / Statement	Sales logics	Service logics	Compliance logics	Rationale for Statement
Item 11	The thing my clients say matters most to them is the performance of their investments.	X		X	This statement is intended to test the researchers intuition with the views of other advisors. If this is, in fact, the case then we should not be avoiding performance discussions. To do otherwise would be to weaken PCAs fiduciary duty in favor of purposefully minimizing the importance of performance. This then becomes an ethics issue. This statement tests the domination of a sales logics over fiduciary duty (compliance logics).
Item 12	I must keep in mind as important that clients equate trading activity with progress.	X		X	Advisors sometimes pander to clients, realizing that clients sometimes believe if there is no activity, that may mean their advisor is 'asleep at the wheel'. Even if no activity is actually warranted, advisors may be prone to want to do a trade at least to some extent, even unnecessarily, to keep appearances up and keep the client engaged - and enrolled in the offer. This statement exposes pressure from / conflict of interest with clients and unethical behavior that can result. If PCAs didn't have to be concerned about unenrollment's, PCAs would, in this situation, only place trades that were warranted and in the clients best interest. They would not have to consider placing trades for the sake of appearances. This statement has to do with the tension between sales logics and fiduciary duty (compliance logics).
Item 13	I must keep in mind as important that clients equate inactivity with their advisor being 'asleep at the wheel.'	X		X	Advisors sometimes pander to clients, realizing that clients sometimes believe if there is no activity, they may think their advisor is 'asleep at the wheel', even if no activity is actually warranted, advisors may be prone to want to do a trade to keep the client engaged - and enrolled in the offer. This statement exposes pressure from / conflict of interest with clients and unethical behavior that can result. If PCAs didn't have to be concerned about unenrollment's, PCAs would, in this situation, only place trades that were warranted and in the clients best interest. They would not have to consider placing trades for the sake of appearances. This exposes pressure from, and conflict of interest with, clients when APCs have pressure to keep clients enrolled in the offer, even when the offer is not a good fit for the client. This statement explores tension between business development (sales logics) and fiduciary duty (compliance logics).

Item No.	Q-item / Statement	Sales logics	Service logics	Compliance logics	Rationale for Statement
Item 14	Adhering to compliance rules is onerous and unproductive.	X		X	This statement is intended to understand the influence of the Supervision and Controls (compliance) department on investment advisor ethics. Do PCAs resent having to take the extra steps involved in properly documenting conversations? Do they take 'short-cuts' in creating their Investment Policy Statements or developing a Suitability Profile for clients? Is compliance training taken seriously? Do PCAs think of Supervision and Controls as their ally helping them stay out of trouble or as more of an adversarial relationship? Do PCAs feel Supervision and Controls (compliance logics) slow or hamper the sales (sales logics) process?
Item 15	Having a performance target for financial planning and single topic solutions provides a desirable way to motivate me.	X		X	This statement is intended to determine how advisors like to be incentivized. Do they like targets, goals, quotas? The firms' position is that people behave in a way that is consistent with how they are paid. This may be true for those whose motivation is extrinsic, but not as true for those who are motivated intrinsically. It is important that workers engage in the activities the firm desires. But knowledge workers are said to be more effective when they have an intrinsic interest in, and personally identify with, those activities versus performing tasks because they must in order to receive verbal or monetary rewards. It is a question of workers engaging in collaboration and cooperation on the one hand and producing mere compliance on the other. Also, when targets are forced through quotas, employees find ways to get the desired results even if a few ethical corners are cut and the quality of the work suffers. Hence, complying with targets might lead to a 'check-the-box' mentality. Even though the worker gets the job done - checks the box, clients may suffer because the quality of the service may be lacking. But what does this do to long-term client relationships and value co-creation? This also fits squarely in the camp of concerns having to do with ethical lapses compromising one's fiduciary duty (compliance logics) because of sales logics.
Item 16	Because at least some of my performance targets are not reasonable it is demotivating.	X		X	Are the targets fair? If the perception of targets are that they are onerous or unfair, morale may be adversely affected. Employees may be tempted, or feel pressure, to cut ethical corners in order to ensure they achieve compliance with the targets. In so doing, their focus shifts away from being client-centered to concern about achieving targets, sometimes by whatever means necessary. Among other drawbacks, this may compromise the quality of service / advice provided to clients. Targets in the context of the organization have to do with sales logics which are in tension with fiduciary duty (compliance logics) and the potential effect on the quality of the work speaks to tensions with service logics.

Item No.	Q-item / Statement	Sales logics	Service logics	Compliance logics	Rationale for Statement
Item 17	Having a big target can lead to a 'check-the-box-mentality' where the quality of the work can be secondary to getting it done.	X		X	To what extent is the quality of work affected because of the volume required? Is client care compromised? If so, this creates a conflict of interest between the need to achieve the target and the quality of the advice or service provided. This falls into the sales logics category being in tension with fiduciary duty (compliance logics) and the potential effect on the quality of the work speaks to tensions with service logics.
Item 18	Concern about getting good Client Promoter Scores may sometimes make me think twice about disagreeing with a client or delivering news that might be perceived negatively.	X		X	Does the pressure to achieve high Client Promoter Score (CPS) targets create conflicts of interest with clients because advisors might not feel comfortable in delivering unwelcome, but perhaps important information for fear of a low score or possible unenrollment that might follow a frank discussion? In this context the primary tensions are between sales logics - keeping clients happy even to their detriment and one's obligation to act as a fiduciary (compliance logics).

Item No.	Q-item / Statement	Sales logics	Service logics	Compliance logics	Rationale for Statement
Item 19	As long as I were well paid, if I didn't have performance targets I would be motivated anyway because I find the work I do is important and personally gratifying.	X	X		To what degree are advisors intrinsically motivated? According to self-determination theory, some workers are motivated more by intrinsic factors and demotivated by extrinsic factors such as goals, quotas and targets. In a business whose main purpose is (or should be) helping people, having workers with an intrinsic desire to do the work is more powerful and effective than having workers performing job functions mainly for the pay rather than for a desire to fulfil a personal mission to serve others, notwithstanding being sufficiently compensated. The tension here is between service to others (service logics) and self-motivation more closely associated with sales (sales logics).
Item 20	The only way to allocate bonuses fairly is through specific measurable performance targets.	X	X		This statement is intended to determine the degree to which advisors are motivated by extrinsic factors. Are there different ways to be fairly compensated beyond specific measurable targets? Those who do not think there are other fair ways to earn what you are worth tend to favor being paid in some way that differentiates compensation based on the workers contribution relative to peers. "If I accomplish more, I should earn more" is the sentiment. This can form healthy competition and innovation, but it can also lead to individuals working in silos and not working for the common good when doing so would be beneficial for the organization. The main tensions here are between sales and service logics.
Item 21	If we were really 'looking through client's eyes', it would be best to tie bonuses to how well clients are doing toward achieving their financial goals.	X	X		Do advisors feel strongly enough about the company's stated goal and the quality of service they should aspire to provide to clients enough to 'put their money where their mouths are?' Should service to the client, and the degree to which they are successful, trump other considerations, for instance achieving goals, quotas and targets? This statement speaks to the tension between sales and service logics.

Item No.	Q-item / Statement	Sales logics	Service logics	Compliance logics	Rationale for Statement
Item 22	It is best to tie bonuses to how many financial plans and single topic solutions my clients receive.	X		X	Do advisors feel being paid and having their performance judged based on what some PCAs consider ancillary activities desirable? The message this sends is that PCAs are not professionals. Instead, they are paid based on piecework, like line factory workers, rather than on the important work of ensuring favorable client outcomes. Do PCAs believe the company is incenting the accomplishment of relatively insignificant activities as opposed to the broader aspect of overall client success? Do PCAs feel less professional than they might otherwise? This statement highlights the tension between sales logics and professionalism associated with fiduciary responsibilities (fiduciary /compliance logics).
Item 23	It is best to tie bonuses to how well the company performed.	X	X		Do advisors have a strong sense of teamwork? Do they make a connection between their personal success with that of the company? Or are they content with working in silos where success depends upon individual contribution alone? If the company is not successful, how long will it be before an otherwise successful employee may have to look for other employment because while everyone did their part individually, the organization as a whole didn't succeed. The tension here is between perceived self-interest and service to others - the organization as a whole.
Item 24	Sometimes an employees' contribution to the firm's business is not fully reflected in their production numbers.	X	X		How do advisors feel about the performance evaluation process? Sometimes numbers do not tell the whole story. Do PCAs feel fairly evaluated based on the circumstances they were presented with, such as life events, natural disasters, other organizational changes that may have been unexpected? Or is the achievement of goals, targets, quotas the only thing that determines a worker's true contribution to the firm?

Item No.	Q-item / Statement	Sales logics	Service logics	Compliance logics	Rationale for Statement
Item 25	Prospects and clients might wonder if they would receive adequate attention if they knew I have responsibility for 185 clients.	X	X	X	Advisors are reluctant to divulge how many clients they have for fear of alienating existing clients / prospects. This is an ethical issue in itself and speaks to the level of service that can be provided against the pressure to grow the practice to a theoretically unlimited size. This statement demonstrates the tensions between 1) sales logics in the sense of the need to attract and retain new investors while not wishing to lose a sale if clients knew how many clients the PCA is responsible for. 2) service logics in the sense of having responsibility for too many clients leads to difficulties in maintaining high levels of service quality and 3) if PCAs lie or sidestep answering this question it strains their duty as fiduciaries (compliance logics).
Item 26	I feel I can easily control which clients I work with and which ones to remove from my practice.	X		X	This statement has to do with self-determination, autonomy and conflicts of interest when advisors feel forced to work with clients for whom the offer is unsuitable. The question of suitability is strong related to fiduciary duty and therefore this a compliance logics issue and how compliance logics are in tension with sales logics where it is important to retain and add new clients.
Item 27	I sometimes have to depend on FCs for referrals whose focus on sales may require me to work with clients for whom the PCA offer may not be well suited.	X		X	Feeling forced to work with clients whom the advisor feels the offer is inappropriate creates a conflict of interest between the best interest of the client and the need to achieve sales goals. This forms tension between sales and fiduciary /compliance logics.

Item No.	Q-item / Statement	Sales logics	Service logics	Compliance logics	Rationale for Statement
Item 28	There are too many PCAs competing with each other to cover the same branch locations.	X		X	Too many salespeople may be a catalyst for healthy competition and innovation but can also lead to advisors cutting ethical corners (compliance logics) by overpromising and under-delivering to internal and external clients in order to gain a business edge. In the retail store environment this is known as 'stacking the floor'. In department stores, management might decide to put far more salesclerks on the floor than business expectations might suggest are actually needed leading to cut-throat tactics to garner the next customers' sale. People in this situation complain about the role being a 'beauty contest' and those who are literally too slow on their feet might not last in the role. Advisors put in essentially the same situation may feel degraded and used. Morale suffers. There simply may not be enough business to go round and they know, or feel they know, that the company is aware of this. This leads workers to view the company's management as callous in spite of lofty mission, vision and value statements. In doing so, the company management may be thought to be hypocritical.
Item 29	Having to please FCs can sometimes lead me to have to compromise my ethical standards at least a little.	X		X	This statement is intended to understand the influence of FCs on advisor ethics (compliance logics). Do PCAs feel they must cut ethical corners to be successful (sales logics)? Hence, compliance logics and sales logics are in tension with one another.
Item 30	My performance targets do a good job of measuring how well I serve clients	X	X		This statement is intended to understand the fairness of incentives and to what degree those incentives enhance or detract from incentivizing PCAs to support favorable client experiences. Do the performance targets put so much emphasis on sales that it takes away from high quality service because people may be working in silos and /or have to check-the-box to say they got the job done? Or do extrinsic factors associated with the targets, goals, quotas carry favor with PCAs and support how well they serve clients? The natural tension here is between sales and service logics.
Item 31	As a fiduciary, I have too many clients to serve them all well.	X	X	X	This statement is intended to understand the degree to which the workload impedes the delivery of proper advice. Does the workload result in a conflict of interest whereby PCAs must choose between providing good service to a limited group of clients or rationalize lesser quality service in order to continue to grow their practice to theoretically an unlimited number? This statement touches on fiduciary duty (fiduciary / compliance logics), the ability to provide proper service (service logics) on the one hand and the mandate to continue to grow individual practices indefinitely (sales logics).

Item No.	Q-item / Statement	Sales logics	Service logics	Compliance logics	Rationale for Statement
Item 32	PCAs should be allowed to 'soft-close' and / or re-open their practice as desired based upon workload.	X	X	X	This statement is intended to understand the importance of self-determination and autonomy and the degree to which advisors are required to continue to grow their practice (sales logics). It also underscores concerns about their ability to properly serve (service logics) their clients as professionals having fiduciary duty (compliance logics). The tension here is between service logics and compliance logics on the one hand and sales logics on the other.
Item 33	PCAs may be hesitant to tell an FC about the true nature of their workload because it might discourage getting new referrals.	X		X	This statement is intended to determine the degree to which the practice sizes affect advisor ethics and create conflicts of interest because of the need to sell. The tension here is primarily between the need to sell (sales logics) and the fiduciary requirement to be transparent in all dealings (fiduciary /compliance logics).
Item 34	It is awkward when a client asks, "How often do you review my investments?" because the real answer may not seem like it would be often enough to them.	X	X	X	This statement is intended to determine the impact of having excessive clients on the ability of advisors to adequately serve their clients and the ethics of having to avoid such questions or worse, to hedge or lie. This statement places the need to sell (sales logics) in tension with the ability to provide adequate levels of service (service logics) along with the need to be transparent associated with fiduciary duty (fiduciary / compliance logics).

Item No.	Q-item / Statement	Sales logics	Service logics	Compliance logics	Rationale for Statement
Item 35	My success depends heavily on getting new referrals from FCs so I should be careful not to contradict or alienate them.	X	X	X	To what extent to PCAs have to pander to the wishes of FCs? Do PCAs forego conversations that have a bearing on working in the best interest of the firm or clients? This statement has to do with the difficulty that arises from too strong a sales culture with not enough emphasis on service and fiduciary /compliance.
Item 36	I feel my role is sales oriented because I have to sell myself to FCs and sell myself to clients.	X			This statement is intended to understand the degree to which sales is the dominant logic.

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Table A-1

Correlation Matrix Between Sorts																					
SORTS	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21
1 I3425	100	61	58	67	50	42	50	48	43	55	54	57	50	45	56	63	45	42	35	73	52
2 I4699	61	100	50	42	53	58	29	57	50	53	26	51	51	46	45	46	63	42	29	61	66
3 I4729	58	50	100	40	39	59	36	52	45	41	26	50	47	38	42	49	43	43	27	54	45
4 I5809	67	42	40	100	39	35	50	46	47	58	50	54	41	35	59	42	42	41	34	47	47
5 I5856	50	53	39	39	100	51	26	40	34	35	29	24	23	26	41	47	36	29	15	46	36
6 I5871	42	58	59	35	51	100	17	42	21	40	11	48	43	30	58	54	37	27	26	35	32
7 I5876	50	29	36	50	26	17	100	50	43	60	58	37	27	35	37	46	28	60	28	66	46
8 I5912	48	57	52	46	40	42	50	100	68	63	59	45	61	65	51	49	53	61	59	57	55
9 I6132	43	50	45	47	34	21	43	68	100	50	69	43	60	59	26	32	59	63	55	48	72
10 I6135	55	53	41	58	35	40	60	63	50	100	56	54	50	63	46	34	47	54	53	58	62
11 I6200	54	26	26	50	29	11	58	59	69	56	100	38	30	49	32	42	43	55	64	52	62
12 I7512	57	51	50	54	24	48	37	45	43	54	38	100	44	36	50	24	42	40	37	46	48
13 I7992	50	51	47	41	23	43	27	61	60	50	30	44	100	50	29	42	31	28	58	49	29
14 I8053	45	46	38	35	26	30	35	65	59	63	49	36	50	100	41	36	48	58	49	60	49
15 I8099	56	45	42	59	41	58	37	51	26	46	32	50	29	41	100	42	43	36	32	45	39
16 I9984	63	46	49	42	47	54	46	49	32	34	42	24	42	36	42	100	29	36	35	66	33
17 I10123	45	63	43	42	36	37	28	53	59	47	43	42	31	48	43	29	100	58	33	42	72
18 I10238	42	42	43	41	29	27	60	61	63	54	55	40	28	58	36	36	58	100	30	49	70
19 I10318	35	29	27	34	15	26	28	59	55	53	64	37	58	49	32	35	33	30	100	30	42
20 I10788	73	61	54	47	46	35	66	57	48	58	52	46	49	60	45	66	42	49	30	100	46
21 I10789	52	66	45	47	36	32	46	55	72	62	62	48	29	49	39	33	72	70	42	46	100

Table 1 illustrates the correlation matrix between sorts. What this means is that from this matrix one can see how each Q sort correlates with every other Q sort. For example, Sort 10 and I6135 are one and the same Q sort. Therefore, they are perfectly correlated at 100. Now, taking sort 10 and seeing how it correlates with Sort 1 I3425 you can see they intersect at 55. Hence, Q sort 10 and 1 I3425 resemble each other by approximately 55%.

Table A-2

Unrotated Factor Matrix		Factors							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
SORTS									
1	I3425	0.7873	0.2420	0.2548	-0.0665	0.0804	-0.0069	-0.2820	-0.1140
2	I4699	0.7437	0.2795	-0.2601	0.2321	-0.1361	-0.0539	-0.1642	-0.2573
3	I4729	0.6729	0.3145	-0.1018	0.0111	-0.0794	-0.3096	-0.0641	0.4049
4	I5809	0.6964	0.0852	0.2327	-0.0183	0.4203	0.1432	-0.1828	-0.0511
5	I5856	0.5520	0.4042	0.0999	0.1861	-0.2702	0.4095	-0.0666	-0.1264
6	I5871	0.5805	0.6051	-0.2536	-0.0206	0.0175	0.0710	0.2384	0.2013
7	I5876	0.6399	-0.2004	0.5774	-0.0223	0.0202	-0.2121	0.0927	0.0911
8	I5912	0.8137	-0.1492	-0.1508	-0.1397	-0.1323	0.0190	0.2095	0.0551
9	I6132	0.7534	-0.4080	-0.2070	0.0475	-0.1423	0.0347	-0.2349	0.1075
10	I6135	0.7817	-0.1567	0.0277	-0.0637	0.2028	-0.0838	0.1573	-0.2481
11	I6200	0.6942	-0.4771	0.2473	-0.0893	0.0202	0.3070	-0.0896	0.1178
12	I7512	0.6640	0.1262	-0.1247	0.0125	0.5106	-0.2335	-0.1400	0.0648
13	I7992	0.6452	0.0396	-0.3546	-0.5100	-0.0729	-0.1756	-0.2015	-0.0653
14	I8053	0.7045	-0.2363	-0.1597	-0.1069	-0.1581	-0.1413	0.3332	-0.3214
15	I8099	0.6466	0.3344	0.0682	0.0272	0.3564	0.1962	0.3774	-0.0283
16	I9984	0.6419	0.3217	0.2875	-0.2485	-0.3666	0.1293	0.0104	0.1739
17	I10123	0.6866	-0.0890	-0.2715	0.4670	-0.0220	0.0813	-0.0247	-0.0278
18	I10238	0.7088	-0.3153	0.0984	0.3358	-0.1029	-0.1683	0.2259	0.1953
19	I10318	0.5952	-0.3404	-0.2670	-0.4706	0.0946	0.3120	0.0318	0.1073
20	I10788	0.7795	0.1067	0.3263	-0.0951	-0.2385	-0.2352	-0.0505	-0.2206
21	I10789	0.7645	-0.2544	-0.0997	0.4338	0.0115	0.0686	-0.1123	0.0604
Eigenvalues		10.1882	1.8413	1.2576	1.2119	0.9904	0.7928	0.7273	0.6461
% expl.Var.		49	9	6	6	5	4	3	3

A Q sort is the result produced by participants after they have sorted the stimuli (statements) on the distribution model. A ‘factor’ represents clusters of people who sorted their Q statements similarly. They think similarly about the topic.

Table 2 shows these factor loadings, or factor saturations as they are also called. They illustrate the extent to which each Q sort exemplifies or is typical of the factor on which it is loaded. For example, 62% of the variance (commonality) in Q sort 1 is representative of Factor 1 in its entirety. The percentage is calculated by squaring the factor loading as follows: $0.7873 \times 0.7873 = 62\%$.

Eigenvalues are listed at the next to the last row. Eigenvalues help to determine what factors to include in the study and which ones to discard. “Low factor eigenvalues (EVs) specifically, EVs of less than 1.00 are often taken as a cut-off point for the extraction and retention of factors. This is called the Kaiser-Guttman criterion” (Watts and Stenner 2012, P.106). As an alternative, Watts and Stenner (2012) suggests extracting one factor for approximately every 6 – 8 participants. Hence, based on having 21 participants in this study, the top three factors are the ones used for further analysis. Factor 1 refers to the first shared pattern or sorting configuration in the data. When the Q sorts that comprise Factor 1 are

extracted (removed from the study) the commonality that remains is represented by Factor 2. When the Q sorts that comprise factor two are removed, the remaining Q sorts with common characteristics are reflected in Factor 3.

The eigenvalues shown on the next to the last line of the table are a measure of the strength of the commonality within each factor. A factors' eigenvalue is calculated by summing the squared loadings of all the Q sorts on that factor. The eigenvalue for Factor 1 is calculated as follows:

Step 1: Square each loading for each factor

For Factor 1: $0.7873^2 + 0.7437^2 + 0.6729^2 \dots$ and so on until you have finished squaring each loading number.

Step 2: Add each of the squared numbers together

$= 0.6198 + 0.5531 + 0.4528 \dots$ and so on until you have finished adding each squared number.

The result is called the eigenvalue. For factor 1 the eigenvalue is 10.1882. An eigenvalue of at least 1 is considered significant and therefore possibly worth considering including in the final analysis.

The variance for Factor 1 is 49, meaning that it represents 49% of the commonality among all Q sorts for the entire study. This percentage is calculated:

Variance for Factor 1 = $100 \times (\text{EV} / \text{no. of Q sorts in Study})$

$= 100 \times (10.1882 / 21)$

$= 100 \times 0.485$

$= 48.5152 =$ variance or 49% rounded. Hence, Factor 1 accounts for 49% of the common variance present in the study and therefore almost half of everything that the Q sorts have in common. The first three factors in this study account for 64% (49 + 9 + 6) of commonality. Ideally, percentage above 35% to 40% or higher is considered sound. (Watts, 2012).

Table A-3

Cumulative Communalities Matrix								
	Factors 1 Thru							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
SORTS								
1 I3425	0.6199	0.6785	0.7434	0.7478	0.7543	0.7543	0.8339	0.8468
2 I4699	0.5531	0.6312	0.6989	0.7528	0.7713	0.7742	0.8012	0.8674
3 I4729	0.4528	0.5517	0.5621	0.5622	0.5685	0.6644	0.6685	0.8324
4 I5809	0.4849	0.4922	0.5464	0.5467	0.7234	0.7439	0.7773	0.7799
5 I5856	0.3047	0.4680	0.4780	0.5126	0.5856	0.7533	0.7578	0.7737
6 I5871	0.3370	0.7031	0.7674	0.7678	0.7682	0.7732	0.8300	0.8705
7 I5876	0.4095	0.4497	0.7831	0.7836	0.7840	0.8291	0.8376	0.8459
8 I5912	0.6620	0.6843	0.7070	0.7265	0.7440	0.7444	0.7883	0.7913
9 I6132	0.5675	0.7340	0.7768	0.7791	0.7993	0.8005	0.8557	0.8673
10 I6135	0.6111	0.6357	0.6364	0.6405	0.6816	0.6886	0.7134	0.7749
11 I6200	0.4819	0.7095	0.7707	0.7787	0.7791	0.8733	0.8814	0.8953
12 I7512	0.4409	0.4568	0.4723	0.4725	0.7332	0.7877	0.8073	0.8115
13 I7992	0.4162	0.4178	0.5436	0.8037	0.8090	0.8398	0.8804	0.8847
14 I8053	0.4963	0.5522	0.5777	0.5891	0.6141	0.6341	0.7451	0.8484
15 I8099	0.4181	0.5299	0.5345	0.5352	0.6622	0.7007	0.8431	0.8439
16 I9984	0.4120	0.5155	0.5981	0.6599	0.7943	0.8110	0.8111	0.8413
17 I10123	0.4715	0.4794	0.5531	0.7712	0.7717	0.7783	0.7789	0.7797
18 I10238	0.5024	0.6018	0.6115	0.7243	0.7349	0.7632	0.8142	0.8523
19 I10318	0.3542	0.4701	0.5414	0.7628	0.7718	0.8691	0.8701	0.8816
20 I10788	0.6076	0.6190	0.7255	0.7345	0.7914	0.8467	0.8493	0.8979
21 I10789	0.5845	0.6492	0.6592	0.8473	0.8475	0.8522	0.8648	0.8684
cum% expl.Var.	49	57	63	69	74	78	81	84

Table 3 illustrates the cumulative communalities matrix. The communality of each Q sort is calculated by summing its squared factor loadings. Q sort communality is calculated as follows:

From Table 2:

The Q sort 1 loadings for each factor are:

<u>F1</u>	<u>F2</u>	<u>F3</u>	<u>F4</u>	<u>F5</u>	<u>F6</u>	<u>F7</u>	<u>F8</u>
0.7873	0.2420	0.2548		-0.0665	0.0804	-0.0069	-0.2820 -0.1140

The squares for each Q sort 1 loading are then summed:

$0.6198 + 0.0586 + 0.0649 + 0.0044 + 0.0065 + 0.00005 + 0.0795 + 0.0130 =$ the cumulative number: 0.8468

The communality for Q sort 1 is .8468 shown as the accumulated number in column 8 in Table 3. This is telling us that nearly 85% of the variance (commonality) in Q sort 1 has been accounted for by the study factors. Or, in other words, that 85% of the variance in Q-sort 1 is common variance. Hence it is highly representative of the entire study because it holds much in common with all the other Q sorts.

Table A-4

Factor Matrix with an X Indicating a Defining Sort			
	Loadings		
QSORT	1	2	3
1 I3425	0.2558	0.6146X	0.5479
2 I4699	0.4591	0.6943X	0.0780
3 I4729	0.3146	0.6580X	0.1735
4 I5809	0.2959	0.4394	0.5155
5 I5856	0.0847	0.6300X	0.2719
6 I5871	0.1632	0.8589X	-0.0561
7 I5876	0.2516	0.1278	0.8388X
8 I5912	0.6952X	0.3760	0.2868
9 I6132	0.8304X	0.1421	0.2590
10 I6135	0.5907X	0.3254	0.4262
11 I6200	0.6071	-0.0139	0.6339X
12 I7512	0.4271	0.5055X	0.1854
13 I7992	0.5771X	0.4587	-0.0044
14 I8053	0.6773X	0.2441	0.2437
15 I8099	0.2023	0.6338X	0.3031
16 I9984	0.0985	0.5890X	0.4914
17 I10123	0.6367X	0.3679	0.1112
18 I10238	0.5980X	0.1458	0.4823
19 I10318	0.7172X	0.1129	0.1193
20 I10788	0.2924	0.4914	0.6313X
21 I10789	0.6976X	0.2558	0.3272
% expl. Var.	25	22	16

The researcher used Principal Component Analysis (PCA) as the method for factor extraction and Varimax as the choice of factor rotation methods. PCA is commonly used in Q methodology and is available with most statistical computer programs. This method analyzes all the commonality in the Q sorts. PCA extracts uncorrelated linear combinations of the observed Q sorts (Akhtar-Danesh, 2017). Table 4 illustrates that what this means is PCA identifies those Q sorts that exemplify a given factor to a statistically sufficient degree. The first factor explains the highest level of variance (commonality) in the dataset and is then removed or in the parlance of Q methodology, ‘extracted’ from the dataset leaving the residual Q sorts to be compared for commonality (variance). The second factor explains the second highest level of variance of the remaining Q sorts; this process is continued until all of the variance in the dataset is accounted for by the factors.

Applying the parameters just described using PCA and Varimax, the PQ Method software program utilized in this study automatically requires a factor loading of at least 0.50 in order to qualify as a ‘defining’ sort. Meaning a Q sort that, from a statistical standpoint, matters enough to be included on a given factor. It is in this sense it helps ‘define’ the factor.

As has been shown, factor loadings have been expressed as correlations. These correlations can also be expressed as coordinates on a graph. This allows for mapping the relative positions, or viewpoints, of all the Q sorts in the study.

In a typical graph you have a vertical and horizontal axis positioned at a 90° angle to each other (orthogonal). To help understand the data more fully it can help to rotate the factors. What is meant by rotation is rotating both axis while keeping the same 90° angle, so that both axis have a chance to cross through an area where the bulk of the coordinates are plotted on the graph. The importance of this is that the process of rotation allows the researcher to view the Q sorts from a different, more useful angle. Varimax is the most common rotation method used in statistical analysis. It maximizes the variance of each factor loading by making high loadings higher and low loadings lower to simplify factor interpretation (Akhtar-Danesh, 2017).

The result of factor extraction and rotation in Table 4 shows that 9 Q defining sorts that were loaded on Factor 1, indicated by the 'X' situated just to the right of the relevant Q sort identifier. For Factor 2 there are 8 defining Q sorts and for Factor 3, there are 3 defining Q sorts.

Factors 1, 2 & 3 explain a robust 63% of the study variance (25% + 22% + 16% taken from the bottom of Table 4). This was a similar result as we noted in Table 2 where the first three factors explain 64% of the study. In this case there does not appear that there was a great deal of difference in the rotated versus unrotated factor analysis, but this will not always be the case.

Table A-5

Free Distribution Data Results		
QSORT	MEAN	ST.DEV.
1 I3425	0.000	2.449
2 I4699	0.000	2.449
3 I4729	0.000	2.449
4 I5809	0.000	2.449
5 I5856	0.000	2.449
6 I5871	0.000	2.449
7 I5876	0.000	2.449
8 I5912	0.000	2.449
9 I6132	0.000	2.449
10 I6135	0.000	2.449
11 I6200	0.000	2.449
12 I7512	0.000	2.449
13 I7992	0.000	2.449
14 I8053	0.000	2.449
15 I8099	0.000	2.449
16 I9984	0.000	2.449
17 I10123	0.000	2.449
18 I10238	0.000	2.449
19 I10318	0.000	2.449
20 I10788	0.000	2.449
21 I10789	0.000	2.449

Table 5 illustrates Free Distribution Data Results. As noted earlier, Factor 1 has 9 defining Q sorts loaded on it. Factor 2 has 8 and Factor 3 has 3 defining Q sorts loaded on it. “Because the different factors have a different number of Q sorts loaded on each it is difficult to make cross-factor comparisons. This means the totals cannot represent a level playing field. In order to facilitate cross-factor comparisons, therefore, the total scores must be converted to z (or standard) scores” (Watts, 2012, p. 139).

To create z scores, the individual Q sorts that were "flagged" with an X, as the best representatives of the factor, are aggregated or "averaged" into one set of statement scores. The exact computational procedure consists in first z-standardizing every sort, and then applying different weights for every sort depending on the sort's factor loading and computing the weighted average. Finally, every factor score is z-standardized again, i.e. every factor score has the same mean (0) and standard deviation (2.449), and hence scores are directly comparable across factors (Schmolck, 2014).

Table A-6

Factor Scores with Corresponding Ranks								
No.	Statement	No.	Factors					
			1	2	3			
1	A focus on planning may sometimes be a way of deflec	1	0.03	20	0.07	19	-0.66	29
2	Management expresses concern and /or interest about	2	-1.44	32	-1.18	30	-2.03	36
3	Because of my workload I sometimes worry about the	3	1.58	3	-0.09	21	1.27	3
4	I would work with less stress and be more effective.	4	-0.05	21	0.51	14	-0.10	17
5	My main motivation for working is to help as many in	5	-0.41	24	2.14	1	-0.20	20
6	My main motivation for working is for me to succeed	6	-0.23	23	0.36	18	-0.83	30
7	My main motivation for working is to get praise from	7	-1.52	34	-1.66	35	-1.69	34
8	My main motivation for working is to help the compan	8	-0.96	28	0.02	20	-1.10	31
9	PCAs may be reluctant to 'fire' a client because of	9	0.63	10	0.46	16	1.10	4
10	1The thing my clients say matters most to them are	10	-0.70	26	-0.67	26	-0.36	25
11	The thing my clients say matters most to them is th	11	0.03	19	0.55	11	-0.33	24
12	I must keep in mind as important that clients equat	12	0.23	16	-0.81	27	0.53	12
13	I must keep in mind as important that clients equat	13	-0.07	22	-0.26	23	0.27	15
14	Adhering to compliance rules is onerous and unprodu	14	-1.15	31	-1.60	34	-0.20	19
15	Having a performance target for financial planning	15	-1.46	33	-0.94	28	-0.40	27
16	Because at least some of my performance targets are	16	0.56	11	0.53	12	0.93	8
17	Having a big target can lead to a 'check-the-box-me	17	1.13	6	0.57	10	1.86	2
18	Concern about getting good Client Promoter Scores	18	-0.47	25	-1.18	31	-1.20	32
19	As long as I were well paid if I didn't have perfo	19	1.59	2	0.51	13	0.47	14
20	The only way to allocate bonuses fairly is through	20	0.14	18	-0.65	25	-0.56	28
21	If we were reallylooking through clients eyes it	21	0.46	13	1.01	6	-0.37	26
22	It is best to tie bonuses to how many financial pla	22	-1.84	36	-1.33	32	-0.30	22
23	It is best to tie bonuses to how well the company	23	-1.03	30	0.47	15	-1.66	33
24	Sometimes an employees contribution to the firm	24	0.94	7	1.38	2	0.73	11
25	Prospects and clients might wonder if they will rec	25	1.13	5	-0.28	24	1.06	6
26	I feel I can easily control which clients I work	26	-1.00	29	-1.86	36	-1.76	35
27	I sometimes have to depend on FCs for referrals who	27	0.31	15	1.03	5	0.50	13
28	There are too many PCAs competing with each other	28	0.35	14	1.23	3	1.03	7
29	Having to please FCs can sometimes lead me to have	29	-0.92	27	-1.08	29	-0.27	21
30	My performance targets do a good job of measuring	30	-1.53	35	-1.36	33	-0.03	16
31	As a fiduciary I have too many clients to serve the	31	1.73	1	1.21	4	-0.13	18
32	PCAs should be allowed to soft-close and or re-open	32	0.55	12	0.39	17	0.86	10
33	PCAs may be hesitant to tell an FC about the true	33	0.90	8	0.97	7	0.90	9
34	It is awkward when a client asks,How often do you	34	1.43	4	-0.14	22	-0.33	23
35	My success depends heavily on getting new referral	35	0.17	17	0.92	8	1.10	5
36	I feel my role is sales oriented because I have to	36	0.88	9	0.77	9	1.93	1

In Table 6 the first column shows the statement number. In the next column the statement is listed. The statement as been truncated because of space constraints. The full statements are shown in the appendix of this document. In the next column the statement number is shown again to make readability of the data easier. Next, Factors 1,2 and 3 are listed. Under each of the three Factor headings are two columns. The column on the left is the z score for the statement and the column on the right is that statements rank among all the statements of that particular Factor.

This Table 6 offers a comparison of how a particular Q item (statement) has been ranked or valued by each of the three study Factors and uses z scores to accomplish this. We can see,

for example, that statement number 31 has a very positive z score in the context of Factor 1 of 1.73 and it has been ranked highest among all the statements by this Factor as indicated by the number 1 shown in the column next to the z score. However, in the context of Factor 3 the same item has a negative z score of -0.13. Factor 3 has ranked this item 18th of the 36 items in the Q set.

Table A-7

Correlations Between Factor Scores			
	1	2	3
1	1.0000	0.6294	0.6724
2	0.6294	1.0000	0.4998
3	0.6724	0.4998	1.0000

Table 7 shows the extent to which each of the Factor arrays intercorrelate. All Factors have at least something in common. Factors 2 and 3 have the least in common at 0.4998. Whereas Factors 1 and three are more closely associated. At 0.6724. Correlations are fairly high considering .50 is considered a significant factor loading on the study. The correlations are not so high, though, as to undermine the distinctiveness of each factor.

Table A-8

Factor Scores -- For Factor 1			
No.	Statement	No.	Z-SCORES
31	As a fiduciary I have too many clients to serve them all	31	1.730
19	As long as I were well paid if I didn't have performance	19	1.593
3	Because of my workload I sometimes worry about the possibi	3	1.579
34	It is awkward when a client asks, How often do you review	34	1.430
25	Prospects and clients might wonder if they will receive a	25	1.135
17	Having a big target can lead to a check-the-box-mentalit	17	1.132
24	Sometimes an employees contribution to the firms bus	24	0.942
33	PCAs may be hesitant to tell an FC about the true nature	33	0.904
36	I feel my role is sales oriented because I have to sell	36	0.881
9	PCAs may be reluctant to 'fire' a client because of the	9	0.628
16	Because at least some of my performance targets are not	16	0.556
32	PCAs should be allowed to soft-close and or re-open their	32	0.550
21	If we were really looking through clients eyes it would be	21	0.457
28	There are too many PCAs competing with each other to cove	28	0.353
27	I sometimes have to depend on FCs for referrals whose focus	27	0.314
12	I must keep in mind as important that clients equate trading	12	0.234
35	My success depends heavily on getting new referral from	35	0.168
20	The only way to allocate bonuses fairly is through specific	20	0.136
11	The thing my clients say matters most to them is the perform	11	0.033
1	A focus on planning may sometimes be a way of deflecting	1	0.032
4	I would work with less stress and be more effective if I did	4	-0.054
13	I must keep in mind as important that clients equate inactiv	13	-0.068
6	My main motivation for working is for me to succeed	6	-0.231
5	My main motivation for working is to help as many investors	5	-0.412
18	Concern about getting good Client Promoter Scores may some	18	-0.469
10	The thing my clients say matters most to them are broad finan	10	-0.698
29	Having to please FCs can sometimes lead me to have to comprom	29	-0.922
8	My main motivation for working is to help the company succ	8	-0.959
26	I feel I can easily control which clients I work with and	26	-1.001
23	It is best to tie bonuses to how well the company perform	23	-1.033
14	Adhering to compliance rules is onerous and unproductive	14	-1.149
2	Management expresses concern and /or interest about indivi	2	-1.439
15	Having a performance target for financial planning and single	15	-1.460
7	My main motivation for working is to get praise from my boss	7	-1.521
30	My performance targets do a good job of measuring how well	30	-1.527
22	It is best to tie bonuses to how many financial plans and	22	-1.842

Table 8 illustrates the z scores that have been calculated for each statement for Factor 1. Calculation of the z scores allows for cross-factor item comparisons. The ranking of the statements in this table is also used to create of the final array for Factor 1. Statements have been listed so that they are ranked with the ones most agreed upon at the top and descending to most common disagreement.

For Factor 1 the main area of agreement was statement 31: “As a fiduciary I have too many clients to serve them all well.” The main consensus around disagreement was statement 22: “It is best to tie bonuses to how many financial plans and single topic solutions my clients receive.”

Table A-9

Factor Scores -- For Factor 2			
No.	Statement	No.	Z-SCORES
5	My main motivation for working is to help as many investor	5	2.144
24	Sometimes an employees contribution to the firms business	24	1.376
28	There are too many PCAs competing with each other to cove	28	1.231
31	As a fiduciary I have too many clients to serve them all	31	1.209
27	I sometimes have to depend on FCs for referrals whose focus	27	1.031
21	If we were reallylooking through clients eyes it would be	21	1.008
33	PCAs may be hesitant to tell an FC about the true nature	33	0.973
35	My success depends heavily on getting new referral from	35	0.922
36	I feel my role is sales oriented because I have to sell	36	0.769
17	Having a big target can lead to a 'check-the-box-mentalit	17	0.572
11	The thing my clients say matters most to them is the perf	11	0.550
16	Because at least some of my performance targets are not	16	0.528
19	Aslong as I were well paid if I didn't have performance	19	0.512
4	I would work with less stress and be more effective if I	4	0.508
23	It is best to tie bonuses to how well the company perform	23	0.465
9	PCAs may be reluctant to 'fire' a client because of the	9	0.456
32	PCAs should be allowed to soft-close and or re-open their	32	0.391
6	My main motivation for working is for me to succeed	6	0.357
1	A focus on planning may sometimes be a way of deflecting	1	0.071
8	My main motivation for working is to help the company succ	8	0.020
3	Because of my workload I sometimes worry about the possibi	3	-0.088
34	It is awkward when a client asks,How often do you review	34	-0.142
13	I must keep in mind as important that clients equate inac	13	-0.260
25	Prospects and clients might wonder if they will receive a	25	-0.282
20	The only way to allocate bonuses fairly is through specif	20	-0.651
10	The thing my clients say matters most to them are broad	10	-0.672
12	I must keep in mind as important that clients equate trad	12	-0.810
15	Having a performance target for financial planning and	15	-0.941
29	Having to please FCs can sometimes lead me to have to com	29	-1.084
2	Management expresses concern and /or interest about indivi	2	-1.178
18	Concern about getting good Client Promoter Scores may som	18	-1.178
22	It is best to tie bonuses to how many financial plans and	22	-1.333
30	My performance targets do a good job of measuring how wel	30	-1.359
14	Adhering to compliance rules is onerous and unproductive	14	-1.602
7	My main motivation for working is to get praise from my	7	-1.658
26	I feel I can easily control which clients I work with and	26	-1.856

Table 9 illustrates the character of Factor 2 is different and unique from Factor 1. For Factor 2 the greatest agreement relates to statement 5, “My main motivation for working is to help as many investors succeed as possible.” The statement with the strongest disagreement was number 26, “I feel I can easily control which clients I work with and which ones to remove from my practice.

Factor Scores -- For Factor 3			
No.	Statement	No.	Z-SCORES
36	I feel my role is sales oriented because I have to sell	36	1.929
17	Having a big target can lead to a 'check-the-box-mentality	17	1.861
3	Because of my workload I sometimes worry about the possibi	3	1.266
9	PCAs may be reluctant to 'fire' a client because of the	9	1.097
35	My success depends heavily on getting new referral from	35	1.096
25	Prospects and clients might wonder if they will receive a	25	1.062
28	There are too many PCAs competing with each other to cover	28	1.028
16	Because at least some of my performance targets are not	16	0.928
33	PCAs may be hesitant to tell an FC about the true nature	33	0.898
32	PCAs should be allowed to soft-close and or re-open their	32	0.864
24	Sometimes an employees contribution to the firms business	24	0.733
12	I must keep in mind as important that clients equate trad	12	0.533
27	I sometimes have to depend on FCs for referrals whose focus	27	0.497
19	Aslong as I were well paid if I didnâ€™t have performance	19	0.466
13	I must keep in mind as important that clients equate inac	13	0.267
30	My performance targets do a good job of measuring how well	30	-0.030
4	I would work with less stress and be more effective if I	4	-0.099
31	As a fiduciary I have too many clients to serve them all	31	-0.135
14	Adhering to compliance rules is onerous and unproductive	14	-0.199
5	My main motivation for working is to help as many investor	5	-0.201
29	Having to please FCs can sometimes lead me to have to com	29	-0.267
22	It is best to tie bonuses to how many financial plans and	22	-0.298
34	It is awkward when a client asks,How often do you review	34	-0.333
11	The thing my clients say matters most to them is the perf	11	-0.334
10	The thing my clients say matters most to them are broad	10	-0.364
21	If we were reallylooking through clients eyes it would be	21	-0.368
15	Having a performance target for financial planning and single	15	-0.398
20	The only way to allocate bonuses fairly is through specif	20	-0.562
1	A focus on planning may sometimes be a way of deflecting	1	-0.663
6	My main motivation for working is for me to succeed	6	-0.832
8	My main motivation for working is to help the company succ	8	-1.098
18	Concern about getting good Client Promoter Scores may some	18	-1.197
23	It is best to tie bonuses to how well the company perform	23	-1.663
7	My main motivation for working is to get praise from my	7	-1.694
26	I feel I can easily control which clients I work with and	26	-1.762
2	Management expresses concern and /or interest about indivi	2	-2.027

In viewing Table 10 one observes based on the normalized z scores for Factor 3 the statement rated having most agreement was statement number 36, "I feel my role is sales oriented because I have to sell myself to FCs and sell myself to clients." The statement garnering the most consensus of disagreement was statement number 2, "Management expresses concerns and/or interest about individual PCA investor portfolio performance."

Viewing each of the three Factors it becomes apparent that there are three distinct groups or clusters of viewpoints. Further analysis reflecting upon this distinctiveness is discussed later.

Table A-11

Descending Array of Differences Between Factors 1 and 2					
No.	Statement	No.	Type 1	Type 2	Difference
3	Because of my workload I sometimes worry about the possibi	3	1.579	-0.088	1.666
34	It is awkward when a client asks,How often do you review	34	1.430	-0.142	1.572
25	Prospects and clients might wonder if they will receive a	25	1.135	-0.282	1.417
19	Aslong as I were well paid if I didn't have performance	19	1.593	0.512	1.081
12	I must keep in mind as important that clients equate trad	12	0.234	-0.810	1.044
26	I feel I can easily control which clients I work with and	26	-1.001	-1.856	0.855
20	The only way to allocate bonuses fairly is through specif	20	0.136	-0.651	0.787
18	Concern about getting good Client Promoter Scores may som	18	-0.469	-1.178	0.709
17	Having a big target can lead to a 'check-the-box-mentalit	17	1.132	0.572	0.560
31	As a fiduciary I have too many clients to serve them all	31	1.730	1.209	0.521
14	Adhering to compliance rules is onerous and unproductive	14	-1.149	-1.602	0.453
13	I must keep in mind as important that clients equate inac	13	-0.068	-0.260	0.191
9	PCAs may be reluctant to 'fire' a client because of the	9	0.628	0.456	0.171
29	Having to please FCs can sometimes lead me to have to com	29	-0.922	-1.084	0.161
32	PCAs should be allowed to soft-close and or re-open their	32	0.550	0.391	0.159
7	My main motivation for working is to get praise from my	7	-1.521	-1.658	0.137
36	I feel my role is sales oriented because I have to sell	36	0.881	0.769	0.112
16	Because at least some of my performance targets are not	16	0.556	0.528	0.028
10	The thing my clients say matters most to them are broad	10	-0.698	-0.672	-0.026
1	A focus on planning may sometimes be a way of deflecting	1	0.032	0.071	-0.039
33	PCAs may be hesitant to tell an FC about the true nature	33	0.904	0.973	-0.069
30	My performance targets do a good job of measuring how well	30	-1.527	-1.359	-0.168
2	Management expresses concern and /or interest about indivi	2	-1.439	-1.178	-0.261
24	Sometimes an employees contribution to the firms bus	24	0.942	1.376	-0.434
22	It is best to tie bonuses to how many financial plans and	22	-1.842	-1.333	-0.509
11	The thing my clients say matters most to them is the perf	11	0.033	0.550	-0.517
15	Having a performance target for financial planning and	15	-1.460	-0.941	-0.518
21	If we were reallylooking through clients eyes it would be	21	0.457	1.008	-0.551
4	I would work with less stress and be more effective if I	4	-0.054	0.508	-0.562
6	My main motivation for working is for me to succeed	6	-0.231	0.357	-0.587
27	I sometimes have to depend on FCs for referrals whose focus	27	0.314	1.031	-0.717
35	My success depends heavily on getting new referral from	35	0.168	0.922	-0.754
28	There are too many PCAs competing with each other to cove	28	0.353	1.231	-0.878
8	My main motivation for working is to help the company succ	8	-0.959	0.020	-0.979
23	It is best to tie bonuses to how well the company perform	23	-1.033	0.465	-1.498
5	My main motivation for working is to help as many investor	5	-0.412	2.144	-2.556

Table 11 illustrates the biggest and smallest differences that hold between the item rankings of any particular pair of Factors in the study. This illustrates a comparison between Factors 1 and 2. The software identifies Factor's 1 and 2 as Type 1 and Type 2. A table like this is produced for every possible pair of factors. Table 11 above shows that Factor 1 is much more positive about items 3, 34, 25, and 19 than Factor 2 and that, at the bottom of the table, Factor 2 is much more positive about items 28, 8, 23 and 5 than Factor 1.

Table A-12

Descending Array of Differences Between Factors 1 and 3					
No.	Statement	No.	Type 1	Type 3	Difference
31	As a fiduciary I have too many clients to serve them all	31	1.730	-0.135	1.864
34	It is awkward when a client asks,How often do you review	34	1.430	-0.333	1.763
19	Aslong as I were well paid if I didn't have performance	19	1.593	0.466	1.127
21	If we were reallylooking through clients eyes it would be	21	0.457	-0.368	0.826
26	I feel I can easily control which clients I work with and	26	-1.001	-1.762	0.761
18	Concern about getting good Client Promoter Scores may some	18	-0.469	-1.197	0.728
20	The only way to allocate bonuses fairly is through specif	20	0.136	-0.562	0.698
1	A focus on planning may sometimes be a way of deflecting	1	0.032	-0.663	0.695
23	It is best to tie bonuses to how well the company perform	23	-1.033	-1.663	0.630
6	My main motivation for working is for me to succeed	6	-0.231	-0.832	0.601
2	Management expresses concern and /or interest about indivi	2	-1.439	-2.027	0.588
11	The thing my clients say matters most to them is the perf	11	0.033	-0.334	0.367
3	Because of my workload I sometimes worry about the possibi	3	1.579	1.266	0.313
24	Sometimes an employees contribution to the firms bus	24	0.942	0.733	0.209
7	My main motivation for working is to get praise from my	7	-1.521	-1.694	0.173
8	My main motivation for working is to help the company succ	8	-0.959	-1.098	0.139
25	Prospects and clients might wonder if they will receive	25	1.135	1.062	0.073
4	I would work with less stress and be more effective if I	4	-0.054	-0.099	0.045
33	PCAs may be hesitant to tell an FC about the true nature	33	0.904	0.898	0.006
27	I sometimes have to depend on FCs for referrals whose focus	27	0.314	0.497	-0.183
5	My main motivation for working is to help as many investor	5	-0.412	-0.201	-0.211
12	I must keep in mind as important that clients equate trad	12	0.234	0.533	-0.299
32	PCAs should be allowed to soft-close and or re-open their	32	0.550	0.864	-0.313
10	The thing my clients say matters most to them are broad	10	-0.698	-0.364	-0.334
13	I must keep in mind as important that clients equate inac	13	-0.068	0.267	-0.335
16	Because at least some of my performance targets are not	16	0.556	0.928	-0.372
9	PCAs may be reluctant to 'fire' a client because of the	9	0.628	1.097	-0.469
29	Having to please FCs can sometimes lead me to have to com	29	-0.922	-0.267	-0.655
28	There are too many PCAs competing with each other to cove	28	0.353	1.028	-0.675
17	Having a big target can lead to a 'check-the-box-mentalit	17	1.132	1.861	-0.729
35	My success depends heavily on getting new referral from	35	0.168	1.096	-0.929
14	Adhering to compliance rules is onerous and unproductive	14	-1.149	-0.199	-0.950
36	I feel my role is sales oriented because I have to sell	36	0.881	1.929	-1.048
15	Having a performance target for financial planning and si	15	-1.460	-0.398	-1.061
30	My performance targets do a good job of measuring how wel	30	-1.527	-0.030	-1.497
22	It is best to tie bonuses to how many financial plans and	22	-1.842	-0.298	-1.545

Table 12 illustrates a comparison between Factors 1 and 3. The software identifies Factor's 1 and 3 as Type 1 and Type 3. As noted, a table like this is produced for every possible pair of factors. Table 12 above shows that Factor 1 is much more positive about items 31, 34, and 19 than Factor 3 and that, at the bottom of the table, Factor 3 is much more positive about items 36,15,30, and 22 than Factor 1.

Table A-13

Descending Array of Differences Between Factors 2 and 3					
No.	Statement	No.	Type 2	Type 3	Difference
5	My main motivation for working is to help as many investor	5	2.144	-0.201	2.345
23	It is best to tie bonuses to how well the company perform	23	0.465	-1.663	2.129
21	If we were reallylooking through clients eyes it would be	21	1.008	-0.368	1.376
31	As a fiduciary I have too many clients to serve them all	31	1.209	-0.135	1.344
6	My main motivation for working is for me to succeed	6	0.357	-0.832	1.188
8	My main motivation for working is to help the company succ	8	0.020	-1.098	1.118
11	The thing my clients say matters most to them is the perf	11	0.550	-0.334	0.884
2	Management expresses concern and /or interest about indivi	2	-1.178	-2.027	0.849
1	A focus on planning may sometimes be a way of deflecting	1	0.071	-0.663	0.734
24	Sometimes an employees contribution to the firms bus	24	1.376	0.733	0.643
4	I would work with less stress and be more effective if I	4	0.508	-0.099	0.607
27	I sometimes have to depend on FCs for referrals whose foc	27	1.031	0.497	0.533
28	There are too many PCAs competing with each other to cove	28	1.231	1.028	0.203
34	It is awkward when a client asks,How often do you review	34	-0.142	-0.333	0.192
33	PCAs may be hesitant to tell an FC about the true nature	33	0.973	0.898	0.075
19	As long as I were well paid if I didn't have performance	19	0.512	0.466	0.046
7	My main motivation for working is to get praise from my bo	7	-1.658	-1.694	0.036
18	Concern about getting good Client Promoter Scores may som	18	-1.178	-1.197	0.019
20	The only way to allocate bonuses fairly is through specif	20	-0.651	-0.562	-0.089
26	I feel I can easily control which clients I work with and	26	-1.856	-1.762	-0.094
35	My success depends heavily on getting new referral from	35	0.922	1.096	-0.174
10	The thing my clients say matters most to them are broad	10	-0.672	-0.364	-0.308
16	Because at least some of my performance targets are not	16	0.528	0.928	-0.400
32	PCAs should be allowed to soft-close and or re-open their	32	0.391	0.864	-0.473
13	I must keep in mind as important that clients equate inac	13	-0.260	0.267	-0.526
15	Having a performance target for financial planning and si	15	-0.941	-0.398	-0.543
9	PCAs may be reluctant to 'fire' a client because of the	9	0.456	1.097	-0.641
29	Having to please FCs can sometimes lead me to have to com	29	-1.084	-0.267	-0.816
22	It is best to tie bonuses to how many financial plans and	22	-1.333	-0.298	-1.036
36	I feel my role is sales oriented because I have to sell	36	0.769	1.929	-1.160
17	Having a big target can lead to a 'check-the-box-mentalit	17	0.572	1.861	-1.289
30	My performance targets do a good job of measuring how wel	30	-1.359	-0.030	-1.329
12	I must keep in mind as important that clients equate trad	12	-0.810	0.533	-1.343
25	Prospects and clients might wonder if they will receive a	25	-0.282	1.062	-1.344
3	Because of my workload I sometimes worry about the possibi	3	-0.088	1.266	-1.353
14	Adhering to compliance rules is onerous and unproductive	14	-1.602	-0.199	-1.403

Table 13 illustrates a comparison between Factors 2 and 3. The software identifies Factor's 2 and 3 as Type 2 and Type 3. As noted, a table like this is produced for every possible pair of factors. Table 12 above shows that Factor 2 is much more positive about items 5, 23, 21, 31, 6 and 8 than Factor 3 and that, at the bottom of the table, Factor 3 is much more positive about items 22, 36, 17, 30, 12, 25, 3 and 14 than Factor 2.

Table A-14

Exact Factor Scores (á la SPSS) in Z-Score and T-Score units								
No.	Statement	No.	Factors					
			1	2	3			
1	A focus on planning may sometimes be a way of deflec	1	0.38	54	-0.02	50	-0.78	42
2	Management expresses concern and /or interest about	2	-0.75	43	-0.77	42	-1.68	33
3	Because of my workload I sometimes worry about the	3	1.72	67	-0.77	42	0.63	56
4	I would work with less stress and be more effective	4	-0.58	44	0.53	55	0.38	54
5	My main motivation for working is to help as many in	5	-1.08	39	2.94	79	-0.70	43
6	My main motivation for working is for me to succeed	6	-0.38	46	0.69	57	-0.45	45
7	My main motivation for working is to get praise from	7	-0.96	40	-0.95	40	-1.22	38
8	My main motivation for working is to help the compan	8	-1.14	39	0.48	55	-0.92	41
9	PCAs may be reluctant to 'fire' a client because of	9	0.15	52	0.23	52	1.38	64
10	The thing my clients say matters most to them are	10	-0.38	46	-0.65	44	-0.24	48
11	The thing my clients say matters most to them is	11	0.08	51	0.85	58	-0.31	47
12	I must keep in mind as important that clients equat	12	0.74	57	-1.02	40	-0.08	49
13	I must keep in mind as important that clients equat	13	0.10	51	-0.42	46	0.09	51
14	Adhering to compliance rules is onerous and unprodu	14	-1.08	39	-1.28	37	0.36	54
15	Having a performance target for financial planning	15	-1.33	37	-0.44	46	-0.12	49
16	Because at least some of my performance targets are	16	0.09	51	0.86	59	0.40	54
17	Having a big target can lead to a 'check-the-box-me	17	0.76	58	0.01	50	1.59	66
18	Concern about getting good Client Promoter Scores	18	-0.06	49	-0.77	42	-0.55	44
19	As long as I were well paid if I didn't have perform	19	1.71	67	0.22	52	-0.29	47
20	The only way to allocate bonuses fairly is through	20	0.71	57	-0.95	40	-0.55	44
21	If we were reallylooking through clients eyes it wo	21	0.45	54	1.38	64	-1.16	38
22	It is best to tie bonuses to how many financial pla	22	-1.58	34	-1.19	38	0.21	52
23	It is best to tie bonuses to how well the company	23	-0.75	43	1.18	62	-2.09	29
24	Sometimes an employees contribution to the firms	24	0.29	53	1.16	62	0.41	54
25	Prospects and clients might wonder if they will rec	25	1.50	65	-0.82	42	0.55	56
26	I feel I can easily control which clients I work wil	26	-0.18	48	-1.60	34	-1.50	35
27	I sometimes have to depend on FCs for referrals who	27	-0.31	47	0.96	60	1.15	61
28	There are too many PCAs competing with each other	28	-0.48	45	1.18	62	0.85	59
29	Having to please FCs can sometimes lead me to have	29	-1.05	39	-0.87	41	0.64	56
30	My performance targets do a good job of measuring	30	-1.42	36	-1.49	35	0.87	59
31	As a fiduciary I have too many clients to serve the	31	2.17	72	0.64	56	-1.24	38
32	PCAs should be allowed to soft-close and or re-open	32	0.15	52	-0.10	49	1.56	66
33	PCAs may be hesitant to tell an FC about the true	33	0.79	58	0.56	56	0.13	51
34	It is awkward when a client asks,How often do you	34	2.12	71	-0.64	44	-0.77	42
35	My success depends heavily on getting new referral	35	-0.82	42	0.98	60	1.70	67
36	I feel my role is sales oriented because I have to	36	0.43	54	-0.07	49	1.78	68

When the PQMethod software developer, Peter Schmolck describes 'exact' factor scores he means what he considers the normal version of factor scores outside the Q methodology context as they might be calculated using another software program such as IBM SPSS. Schmolck states this format is offered because it allows the scores to be produced with sufficient precision in the PQMethod software data format which allows for two digits, non-negative numbers with decimals (Schmolck, 2014).

In Table 14 above, the highest-ranking statement (most agreed with) in Factor 1 is number 31 ranked with a z score of 2.17 and a T-score of 72. The lowest-ranking statement (most disagreed with) in Factor 1 is statement 22 with a z score of -1.58 and a T-score of 34.

According to Schmolck, the sorts' of correlations using this method differ from their factor loadings only because of rounding deviations.

The important point is that this serves as another way to confirm the usefulness of results produced in PQMethod software using the Q oriented method by comparing results that would be generated using a different method of calculation offered by other software packages. The ranking of the statements is the same in both conditions of analysis.

Table A-15

Factor Q-Sort Values for Each Statement					
No.	Statement	No.	Factor Arrays		
			1	2	3
1	A focus on planning may sometimes be a way of deflecting	1	0	0	-2
2	Management expresses concern and /or interest about indivi	2	-3	-2	-5
3	Because of my workload I sometimes worry about the possibi	3	4	0	4
4	I would work with less stress and be more effective if I	4	0	1	0
5	My main motivation for working is to help as many investor	5	-1	5	0
6	My main motivation for working is for me to succeed	6	-1	0	-2
7	My main motivation for working is to get praise from my	7	-4	-4	-4
8	My main motivation for working is to help the company succ	8	-2	0	-3
9	PCAs may be reluctant to 'fire' a client because of the	9	2	0	3
10	The thing my clients say matters most to them are broad	10	-1	-1	-1
11	The thing my clients say matters most to them is the perf	11	0	1	-1
12	I must keep in mind as important that clients equate trad	12	0	-2	1
13	I must keep in mind as important that clients equate inac	13	-1	-1	1
14	Adhering to compliance rules is onerous and unproductive	14	-3	-4	0
15	Having a performance target for financial planning and	15	-3	-2	-2
16	Because at least some of my performance targets are not	16	1	1	2
17	Having a big target can lead to a 'check-the-box-mentalit	17	3	2	4
18	Concern about getting good Client Promoter Scores may some	18	-1	-3	-3
19	Aslong as I were well paid if I didn't have performance	19	4	1	1
20	The only way to allocate bonuses fairly is through specif	20	0	-1	-2
21	If we were reallylooking through clients eyes it would be	21	1	3	-1
22	It is best to tie bonuses to how many financial plans and	22	-5	-3	-1
23	It is best to tie bonuses to how well the company perform	23	-2	1	-3
24	Sometimes an employee contribution to the firms bus	24	2	4	1
25	Prospects and clients might wonder if they will receive a	25	3	-1	3
26	I feel I can easily control which clients I work with and	26	-2	-5	-4
27	I sometimes have to depend on FCs for referrals whose foc	27	1	3	1
28	There are too many PCAs competing with each other to cove	28	1	4	2
29	Having to please FCs can sometimes lead me to have to com	29	-2	-2	0
30	My performance targets do a good job of measuring how well	30	-4	-3	0
31	As a fiduciary I have too many clients to serve them all	31	5	3	0
32	PCAs should be allowed to soft-close and or re-open their	32	1	0	2
33	PCAs may be hesitant to tell an FC about the true nature	33	2	2	2
34	It is awkward when a client asks,How often do you review	34	3	-1	-1
35	My success depends heavily on getting new referral from	35	0	2	3
36	I feel my role is sales oriented because I have to sell	36	2	2	5

Variance = 5.833 St. Dev. = 2.415

Watts and Stenner (2012) assert Table 15 is the most important among all the data. It contains the factor arrays for each study factor. A factor array is a single Q sort configured to represent the viewpoint of a particular factor (Watts, 2012). A factor array, or factor-exemplifying Q sort conforms to the same distribution used in the original data collection and it is constructed by reference to the size and ultimately the rank order of the z scores. The variance and standard deviation suggest that the Factors have about 6% in common with one another, give or take approximately 2%. To visualize this another way Figure A1 illustrates how, as a group, participants landing on Factor 1 sorted their Q statements. Following after this are Figure A2 and F A3 that provides the same visual aid but for Factor Array's 2 and 3.

Table A-16

Factor Q-Sort Values for Statements sorted by Consensus vs. Disagreement (Variance across Factor Z-Scores)					
		Factor Arrays			
No.	Statement	No.	1	2	3
33	PCAs may be hesitant to tell an FC about the true nature	33	2	2	2
7	My main motivation for working is to get praise from my bo	7	-4	-4	-4
10	The thing my clients say matters most to them are broad	10	-1	-1	-1
16	Because at least some of my performance targets are not	16	1	1	2
32	PCAs should be allowed to soft-close and or re-open their	32	1	0	2
13	I must keep in mind as important that clients equate inac	13	-1	-1	1
24	Sometimes an employees contribution to the firms bus	24	2	4	1
9	PCAs may be reluctant to 'fire' a client because of the	9	2	0	3
4	I would work with less stress and be more effective if I	4	0	1	0
27	I sometimes have to depend on FCs for referrals whose foc	27	1	3	1
1	A focus on planning may sometimes be a way of deflecting	1	0	0	-2
18	Concern about getting good Client Promoter Scores may som	18	-1	-3	-3
20	The only way to allocate bonuses fairly is through specif	20	0	-1	-2
29	Having to please FCs can sometimes lead me to have to com	29	-2	-2	0
2	Management expresses concern and /or interest about indivi	2	-3	-2	-5
11	The thing my clients say matters most to them is the perf	11	0	1	-1
28	There are too many PCAs competing with each other to cove	28	1	4	2
26	I feel I can easily control which clients I work with and	26	-2	-5	-4
35	My success depends heavily on getting new referral from	35	0	2	3
15	Having a performance target for financial planning and	15	-3	-2	-2
6	My main motivation for working is for me to succeed	6	-1	0	-2
8	My main motivation for working is to help the company succ	8	-2	0	-3
19	Aslong as I were well paid if I didn't have performance	19	4	1	1
36	I feel my role is sales oriented because I have to sell	36	2	2	5
17	Having a big target can lead to a 'check-the-box-mentalit	17	3	2	4
21	If we were reallylooking through clients eyes it would be	21	1	3	-1
12	I must keep in mind as important that clients equate trad	12	0	-2	1
14	Adhering to compliance rules is onerous and unproductive	14	-3	-4	0
22	It is best to tie bonuses to how many financial plans and	22	-5	-3	-1
25	Prospects and clients might wonder if they will receive a	25	3	-1	3
30	My performance targets do a good job of measuring how wel	30	-4	-3	0
3	Because of my workload I sometimes worry about the possibi	3	4	0	4
31	As a fiduciary I have too many clients to serve them all	31	5	3	0
34	It is awkward when a client asks,How often do you review	34	3	-1	-1
23	It is best to tie bonuses to how well the company perform	23	-2	1	-3
5	My main motivation for working is to help as many investor	5	-1	5	0

Table 16 shows the Q statements sorted by the degree to which there is commonality among the Factors. There is complete consensus across all three Factors having to do with statements 33,7, and 10 with less consensus between the Factors as the list continues downward. The widest gap in terms of consensus rests with statement number 5 where Factor 1 rates this at -1, Factor 2 rates the statement at +5 and Factor 3 rates it at 0. This represents a potentially significant area of difference of opinion.

Table A-17

Factor Characteristics	Factors		
	1	2	3
No. of Defining Variables	9	8	3
Average Rel. Coef.	0.800	0.800	0.800
Composite Reliability	0.973	0.970	0.923
S.E. of Factor Z-Scores	0.164	0.174	0.277
Standard Errors for Differences in Factor Z-Scores (Diagonal Entries Are S.E. Within Factors)			
Factors	1	2	3
1	0.232	0.239	0.322
2	0.239	0.246	0.327
3	0.322	0.327	0.392

Table 17 shows the Number of 'Defining Variables' which refers to the number of Q sorts that comprise each Factor. This table also illustrates the composite reliability factor for each factor. This is important because the quality of a factor can be measured by its composite reliability (Ward, 2009),(Chung, 2019). The more Q sorts flagged for the factor, the higher the reliability. When more participants share a viewpoint, there is more confidence in the score of the items composing it (Brown 1980). Furthermore, since reliability is inversely related to the standard error, the higher the reliability, the lower the standard error (Ward, 2009, p. 78).

Table A-18

Distinguishing Statements for Factor 1							
(P < .05 ; Asterisk (*) Indicates Significance at P < .01)							
Both the Factor Q-Sort Value (Q-SV) and the Z-Score (Z-SCR) are Shown.							
No. Statement	No.	Factors					
		1		2		3	
		Q-SV	Z-SCR	Q-SV	Z-SCR	Q-SV	Z-SCR
31 As a fiduciary I have too many clients to serve them all	31	5	1.73	3	1.21	0	-0.13
19 Aslong as I were well paid if I didn't have performance	19	4	1.59*	1	0.51	1	0.47
34 It is awkward when a client asks,How often do you review	34	3	1.43*	-1	-0.14	-1	-0.33
17 Having a big target can lead to a 'check-the-box-mentalit	17	3	1.13	2	0.57	4	1.86
21 If we were really looking through clients eyes it would be	21	1	0.46	3	1.01	-1	-0.37
28 There are too many PCAs competing with each other to cove	28	1	0.35	4	1.23	2	1.03
35 My success depends heavily on getting new referral from	35	0	0.17*	2	0.92	3	1.10
20 The only way to allocate bonuses fairly is through specif	20	0	0.14	-1	-0.65	-2	-0.56
18 Concern about getting good Client Promoter Scores may some	18	-1	-0.47	-3	-1.18	-3	-1.20
26 I feel I can easily control which clients I work with and	26	-2	-1.00	-5	-1.86	-4	-1.76
15 Having a performance target for financial planning and	15	-3	-1.46	-2	-0.94	-2	-0.40
22 It is best to tie bonuses to how many financial plans and	22	-5	-1.84	-3	-1.33	-1	-0.30

Table 18, along with the following two tables, list all the items that a particular factor has ranked in a significantly different way to all the other factors. A difference at the $p < 0.01$ level is indicated by an asterisk. For example, at the $p < 0.01$ level, Factor 1 has ranked item 19 highest with a z score of 1.59 and item 35 lower with a z score of 0.17. Together the three items marked with the asterisk are the items that most distinguish the differences between Factor 1 and the other two factors.

Table A-19

Distinguishing Statements for Factor 2							
(P < .05 ; Asterisk (*) Indicates Significance at P < .01)							
Both the Factor Q-Sort Value (Q-SV) and the Z-Score (Z-SCR) are Shown.							
No. Statement	No.	Factors					
		1		2		3	
		Q-SV	Z-SCR	Q-SV	Z-SCR	Q-SV	Z-SCR
5 My main motivation for working is to help as many investor	5	-1	-0.41	5	2.14*	0	-0.20
31 As a fiduciary I have too many clients to serve them all	31	5	1.73	3	1.21	0	-0.13
21 If we were reallylooking through clients eyes it would be	21	1	0.46	3	1.01	-1	-0.37
17 Having a big target can lead to a 'check-the-box-mentalit	17	3	1.13	2	0.57	4	1.86
11 The thing my clients say matters most to them is the perf	11	0	0.03	1	0.55	-1	-0.33
23 It is best to tie bonuses to how well the company perform	23	-2	-1.03	1	0.47*	-3	-1.66
6 My main motivation for working is for me to succeed	6	-1	-0.23	0	0.36	-2	-0.83
8 My main motivation for working is to help the company succ	8	-2	-0.96	0	0.02*	-3	-1.10
3 Because of my workload I sometimes worry about the possibi	3	4	1.58	0	-0.09*	4	1.27
25 Prospects and clients might wonder if they will receive a	25	3	1.13	-1	-0.28*	3	1.06
12 I must keep in mind as important that clients equate trad	12	0	0.23	-2	-0.81*	1	0.53
22 It is best to tie bonuses to how many financial plans and	22	-5	-1.84	-3	-1.33	-1	-0.30

Table 19, along with Tables 18 and 20, list all the items that a particular factor has ranked in a significantly different way to all the other factors. A difference at the $p < 0.01$ level is indicated by an asterisk. For example, at the $p < 0.01$ level, Factor 2 has ranked item 5 highest with a z score of 2.14 and item 12 lower with a z score of -0.81. Together the six items marked with the asterisk are the items that distinguish the differences between Factor 2 and the other two factors.

Table A-20

Distinguishing Statements for Factor 3							
(P < .05 ; Asterisk (*) Indicates Significance at P < .01)							
Both the Factor Q-Sort Value (Q-SV) and the Z-Score (Z-SCR) are Shown.							
No. Statement	No.	Factors					
		1		2		3	
		Q-SV	Z-SCR	Q-SV	Z-SCR	Q-SV	Z-SCR
36 I feel my role is sales oriented because I have to sell	36	2	0.88	2	0.77	5	1.93*
17 Having a big target can lead to a 'check-the-box-mentalit	17	3	1.13	2	0.57	4	1.86
30 My performance targets do a good job of measuring how wel	30	-4	-1.53	-3	-1.36	0	-0.03*
31 As a fiduciary I have too many clients to serve them all	31	5	1.73	3	1.21	0	-0.13*
14 Adhering to compliance rules is onerous and unproductive	14	-3	-1.15	-4	-1.60	0	-0.20*
29 Having to please FCs can sometimes lead me to have to com	29	-2	-0.92	-2	-1.08	0	-0.27
22 It is best to tie bonuses to how many financial plans and	22	-5	-1.84	-3	-1.33	-1	-0.30*
21 If we were reallylooking through clients eyes it would be	21	1	0.46	3	1.01	-1	-0.37
1 A focus on planning may sometimes be a way of deflecting	1	0	0.03	0	0.07	-2	-0.66

Table 20, along with Tables 18 and 19, list all the items that a particular factor has ranked in a significantly different way to all the other factors. A difference at the $p < 0.01$ level is indicated by an asterisk. For example, at the $p < 0.01$ level, Factor 3 has ranked item 36 highest with a z score of 1.93 and item 1 lower with a z score of -0.66. Together the five items marked with the asterisk are the items that distinguish the differences between Factor 3 and the other two factors.

Table A-21

Consensus Statements -- Those That Do Not Distinguish Between ANY Pair of Factors.							
All Listed Statements are Non-Significant at $P > .01$, and Those Flagged With an * are also Non-Significant at $P > .05$.							
		Factors					
		1		2		3	
No.	Statement	No.	Q-SV Z-SCR				
1	A focus on planning may sometimes be a way of deflecting	1	0 0.03	0 0.07	-2 -0.66		
4	I would work with less stress and be more effective if I	4	0 -0.05	1 0.51	0 -0.10		
7*	My main motivation for working is to get praise from my	7	-4 -1.52	-4 -1.66	-4 -1.69		
9*	PCAs may be reluctant to 'fire' a client because of the	9	2 0.63	0 0.46	3 1.10		
10*	The thing my clients say matters most to them are broad	10	-1 -0.70	-1 -0.67	-1 -0.36		
13*	I must keep in mind as important that clients equate inac	13	-1 -0.07	-1 -0.26	1 0.27		
16*	Because at least some of my performance targets are not	16	1 0.56	1 0.53	2 0.93		
24	Sometimes an employees contribution to the firms bus	24	2 0.94	4 1.38	1 0.73		
29	Having to please FCs can sometimes lead me to have to com	29	-2 -0.92	-2 -1.08	0 -0.27		
32*	PCAs should be allowed to soft-close and or re-open their	32	1 0.55	0 0.39	2 0.86		
33*	PCAs may be hesitant to tell an FC about the true nature	33	2 0.90	2 0.97	2 0.90		

These are the items whose rankings do not distinguish between any pair of factors. All the study factors have valued items 7, 9, 10, 13, 16, 32, and 33 in similar ways.

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And yeah, really being able to build relationships with and wrap your head around 250 clients. Yeah. In general, it's for one person, I don't think it's feasible.

Yeah, I mean, managements concern over portfolio performance, I've never seen any evidence that.

So, I wish there was more that I could do as a fiduciary in my role to control the number of clients that I work with so that I can give them better attention.

It's just, it's just they're concerned about quantity, whether or not too much quantity means too little quality...

Yeah, I roll my eyes when I'm, you know, forgot to check a box or something like that. You know, I get these nasty grams from compliance. But on the other hand, I mean, those, those hurdles exist to protect, not just the company brand, but also clients.

I still feel like I haven't quite put my arms around how I, how I continue to support this whole practice and give them what they're paying for.

I've struggled with the Private Client Advisor role being a sales role.

Do we have to have some type of incentive structure? Yes. Is it on retention? Is it on client service? Is it keeping the client's content? Is it, maybe, you know, some asset consolidation? What we are capable of doing there. But I think it's very hard to have those two roles, both have a sales component.

I think the main thing is the practice sizes. Among most of them we've never really, you know, they started saying this was an ideal practice size and we don't hear anything about that anymore. So, it's really, you know, from my understanding, they are not, they are not concerned about decreasing your practice size.

I've never really shared the number of clients issue because I think that creates a barrier of them; scratching their head as to, "Ok, can she handle these new clients?" And that's the challenge is that, you know, you have so many clients already, but you still have an NSF goal.

So, you know, if you're giving the FCs the impression that you don't have that capacity then you're not going to, you're not going to reach your NSF target. I have to look at them as my customers if they're not giving me business, I'm not able to (reach my NSF target).

I think that's, that's probably what I'm always thinking of when I come in, you know, over a weekend is what am I going to come into, an email of maybe who have I missed. Or who's, who, you know, dropped. You know, if there was a ball dropped.

As far as devoting more time to some clients than others, well I don't think that every client, you know, should get the exact same amount of time. Because their needs are different, number one, and certainly someone that's paying you \$15,000 a year probably deserves a little more of your time than someone is paying you \$4,000 a year, you know. So, the larger clients that, I think it's just the nature of the business, larger clients will tend to get more of your, your focus, more of your time, because they've got more complex situations and it hurts more when they leave.

I know that it hurts them when a client leaves and they know that it hurts me when a client leaves and there is an understanding there.

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Touchy subject. Because you don't want to just kick somebody out of your practice without working in conjunction with your FC because that FC is your business partner. And you don't want to burn bridges with your business partners.

With the FC, I will say I hold back a little bit, right? Look, I'm hesitant to, like, maybe sometimes push back more, just because of the way that, even though I don't have a large target, asset target, I've got a big practice. I mean, they're really the ones that close the business, right?

So, I do remember one of the questions was, as a fiduciary do I have too many clients to serve them all well? I definitely would say in the affirmative. I absolutely agree with that. I think we; I think the 'God of Scale' - that the firm worships that, right? I think in a relationship business, there's a finite number, right? And I think I don't remember exactly the order, but I know that I have a strong feeling. But I think the idea of 200 households, my perspective is really absurd, right? I remember thinking, well, like, would I say that I serve all of them well? Yes, but I guess the way you would say it is, is it well enough, right? Not... You could do so much more if you had fewer, right? You could have such deeper relationships. I think this ties-in the firms concerned that they're tied to you less to the firm interest. Because it makes me wonder if there's some intentionality about it.

And a lot of younger guys that are relatively new, it's, "I feel like I have to say yes to anything that comes my way, even though I feel like it's a dubious fit or it's maybe not appropriate or the investment philosophy that the client, maybe explicitly, you know, maybe explicit or implicit is not a strategy that I'm fully on board with, but I can't turn it away, right?"

I think what's gratifying about it is that at least where we work, right? It really does allow you to get to know a client on a very personal level and to really understand their circumstances, which I think I know it sounds silly, but I mean, it really is true that the more you know somebody, the more you tend to have a better grasp of their situation.

Are we say, are we what we say we are - which is wealth managers? Because I think we were talking out of both sides of our mouth. I think we were marketing ourselves as wealth managers, but all of our energy was focused on sales. So, to me that was, that was a huge pit in my stomach. And it just, I just thought it was incongruent with all the marketing and you know how we position Private Client to prospects, right?

Oh, sure, financial planning. Yeah, cuz there's a way you can even, you can push out a plan pretty quick. I mean, there's a way to do that. You just say, all right, well, what's the portfolio look like? If you know you only take out your RMDs right. You know, we, we have a term for that, a term, like internally. We've named it within our practice. And, you know, you just, you leave all the other planning out of it. So, it really just looks like, what's that withdrawal rate, that draw down on the portfolio? Very simple. But does that really, is that beneficial to the client? Maybe? Maybe not. Do I feel that I've done an adequate job of financial planning for the client? Not at all. Not in the least bit.

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So, I'm just saying I think that there are, there are obvious error areas that we overlook. And I think a lot of times we just assume that the client situation has remained the same. I mean, when we set-up the appointments, we say, "Has anything changed?" The client will say, yes or no. And we truly don't know. Like, I just had a client that, I don't know, she's in her 80s and scheduled her meeting. And "Has anything changed?" Well, no. "Any cash needs?" No. I mean, we asked the same questions over and over again. But turns out, you know, she's, she's, she lives on a 21-acre farm in Georgia. And you know, her kids don't want her living there on her own anymore. And so, unbeknownst to me, she's, you know, she sold her house and bought a townhouse and she's been mulling it for a while. And, you know, not any real, I mean, that's, that's a planable event, right? That's something that maybe we perhaps should have explored in financial planning. What does that mean? What does that look like? And did we do that? No. One because it happens so quickly, but two, we were unaware. And I think that gets down to because we, you know, we've, we've got, you've got, especially in my mind, it's very similar to what family physicians and medical field looks like right now. They book 15-minute appointments. That's what you get out. That's what they're allocated, you get 15 minutes. So how much can you really understand about a person's, you know, total physical wellbeing in 15 minutes, right, you know, 5, 5-10 minutes that was probably just, "Hey, how you doing? What's going on in your world?" And then you got five minutes left? It's just simply not realistic. And I think similarly, with financial planning with, with the portfolio. Oftentimes, my meetings go way over. And do I worry about that as my practice continues to grow? Yeah, for sure. I worry that in order to be efficient, I need to scale back the length of my meetings. But I fear there's a loss not just in the relationship, but really understanding what's going on in the client's world and which trend has so many different translations? And then, you know, so let's say your appointment goes beyond what the expectation. Because I think management has the expectation that your meeting should be about 40-45 minutes with 15 minutes for wrap up documentation, etc.; etc. So it might easily go beyond that. And I feel like I'm gonna get in trouble at some point, but I don't feel like I'm doing the client service. If you look at how much these clients are charged from, you know, from a basis point perspective, not a lot, right? It's not a lot. But when you see the actual debit, hit your account, and you really start reflecting. So, do I really think I got \$25,000 worth of value this year? Hmm. You know, when my portfolio consultant kind of blew in blew out, making a couple changes, made small talk and then you know, I don't know.

I have a few instances of that, you know, transition client that I got from somebody and not once have they taken any recommendations. In fact, they've, you know, won't meet with me. So, you know, how can you justify charging them? He's a CFA. I'm not exactly sure why he's in Private Client. He's on his mom's account as power of attorney. So, he's been managing his mom's account. So why are they in Private Client? But if I say anything, that's a million-dollar un-enrollment, and you know, then I gotta justify that. I can't even get them on the calendar.

You know, we always say that you were supposed to do what's right for the client, but we're really, it's, I feel like there is a lot of pressure to keep clients enrolled simply because it impacts Financial Consultant money, you know, FCs compensation. And, you know, furthermore, you know, because then they gotta, they got to make that up right? It rolls up into, into their sales figures which puts pressure on them with their manager. So it's like you're on the front line and you do everything to manage. Remember that that was in the environment of, I need this Financial Consultant to send me business and if I hack him off, is he going to send me business because I'm unenrolling clients? Yeah, I really think that that's, that's the predominant reason why we do that and is that really in the best interest of clients? I don't know.

I mean, for sure, the sheer quantity of clients I have is really high over 220.

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Or, or suggest them not working with me. Maybe another Portfolio, a Private Client Advisor instead. You may get kind of that pushback or there's that, I mean, that may suggest you're difficult to do business with; you're kind of high maintenance or so there could be some of those where it's kind of feel like you need to take almost anything on. Or it could ultimately, you run the risk where people may not like you or they say, yeah, and they'll just find someone else to give business to.

So, it varies. But I think for the most part, clients are pretty well qualified. Of course, you're going to get the ones that are just not on the same page and they're, they're, the FC is really trying to force something. You often find, like, like options is a great example of what they might throw in last minute to save a relationship. But I've been in that situation a few times now where it's just not the right fit. And then the client might vocalize that, and the FC just jumps in that, you know, oh, well, we can, we can do options for you, right? And then, you know, we bring in Jay in the conversation, and just like falls flat, you know? But luckily, those are few and far between.

I mean, that's a great question. I don't know if it's like an implied, it seems like it's almost implied in Private Client. Like, people don't fire, PCs don't fire clients.

I have 150 now, I'm considered, you know, a teenager. You know, some people have more mature books than mine, mine's only a teenager level. But anything, even at that level, it's not, it's not, not, not efficient, not feasible. So, you get, you, I think by default, you end up falling into that rut of every quarter, you know, every three months. You've got to have this call and you gotta talk about the market. You've got to place some trades! You gotta have some trades! You know, I've been getting better at not having trades. And that's going well with clients. But, you know, I think client and PC getting this, right? It's like, it's kind of, it comes to this.

But yeah, the IPSs and the Suitability, I'm sure it's probably, to some degree, regardless of which firms you go to, I think at Morgan, it was something similar. But yeah, it just seems a little bit burdensome, you know, and it's in, you know, when the, when the expectation is, you know, you just do Suitability, you just 'check the box' and you move on. You know, it's like it's the last of my priorities. You know, if the expectation really was to use Suitability as a way to, to have a conversation and meaningful conversation with the client? Then that's different. But that would be overly burdensome. I mean, that would be almost impossible, in my view. Every time, every time, every year, you'd have to, have a, you know, run down this laundry list to really be able to, to cross your T's and dot your I's. But you'd have to ask about a slew of issues, which just, I think if you did it every year, it would just seem so, so non-sequitur to the client.

... you know, the IPS and getting the fact-finder information there from them. Because realistically, it's, it's a little backwards in the way that, that, that we sometimes approached this in the sense that they want to make sure that their investments are lined up, you know, what's kind of their preferences and needs. But until we actually run that plan, and identify what those needs are, and maybe they're taking more risks than what's really warranted for the success for the plan, if you kind of be, like a little a little backwards the way that we approach it and, and I think what the clients want as well.

It's when we get into that kind of question of, how many clients we are responsible for, whether being a client or an FC. That's really where you can't tell them. You can't tell the truth! You can't tell them you have 200 million or 206 clients.

We don't say that word 'capacity' to a client because we have to be responsive. To the FC world and to that side of things internally to our internal partners, we absolutely have to pretend that we have this unlimited capacity.

I go to the other issues of how we are incentivized to provide that, you know, the, the ideal or the illusion that we have to create for the client and for the FC of our time constraints, right? And how we are incented in reality.

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We're not free of conflict. No one is free. But I think we do a good job of minimizing some of the issues that are out there in the industry with conflicts. I think no one's perfect. I think we do a good job of serving the client. I think we do a good job of, if there's issues with the client. I think from that standpoint we do a really good job.

I still think the one area that that needs, there needs some refining is, is meeting those, those planning numbers and what is considered delivering a plan versus just having planning conversations that are meaningful and helpful to a client. I think that's where you're gonna see a lot of boxes checked. In the sense that we have to complete this plan. Well, let's just go on ahead and, "Hey, what's your what's your monthly spending? What's your income? You know, what's your Social Security," and then we throw together this plan. "Here's your Monte Carlo simulation. There you go." We checked the box, right? It's not real, detailed, meaningful planning. You know, what are some concerns that you have? Are you putting in those stress factors of here's what, you know, two years of long-term care would do to your plan or just asking them those questions have left concerning you versus just throwing these numbers into a planning software and projecting some numbers.

I think the most challenging is we have too many clients, we really need a deeper dive with each client. You know, I think maybe with some other RIAs they have, you know, less clients or more defined roles. You know, planners can do a better job of, you know, looking at maybe a client's tax situation and analysing other assets that they have pulling that all together to give them deeper financial advice. Advice outside of just going to more of a portfolio. I don't think that we can do that very well with the number of clients that we have it's just not possible.

I, I don't, I, I'm, I'm very much a dyed-in-the-wool of kind of what we do. And so, I try really hard. You know, occasionally there is, there is the, I will, I will bend. But I won't break. So, if it's something that somebody wants something ... I absolutely can't recommend things beyond what we're allowed to recommend. But if it's something where a client wants to do something that I think is, is not 100% within what we're trying to do, but maybe is 75% what we're trying to do, then I will try to find a way to make that then work for them. Because I just get, I honestly, I get tired of trying to fight them on it.

Yes, so that definitely happens. That's happened since day one. That, that I think will, because it's never... their, their role in some ways is in contrast to our role, not in contrast, but, but in more of, it's just, it's different. And because of that, they're going to be incented to get people through the door and hope it works. And if it doesn't, they're going to get a little bit of a sting. But their hope is, they get it to us, and we then wrangle the wild horse and get it in the pen. And if we can do that, then we're gonna, then they appreciate us and they like us, and, you know, they'll give us, you know, they'll keep bringing it to us. And so that's where, for what we do, it's so vital for us to try and figure out, even if it's somebody who might be a bad fit. And I guess maybe this isn't an ethical as much as it's just awkward, to try and find a way to make that client who doesn't necessarily fit, how can we keep them in? Because it's it hurts everybody. It helps everybody on the way in and hurts everybody on the way out and we're the ones who work the back door. So, we've got to try and do everything we can to keep him in that place.

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I think when you put numbers to anything, there's going to be, you know, not necessarily unethical things, but you're, you're going to your competitive nature, is going to take in, into effect there and you want to do your best and if you want to provide for your team and for yourself, so when there was the, you know, the quantitative metrics there of hitting planning and hitting assets and stuff, you know, there was maybe a little bit, a little bit more of a, you know, these, these CDs that we recommended here to you, you know, we made the recommendation on these and they're sitting in the account, so you should be paying a fee on those. Versus, hey, we've got no intention to sell these. Maybe they should be in a non PCA account, where you're not paying a fee and then as they mature, then maybe we decide what we want to do. I think there can be a little, a little bit of that, but for the sense of not making unsuitable recommendations based on pay I really like that aspect of Private Client Advisory, right?

And the 'check the box' thing has one thing though, that I think we do run into, is that we are asked to do; when, when you're being measured on numerical metrics, someone's gonna find a way to get over that hurdle in a way that might not be the most, they might not fit, they'll get the desired, desired response, without the required steps. Because of the fact that, if your planning numbers says this; well, I'm gonna run some plans that maybe, I don't think ethically incur unethical, but they're, I don't know they're productive either. It's just I need to get a number. And so, I'm going to do my Investment Policy Statements - 100 in one day to get them off. Does that create any quality? No. But it 'checks the box' to say we're, we're done.

It's, it's tough because I feel like a lot of, over the years and having been doing this for as long as I have, the vast majority of things, the bigger themes that they, that they work on us with, are, they are, they kind of bring out in terms of, you know, CPS or IPS or planning or whatever it might be, I feel like it's 75% good. And I feel like it is trending us in a direction that is, that is better at, at the end. Because I do think that things like planning are more holistic, because I've got so many times where I meet somebody, and I have three things to do in their portfolio. So, it is nice to have a broader conversation, to have other things to work on. So, I get the idea behind it. The issue is always, here is a number. And it is not ... What they're trying to do is find a way to evaluate what the behaviors they want to have done. And it's really hard to evaluate a behavior without some sort of numeric to put through. Unless you're just sitting with them all the time and listening to the conversations or not. So, you have to put a number to say, well, you need to do this many things. Well, since you put a number on it, well, now, it's not that I'm trying to get the behaviors that you're trying to do, I'm trying to get that number. And that's where I think the struggle comes in. So, I don't know how you get, I definitely see my calls differently now than I did three years ago, than six years ago, 10 years ago because of these different themes that we've been adding to it and doing different things. But at the end of it all, it still says, OK, well, I need to get to 50% planning. So, I'm going to try something in here just to shoehorn a plan in. I can talk about the bigger, what we want to do as we manage this. We want to talk about how are we going as planned. But if literally I did a plan 10 months ago, and the markets have just kind of been along the line of a 5% growth over that 10 months, zero has changed on that plan. We build a plan to say what happens when the markets are good, what happens when the markets are bad. And it almost makes it seem like it to me, I feel like we're almost invalidating what we're doing by saying, well, every year we have to do another one, because every five years maybe I could see, every three years. But it's just, we're like, saying to clients, we do this to see what happens in different financial situations. And then we're saying, let's do it again or let's do it again, let's do it again. And that's where I think the conflict comes in, saying, 'This is what we'd like you to do - this is how we'd like it to look.' And by making it, the way we get you to do that is by putting a number in place. But it always ends up being, you know, 'Here is, here is the cheese, find it!' The rat will always get to it. But, not in the path that they necessarily want. And then they say, well, to put the cheese over here, OK. We'll always find a way to get those numbers. It's just not the behavior sometimes they want to get out of it.

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I thought it was interesting that we got really into planning at the height of a bull market, you know, and it's like, okay, so how do we make sure we don't lose clients? Well, we say that performance doesn't really matter as much and we have to talk about other things to obfuscate, you know, what we're doing.

It's hard for me to pick a specific one, but like it's awkward when a client asks how often do you review my investments because they have an assumption that we're constantly looking at them adjusting things and it's more like four times a year at most.

END OF SECTION

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And yeah, really being able to build relationships with and wrap your head around 250 clients, yeah, in general, it's for one person, I don't think it's feasible.

Yeah, I mean, managements' concern over portfolio performance, I've never seen any evidence that.

So, I wish there was more that I could do as a fiduciary in my role to control the number of clients that I work with so that I can give them better attention.

It's just, it's just they're concerned about quantity, whether or not too much quantity means too little quality...

Do we have to have some type of incentive structure? Yes. Is it on retention? Is it on client service? Is it keeping the client's content? Is it, maybe, you know, some asset consolidation- what we are capable of doing there? But I think it's very hard to have those two roles - both have a sales component.

I've never really shared the number of clients issue because I think that creates a barrier - of them scratching their head as to, "Ok, can she handle these new clients?" And that's the challenge is that, you know, you have so many clients already, but you still have an NSF goal.

So, you know, if you're giving the FCs the impression that you don't have that capacity then you're not going to, you're not going to reach your NSF target.

I have to look at them (FCs) as my customers if they're not giving me business, I'm not able to (meet my NSF target).

As far as devoting more time to some clients than others, well I don't think that every client, you know, should get the exact same amount of time. Because their needs are different, number one, and certainly someone that's paying you \$15,000 a year probably deserves a little more of your time than someone who is paying you \$4,000 a year, you know. So, the larger clients that, I think it's just the nature of the business, larger clients will tend to get more of your, your focus, more of your time, because they've got more complex situations and it hurts more when they leave.

I know that it hurts them when a client leaves and they know that it hurts me when a client leaves and there is an understanding there.

Touchy subject. Because you don't want to just kick somebody out of your practice without working in conjunction with your FC because that FC is your business partner. And you don't want to burn bridges with your business partners.

With the FC, I will say I hold back a little bit, right? Look, I'm hesitant to, like, maybe sometimes push back more, just because of the way that, even though I don't have a large target, asset target- I've got a big practice. I mean, they're really the ones that close the business, right?

And a lot of younger guys that are relatively new, it's, "I feel like I have to say yes to anything that comes my way, even though I feel like it's a dubious fit or it's maybe not appropriate or the investment philosophy that the client, maybe explicitly, you know, maybe explicit or implicit is not a strategy that I'm fully on board with, but I can't turn it away, right?"

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Are we say, are we what we say we are, which is wealth managers? Because I think we were talking out of both sides of our mouth. I think we were marketing ourselves as wealth managers, but all of our energy was focused on sales. So, to me that was, that was a huge pit in my stomach. And it just, I just thought it was incongruent with all the marketing and you know how we position Private Client to prospects, right?

Oh, sure, financial planning. Yeah, cuz there's a way you can even, you can push out a plan pretty quick. I mean, there's a way to do that. You just say, all right, well, what's the portfolio look like? If, you know, you only take out your RMDs, right. You know, we, we have a term for that internally, like internally. We've named it within our practice. And, you know, you just, you leave all the other planning out of it. So, it really just looks like what's that withdrawal rate, that draw down on the portfolio? Very simple. But does that really, is that beneficial to the client? Maybe? Maybe not. Do I feel that I've done an adequate job of financial planning for the client? Not at all. Not in the least bit.

So, I'm just saying I think that there are, there are obvious error areas that we overlook. And I think a lot of times we just assume that the client situation has remained the same. I mean, when we set up the appointments, we say is anything changed? The client will say yes or no. And we truly don't know. Like, I just had a client that, I don't know, she's in her 80s and scheduled her meeting. And "Has anything changed?" Well, no. "Any cash needs?" No. I mean, we asked the same questions over and over again. But turns out, you know, she's, she's, she lives on a 21-acre farm in Georgia. And you know, her kids don't want her living there on her own anymore. And so, unbeknownst to me, she's, you know, she sold her house and bought a townhouse and she's been mulling it for a while. And, you know, not any real, I mean, that's, that's a planable event, right? That's something that maybe we perhaps should have explored in financial planning. What does that mean? What does that look like? And did we do that? No. One, because it happens so quickly, but two, we were unaware. And I think that gets down to because we, you know, we've, we've got, you've got, especially in my mind, it's very similar to what family physicians and medical field looks like right now. They book 15-minute appointments. That's what you get out. That's what they're allocated, you get 15 minutes. So how much can you really understand about a person's you know, total physical wellbeing in 15 minutes, right, you know, 5, 5-10 minutes that was probably just, "Hey, how you doing? What's going on in your world?" And then you got five minutes left. It's just simply not realistic. And I think similarly, with financial planning with, with the portfolio. Oftentimes, my meetings go way over. And do I worry about that as my practice continues to grow? Yeah, for sure. I worry that in order to be efficient, I need to scale back the length of my meetings. But I fear there's a loss not just relationship, but really understanding what's going on in the client's world and which trend has so many different translations? And then, you know, so let's say your appointment goes beyond what the expectation. Because I think management has the expectation that your meeting should be about 40-45 minutes with 15 minutes for wrap up documentation, etc., etc. So, it might easily go beyond that. And I feel like I'm gonna get in trouble at some point, but I don't feel like I'm doing the client service. If you look at how much these clients are charged from, you know, from a basis point perspective, not a lot, right? It's not a lot. But when you see the actual debit hit your account, and you really start reflecting. So do I really think I got \$25,000 worth of value this year. Hmm. You know, when my portfolio consultant kind of blew in blew out, making a couple changes, made small talk and then you know, I don't know.

I have a few instances of that, you know, transition client that I got from somebody and not once have they taken any recommendations. In fact, they've, you know, won't meet with me. So, you know, how can you justify charging them? He's a CFA. I'm not exactly sure why he's in Private Client. He's on his mom's account as power of attorney. So, he's been managing his mom's account. So why are they in Private Client? But if I say anything, that's a million-dollar un-enrolment, and you know, then I gotta justify that. I can't even get them on the calendar.

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You know, we always say that you were supposed to do what's right for the client, but we're really, it's, I feel like there is a lot of pressure to keep clients enrolled simply because it impacts Financial Consultant money, you know, FCs compensation. And, you know, furthermore, you know, because then they gotta, they got to make that up right? It rolls up into, into their sales figures which puts pressure on them with their manager. So, it's like you're on the front line and you do everything to manage. Remember that that was in the environment of I need this Financial Consultant to send me business and if I hack him off, is he going to send me business because I'm unenrolling clients? Yeah, I really think that that's, that's the predominant reason why we do that and is that really in the best interest of clients? I don't know.

I mean, for sure, the sheer quantity of clients I have is really high over 220.

Or, or suggest them not working with me. Maybe another Portfolio, a Private Client Advisor instead. You may get kind of that pushback or there's that, I mean, that may suggest you're difficult to do business with, you're kind of high maintenance or so there could be some of those where it's kind of feel like you need to take almost anything on. Or it could ultimately, you run the risk where people may not like you or they say, yeah, and they'll just find someone else to give business to.

So, it varies. But I think for the most part, clients are pretty well qualified. Of course, you're going to get the ones that are just not on the same page and they're, they're, the FC is really trying to force something. You often find, like, like options is a great example of what they might throw in last minute to save a relationship. But I've been in that situation a few times now where it's just not the right fit. And then the client might vocalize that, and the FC just jumps in that, you know, oh, well, we can, we can do options for you, right? And then, you know, we bring in Jay in the conversation, and just like falls flat, you know? But luckily, those are few and far between.

I mean, that's a great question. I don't know if it's like an implied, it seems like it's almost implied in Private Client. Like, people don't fire, PCAs don't fire clients.

I have 150 now, I'm considered, you know, a teenager. You know, some people have more mature books than mine, mine's only a teenager level. But anything, even at that level, it's not, it's not, not, not efficient, not feasible. So, you get, you, I think by default, you end up falling into that rut of every quarter, you know, every three months. You've got to have this call and you gotta talk about the market. You've got to place some trades! You gotta have some trades! You know, I've been getting better at not having trades. And that's going well with clients. But, you know, I think client and PC getting this, right? It's like, it's kind of, it comes to this.

... you know, the IPS and getting the fact-finder information there from them. Because realistically, it's, it's a little backwards in the way that, that, that we sometimes approach this in the sense that they want to make sure that their investments are lined up, you know, what's kind of their preferences and needs. But until we actually run that plan, and identify what those needs are, and maybe they're taking more risks than what's really warranted for the success for the plan, if you, kind of, be like, a little a little backwards the way that we approach it and, and I think what the clients want as well.

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I still think the one area that, that needs, there needs some refining is, is meeting those, those planning numbers and what is considered delivering a plan versus just having planning conversations that are meaningful and helpful to a client? I think that's where you're gonna see a lot of boxes checked. In the sense that we have to complete this plan. Well, let's just go on ahead and, "Hey, what's your, what's your monthly spending? What's your income? You know, what's your Social Security," and then we throw together this plan. "Here's your Monte Carlo simulation. There you go." We checked the box, right? It's not real detailed, meaningful planning. You know, what are some concerns that you have? Are you putting in those stress factors of here's what, you know, two years of long-term care event would do to your plan or just asking them those questions have left concerning you versus just throwing these numbers into a planning software and projecting some numbers?

I think when you put numbers to anything, there's going to be, you know, not necessarily unethical things, but you're, you're going to your competitive nature, is going to take in, into effect there and you want to do your best and if you want to provide for your team and for yourself, so when there was the, you know, the quantitative metrics there of hitting planning and hitting assets and stuff, you know, there was maybe a little bit, a little bit more of a, you know, these, these CDs that we recommended here to you, you know, we made the recommendation on these and they're sitting in the account, so you should be paying a fee on those. Versus, hey, we've got no intention to sell these. Maybe they should be in a non-PC account, where you're not paying a fee and then as they mature, then maybe we decide what we want to do. I think there can be a little, a little bit of that, but for the sense of not making unsuitable recommendations based on pay I really like that aspect of Private Client, right?

I think the most challenging is we have too many clients, we really need a deeper dive with each client. You know, I think maybe with some other RIAs they have you know less clients or more defined roles. You know, planners can do a better job of, you know, looking at maybe a client's tax situation and analysing other assets that they have, pulling that all together to give them deeper financial advice; advice outside of just going to more of a portfolio. I don't think that we can do that very well with the number of clients that we have, it's just not possible.

And the 'check the box' thing has one thing though, that I think we do run into, is that we are asked to do; when, when you're being measured on numerical metrics, someone's gonna find a way to get over that hurdle in a way that might not be the most, they might not fit, they'll get the desired, desired response, without the required steps. Because of the fact that, if you're planning numbers says this, well, I'm gonna run some plans that maybe, I don't think ethically incur unethical, but they're, I don't know they're productive either. It's just I need to get a number. And so, I'm going to do my Investment Policy Statements - 100 in one day to get them off. Does that create any quality? No. But it 'checks the box' to say we're, we're done.

Yes, so that definitely happens. That's happened since day one. That, that I think will, because it's never... their, their role in some ways is in contrast to our role, not in contrast, but, but in more of, it's just, it's different. And because of that, they're going to be incented to get people through the door and hope it works. And if it doesn't, they're going to get a little bit of a sting. But their hope is, they get it to us and we then wrangle the wild horse and get it in the pen. And if we can do that, then we're gonna, then they appreciate us and they like us, and you know they'll give us, you know, they'll keep bringing it to us. And so that's where, for what we do, it's so vital for us to try and figure out, even if it's somebody who might be a bad fit. And I guess maybe this isn't an ethical as much as it's just awkward, to try and find a way to make that client who doesn't necessarily fit, how can we keep them in? Because it hurts everybody. It helps everybody on the way in and hurts everybody on the way out and we're the ones who work the back door. So, we've got to try and do everything we can to keep him in that place.

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I, I don't, I, I'm, I'm very much a dyed-in-the-wool of kind of what we do. And so, I try really hard. You know, occasionally there is, there is the, I will, I will bend. But I won't break. So, if it's something that somebody wants something ... I absolutely can't recommend things beyond what we're allowed to recommend. But if it's something where a client wants to do something that I think is, is not 100% within what we're trying to do, but maybe is 75% what we're trying to do, then I will try to find a way to make that then work for them. Because I just get, I honestly, I get tired of trying to fight them on it.

It's, it's tough because I feel like a lot of, over the years and having been doing this for as long as I have, the vast majority of things, the bigger themes that they, that they work on us with, are, they are, they kind of bring out in terms of, you know, CPS or IPS or planning or whatever it might be, I feel like it's 75% good. And I feel like it is trending us in a direction that is, that is better at, at the end. Because I do think that things like planning are more holistic, because I've got so many times where I meet somebody, and I have three things to do in their portfolio. So, it is nice to have a broader conversation, to have other things to work on. So, I get the idea behind it. The issue is always, here is a number. And it is not ... What they're trying to do is find a way to evaluate what the behaviours they want to have done. And it's really hard to evaluate a behavior without some sort of numeric to put through. Unless you're just sitting with them all the time and listening to the conversations or not. So, you have to put a number to say, well, you need to do this many things. Well, since you put a number on it, well, now, it's not that I'm trying to get the behaviours that you're trying to do, I'm trying to get that number. And that's where I think the struggle comes in. So, I don't know how you get, I definitely see my calls differently now than I did three years ago, than six years ago, 10 years ago because of these different themes that we've been adding to it and doing different things. But at the end of it all, it still says, OK, well, I get to 50% planning. So, I'm going to try something in here just to shoehorn a plan in. I can talk about the bigger, what we want to do as we manage this. We want to talk about how are we going as planned. But if literally I did a plan 10 months ago. And the markets have just kind of been along the line of a 5% growth over that 10 months. Zero has changed on that plan. We build a plan to say, what happens when the markets are good? What happens when the markets are bad? And it almost makes it seem like it to me, I feel like we're almost invalidating what we're doing by saying, well, every year we have to do another one, because every five years maybe I could see, every three years. But it's just, we're like, saying to clients, we do this to see what happens in different financial situations. And then we're saying, let's do it again or let's do it again, let's do it again. And that's where I think the conflict comes in, saying, 'This is what we'd like you to do - this is how we'd like it to look.' And by making it, the way we get you to do that is by putting a number in place. But it always ends up being, you know, 'Here is, here is the cheese, find it!' The rat will always get to it. But, not in the path that they necessarily want. And then they say, well, to put the cheese over here, OK, we'll always find a way to get those numbers. It's just not the behavior sometimes they want to get out of it.

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I thought it was interesting that we got really into planning at the height of a bull market, you know, and it's like, okay, so how do we make sure we don't lose clients? Well, we say that performance doesn't really matter as much and we have to talk about other things to obfuscate, you know, what we're doing.

But that's a really challenging thing to do when the sales business, who you solely rely on for incoming business, incoming clients, has sat in a meeting prior to you saying, oh, you only got 9% last year? I'm sure PC can do better than that. And I've been on phone calls when I've heard that said and that is the polar opposite of how we think about investing. So, I don't, and that's not fair to a client to, like, sign them up to something and then pivot the investment approach. I mean, we all get frustrated with performance driven clients, but to a degree, like, the frustration should be with our model, because if a client wants to go out-perform, they should go, you know, buy some active mutual funds or go find somebody else that wants to do that, because I know very few people in PC, that want, or are interested in doing that.

We're not free of conflict. No one is free. But I think we do a good job of minimizing some of the issues that are out there in the industry with conflicts. I think no one's perfect. I think we do a good job of serving the client. I think we do a good job of, if there's issues with the client. I think from that standpoint we do a really good job.

I go to the other issues of how we are incentivized to provide that, you know, the, the ideal or the illusion that we have to create for the client and for the FC of our time constraints, right? And how we are incited in reality.

We don't say that word capacity to a client because we have to be responsive. To the FC world and to that side of things internally to our internal partners, we absolutely have to pretend that we have this unlimited capacity.

It's when we get into that kind of question of, how many clients we are responsible for, whether being a client or an FC. That's really where you can't tell them. You can't tell the truth! You can't tell them you have 200 million or 206 clients.

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It's just, it's just they're concerned about quantity, whether or not too much quantity means too little quality...

Yeah, so to give an example from the other day. Market; as of today is, what, about twenty-nine-five on the Dow? I got a call from one of my clients who said he wanted to sell some of his high-quality bond funds, put more money in tech stocks and emerging market bonds and multi-sector bond funds that you take on a lot of risk and I wasn't comfortable with that.

You know, sometimes I ask myself that in a non-discretionary offer, we can't tell clients, no.

Or we could tell them, no. But we can't block them from doing something that's not in their best interest. All we can do is say, I don't think this is a great idea. And try and move them. And in this case, I was able to compromise a little bit, but I still think increasing risk at these levels is a bad idea. And I, I felt some pressure to sugar-coat it, because I didn't want to them to leave, because I didn't want the FC to stop sending me business.

But I have trouble sort of figuring out a better model where, you know, if something was not in the client's best interests that you could tell them no and not risk losing them. I don't think such a model exists.

I mean the main challenge is just the, the, the, the load itself. You know I'm one person to 215 clients

I've struggled with the Private Client Advisor role being a sales role.

Is, is this an advice, advised offer? Or, you know, kind of that. I struggle with why we have a sales component in our structure.

I think it's, I don't, I don't feel like we should have a sales component. I feel like that's the Financial Consultant's job. Do we have to have some type of incentive structure? Yes. Is it on retention? Is it on client service? Is it keeping the client's content? Is it, maybe, you know, some asset consolidation? What we are capable of doing there. But I think it's very hard to have those two roles both have a sales component.

I think the main thing is the practice sizes. Among most of them we've never really, you know, they started saying this was an ideal practice size and we don't hear anything about that anymore. So, it's really, you know, from my understanding, they are not, they are not concerned about decreasing your practice size.

I've never really shared the number of clients issue because I think that creates a barrier of them; scratching their head as to, "Ok, can she handle these new clients?" And that's the challenge is that, you know, you have so many clients already, but you still have an NSF goal.

I have to look at them as my customers if they're not giving me business, I'm not able to (meet my NSF targets).

I think that's, that's probably what I'm always thinking of when I come in, you know, over a weekend is what am I going to come into, an email of maybe who have I missed. Or who's, who, you know, dropped. You know, if there was a ball dropped.

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As far as devoting more time to some clients than others, well I don't think that every client, you know, should get the exact same amount of time. Because their needs are different, number one, and certainly someone that's paying you \$15,000. a year probably deserves a little more of your time than someone is paying you \$4,000. a year, you know. So, the larger clients that, I think it's just the nature of the business, larger clients will tend to get more of your, your focus, more of your time, because they've got more complex situations and it hurts more when they leave.

I know that it hurts them when a client leaves and they know that it hurts me when a client leaves and there is an understanding there.

Touchy subject. Because you don't want to just kick somebody out of your practice without working in conjunction with your FC because that FC is your business partner. And you don't want to burn bridges with your business partners.

With the FC, I will say I hold back a little bit, right? Look, I'm hesitant to, like, maybe sometimes push back more, just because of the way that, even though I don't have a large target, asset target- I've got a big practice. I mean, they're really the ones that close the business, right?

So, I do remember one of the question was, as a fiduciary do I have too many clients to serve them all well? I definitely would say in the affirmative. I absolutely agree with that. I think we; I think the 'God of scale' - that the firm worships that, right? I think in a relationship business, there's a finite number, right? And I think I don't remember exactly the order, but I know that I have a strong feeling. But I think the idea of 200 households, my perspective is really absurd, right?

And a lot of younger guys that are relatively new, it's, "I feel like I have to say yes to anything that comes my way, even though I feel like it's a dubious fit or it's maybe not appropriate or the investment philosophy that the client, maybe explicitly, you know, maybe explicit or implicit is not a strategy that I'm fully on board with, but I can't turn it away, right?"

Are we say, are we what we say we are, which is wealth managers? Because I think we were talking out of both sides of our mouth. I think we were marketing ourselves as wealth managers, but all of our energy was focused on sales. So, to me that was, that was a huge pit in my stomach. And it just, I just thought it was incongruent with all the marketing and you know how we position Private Client to prospects, right?

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So, I'm just saying I think that there are, there are obvious error areas that we overlook. And I think a lot of times we just assume that the client situation has remained the same. I mean, when we set up the appointments, we say is anything changed? The client will say yes or no. And we truly don't know. Like, I just had a client that, I don't know, she's in her 80s and scheduled her meeting. And "Has anything changed?" Well, no. "Any cash needs?" No. I mean, we asked the same questions over and over again. But turns out, you know, she's, she's, she lives on a 21-acre farm in Georgia. And you know, her kids don't want her living there on her own anymore. And so, unbeknownst to me, she's, you know, she sold her house and bought a townhouse and she's been mulling it for a while. And, you know, not any real, I mean, that's, that's, a planable event, right? That's something that maybe we perhaps should have explored in financial planning. What does that mean? What does that look like? And did we do that? No. One, because it happens so quickly, but two, we were unaware. And I think that gets down to because we, you know, we've, we've got, you've got, especially in my mind, it's very similar to what family physicians and medical field looks like right now. They book 15-minute appointments. That's what you get out. That's what they're allocated, you get 15 minutes. So how much can you really understand about a person's you know, total physical wellbeing in 15 minutes, right, you know, 5, 5-10 minutes that was probably just, "Hey, how you doing? What's going on in your world?" And then you got five minutes left? It's just simply not realistic. And I think similarly, with financial planning with, with, the portfolio. Oftentimes, my meetings go way over. And do I worry about that? As my practice continues to grow? Yeah, for sure. I worry that in order to be efficient, I need to scale back the length of my meetings. But I fear there's a loss not just relationship, but really understanding what's going on in the client's world and which trend has so many different translations? And then, you know, so let's say your appointment goes beyond what the expectation. Because I think management has the expectation that your meeting should be about 40-45 minutes with 15 minutes for wrap-up documentation, etc., etc. So it might easily go beyond that. And I feel like I'm gonna get in trouble at some point, but I don't feel like I'm doing the client service. If you look at how much these clients are charged from, you know, from a basis point perspective, not a lot, right? It's not a lot. But when you see the actual debit, hit your account, and you really start reflecting. So do I really think I got \$25,000 worth of value this year. Hmm. You know, when my portfolio consultant kind of blew in blew out, making a couple changes, made small talk and then you know, I don't know.

I have a few instances of that, you know, transition client that I got from somebody and not once have they taken any recommendations. In fact, they've, you know, won't meet with me. So, you know, how can you justify charging them? He's a CFA. I'm not exactly sure why he's in Private Client. He's on his mom's account as power of attorney. So, he's been managing his mom's account. So why are they in Private Client? But if I say anything, that's a million-dollar un-enrollment, and you know, then I gotta justify that. I can't even get them on the calendar.

You know, we always say that you were supposed to do what's right for the client, but we're really, it's, I feel like there is a lot of pressure to keep clients enrolled simply because it impacts Financial Consultant money, you know, FCs compensation. And, you know, furthermore you know, because then they gotta, they got to make that up right? It rolls up into, into, their sales figures which puts pressure on them with their manager. So, it's like you're on the front line and you do everything to manage. Remember that, that was in the environment of I need this financial consultant to send me business and if a hack him off, is he going to send me business because I'm unenrolling clients? Yeah, I really think that, that's, that's the predominant reason why we do that and is that really in the best interest of clients? I don't know.

Or, or suggest them not working with me. Maybe another Portfolio, a Private Client Advisor instead. You may get kind of that pushback or there's that, I mean, that may suggest you're difficult to do business with, you're kind of high maintenance or so there could be some of those where it's kind of feel like you need to take almost anything on. Or it could ultimately, you run the risk where people may not like you or they say, yeah, and they'll just find someone else to give business to.

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So, it varies. But I think for the most part, clients are pretty well qualified. Of course, you're going to get the ones that are just not on the same page and they're, they're, the FC is really trying to force something. You often find, like, like options is a great example of what they might throw in last minute to save a relationship. But I've been in that situation a few times now where it's just not the right fit. And then the client might vocalize that, and the FC just jumps on that, you know, oh, well, we can, we can do options for you, right? And then, you know, we bring in Jay in the conversation, and just like falls flat, you know? But luckily, those are few and far between.

I mean, that's a great question. I don't know if it's like an implied, it seems like it's almost implied in Private Client. Like, people don't fire, PCs don't fire clients.

I have 150 now, I'm considered, you know, a teenager. You know, some people have more mature books than mine, mine's only a teenager level. But anything, even at that level, it's not, it's not, not, not efficient, not feasible. So, you get, you, I think by default, you end up falling into that rut of every quarter, you know, every three months. You've got to have this call and you gotta talk about the market. You've got to place some trades! You gotta have some trades! You know, I've been getting better at not having trades. And that's going well with clients. But, you know, I think client and PC getting this, right? It's like, it's kind of, it comes to this.

But yeah, the IPSs and the Suitability, I'm sure it's probably, to some degree, regardless of which firms you go to, I think at Morgan, it was something similar. But yeah, it just seems a little bit burdensome, you know, and it's in, you know, when the when the expectation is, you know, you just do Suitability, you just check the box, and you move on. You know, it's like it's the last of my priorities. You know, if the expectation really was to use, use Suitability as a way to, to have a conversation and meaningful conversation with the client? Then that's different. But that would be overly burdensome. I mean, that would be almost impossible, in my view. Every time, every time, every year, you'd have to, have a, you know, run down this laundry list to really be able to, to cross your T's and dot your I's. But you'd have to ask about a slew of issues, which just, I think if you did it every year, it would just seem so, so non-sequitur to the client.

You know, the IPS and getting the fact-finder information there from them. Because realistically, it's, it's a little backwards in the way that, that, that we sometimes approach this in the sense that they want to make sure that their investments are lined up, you know, what's kind of their preferences and needs. But until we actually run that plan, and identify what those needs are, and maybe they're taking more risks than what's really warranted for the success for the plan, if you kind of, be, like a little a little backwards the way that we approach it and, and I think what the clients want as well.

I still think the one area that that needs, there needs some refining is, is meeting those, those planning numbers and what is considered delivering a plan versus just having planning conversations that are meaningful and helpful to a client. I think that's where you're gonna see a lot of boxes checked. In the sense that we have to complete this plan, well, let's just go on ahead and "Hey, what's your what's your monthly spending? What's your income? You know, what's your Social Security," and then we throw together this plan. "Here's your Monte Carlo simulation. There you go." We checked the box, right? It's not real detailed, meaningful planning. You know, what are some concerns that you have? Are you putting in those stress factors of here's what, you know, two years of long-term care event will do to your plan or just asking them those questions have left concerning you versus just throwing these numbers into a planning software and projecting some numbers.

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I think when you put numbers to anything, there's going to be, you know, not necessarily unethical things, but you're, you're going to your competitive nature, is going to take in, into effect there and you want to do your best and if you want to provide for your team and for yourself, so when there was the, you know, the quantitative metrics there of hitting planning and hitting assets and stuff, you know, there was maybe a little bit, a little bit more of a, you know, these, these CDs that we recommended here to you, you know, we made the recommendation on these and they're sitting in the account, so you should be paying a fee on those. Versus, hey, we've got no intention to sell these. Maybe they should be in a non- PC account, where you're not paying a fee and then as they mature, then maybe we decide what we want to do. I think there can be a little, a little bit of that, but for the sense of not making unsuitable recommendations based on pay I really like that aspect of Private Client, right?

And so, I, you know, for my clients, every practice is different, but you know for mine, or why clients are doing covered calls. They want more individual stocks in your portfolio, and they find their way to me and I'm the only one that will do it, or there's not a lot of people that will do it with clients. They don't care as much about planning it's not where they see value and see value in customizing your portfolio, trying to push planning down their throat when they don't want it, so I can get my tick mark.

And the 'check the box' thing has one thing though, that I think we do run into, is that we are asked to do; when, when you're being measured on numerical metrics, someone's gonna find a way to get over that hurdle in a way that might not be the most, they might not fit, they'll get the desired, desired response, without the required steps. Because of the fact that, if you're planning numbers says this, well, I'm gonna run some plans that, maybe, I don't think ethically incur unethical, but they're, I don't know they're productive either. It's just I need to get a number. And so, I'm going to do my Investment Policy Statements - 100 in one day to get them off. Does that create any quality? No. But it 'checks the box' to say we're, we're done.

Yes, so that definitely happens. That's happened since day one. That, that I think will, because it's never... their, their role in some ways is in contrast to our role, not in contrast, but, but in more of, it's just, it's different. And because of that, they're going to be incented to get people through the door and hope it works. And if it doesn't, they're going to get a little bit of a sting. But their hope is, they get it to us and we then wrangle the wild horse and get it in the pen. And if we can do that, then we're gonna, then they appreciate us and they like us, and you know they'll give us, you know, they'll keep bringing it to us. And so that's where, for what we do, it's so vital for us to try and figure out, even if it's somebody who might be a bad fit. And I guess maybe this isn't an ethical as much as it's just awkward, to try and find a way to make that client who doesn't necessarily fit, how can we keep them in? Because it's it hurts everybody. It helps everybody on the way in and hurts everybody on the way out and we're the ones who work the back door. So, we've got to try and do everything we can to keep him in that place.

I, I don't, I, I'm, I'm very much a dyed-in-the-wool of kind of what we do. And so, I try really hard. You know, occasionally there is there is the, I will, I will bend. But I won't break. So, if it's something that somebody wants something ... I absolutely can't recommend things beyond what we're allowed to recommend. But if it's something where a client wants to do something that I think is, is not 100% within what we're trying to do, but maybe is 75% what we're trying to do, then I will try to find a way to make that then work for them. Because I just get, I honestly, I get tired of trying to fight them on it.

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It's, it's tough because I feel like a lot of, over the years and having been doing this for as long as I have, the vast majority of things, the bigger themes that they, that they work on us with, are, they are, they kind of bring out in terms of, you know, CPS or IPS or planning or whatever it might be, I feel like it's 75% good. And I feel like it is trending us in a direction that is, that is better at, at the end. Because I do think that things like planning are more holistic, because I've got so many times where I meet somebody, and I have three things to do in their portfolio. So, it is nice to have a broader conversation, to have other things to work on. So, I get the idea behind it. The issue is always, here is a number. And it is not ... What they're trying to do is find a way to evaluate what the behaviors they want to have done. And it's really hard to evaluate a behavior without some sort of numeric to put through. Unless you're just sitting with them all the time and listening to the conversations or not. So, you have to put a number to say, well, you need to do this many things. Well, since you put a number on it, well now, it's not that I'm trying to get the behaviors that you're trying to do, I'm trying to get that number. And that's where I think the struggle comes in. So, I don't know how you get, I definitely see my calls differently now than I did three years ago, than six years ago, 10 years ago because of these different themes that we've been adding to it and doing different things. But at the end of it all, it still says, OK, well, I get to 50% planning. So, I'm going to try something in here just to shoehorn a plan in. I can talk about the bigger, what we want to do as we manage this. We want to talk about how are we going as planned. But if literally I did a plan 10 months ago. And the markets have just kind of been along the line of a 5% growth over that 10 months. Zero has changed on that plan. We build a plan to say what happens when the markets are good? What happens when the markets are bad? And it almost makes it seem like it to me, I feel like we're almost invalidating what we're doing by saying, well, every year we have to do another one, because every five years maybe I could see, every three years. But, it's just, we're like, saying to clients, we do this to see what happens in different financial situations. And then we're saying, let's do it again or let's do it again, let's do it again. And that's where I think the conflict comes in, saying, 'This is what we'd like you to do - this is how we'd like it to look.' And by making it, the way we get you to do that is by putting a number in place. But it always ends up being, you know, 'Here is, here is the cheese, find it!' The rat will always get to it. But, not in the path that they necessarily want. And then they say, well, to put the cheese over here, OK. We'll always find a way to get those numbers. It's just not the behavior sometimes they want to get out of it.

I thought it was interesting that we got really into planning at the height of a bull market, you know, and it's like, okay, so how do we make sure we don't lose clients? Well, we say that performance doesn't really matter as much and we have to talk about other things to obfuscate, you know, what we're doing.

Keep in mind that clients equate activity with progress and then the sister statement that inactivity is the advisor being asleep at the wheel.

I'm still sometimes totally unclear on who my real client is, whether it's the client or the FC. You know what I mean? And who I should make happy first and whose needs matter more. I mean, I know at the end of the day, theoretically, it should be the person that is doing business with the firm, the client. You know, all too often there's just, there's always this, maybe pressure is too heavy handed of a word, but maybe it's not on the branch optics on a situation and how the branch views what we say and what we do.

But that's a really challenging thing to do when the sales business, who you solely rely on for incoming business, incoming clients, has sat in a meeting prior to you saying, oh, you only got 9% last year? I'm sure PC can do better than that. And I've been on phone calls when I've heard that said and that is the polar opposite of how we think about investing. So, I don't, and that's not fair to a client to, like, sign them up to something and then pivot the investment approach. I mean, we all get frustrated with performance driven clients, but to a degree, like, the frustration should be with our model, because if a client wants to go out-perform, they should go, you know, buy some active mutual funds or go find somebody else that wants to do that, because I know very few people in Private Client, that want, or are interested in doing that.

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I mean, we talk, Private Client talks all the time about how profitable their clients are, right? But one of the main, I think the biggest reason, one of the biggest reasons I have to think clients leave their advisors is just because they don't feel like they hear from them, right? So, to me, that's really clear logic. Like you've got a vested interest in keeping clients happy, right? When clients are paying at least, what, between four to 10 grand a year on average in fees, like if you need to, to press pause for a bit and just work your existing book without having to worry about how branch reps perceive you, you know? Because I think that's the real problem. The real, one of the big concerns,

Often there are some clients that are too obsessed with, they're never going to be happy unless they're beating whatever arbitrary index they've decided as their benchmark.

I think, I think one of the hardest things is contact strategy. And this is something that, as an advisor that has really only been in the industry during a bull market, realistically. I've yet to see this happen. And I don't know what's going to happen at Private Client, but what happens when we have a year when the S&P is down 20%? Like, so these clients, because we preach asset allocation and hopefully people are, that's resonating. But I would assume that if we do have a year where the market crashes, so to speak, those clients are going to want to be talked to all the time about their portfolio and they're going to expect proactive outreach. And I don't, even like on a book of 175 clients, unless everybody, maybe I'm, maybe I'm not giving clients enough credit, but my, my assumption is they're all gonna want to get a phone call to talk about it and they're going to want to make changes that they would perceive as activity. That's what I'm paying for.

I mean, you know, the whole, I mean the other dumb thing is, is 'everybody needs a plan'. No, everyone doesn't need a plan. Everyone should need help.

We all know that we have some of that, you know, looking at capacity again, with asked to do more, and then come back and said, Okay, then how does that fit into trying to do a quality job for each individual when the conveyor belts moving faster than it ever has before in the industry?

You know, when you kind of have that sprocket spinning and you're like, Okay, this one doesn't belong here, the stress kind of goes up. And, you know, you don't feel like it's going to be a good working relationship. But you can't be as honest you would like to be if you own the firm, and, you know, either little know up front that it's not gonna be a good fit or just not accept the assignment.

So, a couple of years ago we still wanted to do financial plans for clients but we were told, you know, update the plan every three to five years or unless something major changes. You know, then, then we'll revisit it. And we had let the client know, let us, you know, we'd get the client agreement to do a financial plan. But now to meet, to meet numbers, I'm getting the message, refresh it every year. And really try and force it on the clients who haven't had one done before. So, you know that, that's, that's kind of frustrating.

Probably most recently it's the goal of planning penetration and I get the sense that, you know, and just look at clients who've had plans done in the last year or two, and just send it out, you know, update the assets and send it out. You don't even need to talk to the client before you send it out. And I'm uncomfortable with that. Maybe a handful of clients I can do that with because they have very simple plans, you know, they're retired and they only have Social Security and a pension, that's it. So that's easy enough. But otherwise, I want to make sure that the information in the plan that I'm sending them is correct and still, still relevant. So, you know, trying to get plans out to get my planning penetration numbers up, I don't necessarily like that.

But you know, you kind of danced that fine line there of saying no, I'm, I'm not going to take this client because I don't think that they're actually a right fit to an FC because, essentially, you know, our FCs are our biggest clients, right - where, where our business comes from. So, to sit there and say, no, I don't think this is a great fit. I'll say, personally, Brad and myself, with us still having capacity and getting up to, to that point, we're not necessarily in the position to do too much as far as our picking and choosing - just to not burn any of those bridges with, with FCs.

End of Section

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It's just, it's just they're concerned about quantity, whether or not too much quantity means too little quality...

I mean the main challenge is just the, the, the, the load itself. You know I'm one person to 215 clients

I've struggled with the Private Client Advisor role being a sales role.

Is, is this an advice, advised offer? Or, you know, kind of that. I struggle with why we have a sales component in our structure.

I think it's, I don't I don't feel like we should have a sales component. I feel like that's the Financial Consultant's job. Do we have to have some type of incentive structure? Yes. Is it on retention? Is it on client service? Is it keeping the client's content? Is it, maybe, you know, some asset consolidation? What we are capable of doing there? But I think it's very hard to have those two roles both have a sales component.

I think the main thing is the practice sizes. Among most of them we've never really, you know, they started saying this was an ideal practice size and we don't hear anything about that anymore. So, it's really, you know, from my understanding, they are not, they are not concerned about decreasing your practice size.

I think that's, that's probably what I'm always thinking of when I come in, you know, over a weekend is what am I going to come into, an email of maybe who have I missed. Or who's, who, you know, dropped. You know, if there was a ball dropped.

As far as devoting more time to some clients than others, well I don't think that every client, you know, should get the exact same amount of time. Because their needs are different, number one, and certainly someone that's paying you \$15,000 a year probably deserves a little more of your time than someone is paying you 4,000 a year, you know. So the larger clients that, I think it's just the nature of the business, larger clients will tend to get more of your, your focus, more of your time, because they've got more complex situations and it hurts more when they leave.

So, I do remember one of the questions was, as a fiduciary do I have too many clients to serve them all well? I definitely would say in the affirmative. I absolutely agree with that. I think we; I think the 'God of scale' - that the firm worships that, right? I think in a relationship business, there's a finite number, right? And I think I don't remember exactly the order, but I know that I have a strong feeling. But I think the idea of 200 households, my perspective is really absurd, right?

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I have a few instances of that, you know, transition client that I got from somebody and not once have they taken any recommendations. In fact, they've, you know, won't meet with me. So, you know, how can you justify charging them? He's a CFA. I'm not exactly sure why he's in private client. He's on his mom's account as power of attorney. So, he's been managing his mom's account. So why are they in private client? But if I say anything, that's a million-dollar un-enrollment, and you know, then I gotta justify that. I can't even get them on the calendar.

I think for the most part, The Organization is an ethical firm, I do think they act as an advocate for clients. I got to say a lot of my frustrations have been about, you know, that our acting as salespeople, that think that, that's going to go away even though we're not incented on it anymore think that that pressure still going to be there from the Financial Consultants, we're just not going to be rewarded or punished for it come bonus time. And you know that, that's one more thing. So, it's so ridiculous. They set these ridiculous targets that are almost inhuman to me. And so, you've got a few superstars - good for them. But you can hit your target, you can do everything that you're supposed to do, and you know, they, management, throughout the course of the year says, you know, you got to hit these targets, got to hit these targets, you've got to hit them. And then you do that. And when it comes around to evaluation, you're like, well, somebody, somebody hit those targets just a little bit better than us. So, we're going to take from you and give to somebody else. You're just like, really, if I live, this is what you said I needed to do, and I did it, and yet I'm still being punished. So, because somebody else either, you know, has a super relationship with you, you know, is tied or connected to a particular region that does well. So, you know, if you tell me that I need to do this and I do that, don't punish me, because you want to reward somebody else. Because to me in my mind, then I always have this moving target, you can tell me what I'm supposed to do. It doesn't, it doesn't have any meaning or validity to me because it's always moving.

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I mean, that's a great question. I don't know if it's like an implied, it seems like it's almost implied in Private Client. Like, people don't fire, PCs don't fire clients.

But yeah, the IPSs and the Suitability, I'm sure it's probably, to some degree, regardless of which firms you go to, I think at Morgan, it was something similar. But yeah, it just seems a little bit burdensome, you know, and it's in you know, when the, when the expectation is, you know, you just do Suitability, you just check the box, and you move on. You know, it's like it's the last of my priorities. You know, if the expectation really was to you use Suitability as a way to, to have a conversation and meaningful conversation with the client? Then that's different. But that would be overly burdensome. I mean, that would be almost impossible, in my view. Every time, every time, every year, you'd have to, have a, you know, run down this laundry list to really be able to, to cross your T's and dot your I's. But you'd have to ask about a slew of issues, which just, I think if you did it every year, it would just seem so, so non-sequitur to the client.

You know, the IPS and getting the fact-finder information there from them. Because realistically, it's, it's a little backwards in the way that, that, that we sometimes approach this in the sense that they want to make sure that their investments are lined up, you know, what's kind of their preferences and needs. But until we actually run that plan, and identify what those needs are, and maybe they're taking more risks than what's really warranted for the success for the plan, if you, kind of be like a little, a little backwards the way that we approach it and, and I think what the clients want as well.

But you know, you kind of danced that fine line there of saying no, I'm, I'm not going to take this client because I don't think that they're actually a right fit to an FC because, essentially, you know, our FCs are our biggest clients, right - where, where our business comes from. So, to sit there and say, no, I don't think this is a great fit. I'll say, personally, Brad and myself, with us still having capacity and getting up to, to that point, we're not necessarily in the position to do too much as far as our picking and choosing - just to not burn any of those bridges with, with FCs.

Statements / Phrases Coded to Aggressive Sales

I think when you put numbers to anything, there's going to be, you know, not necessarily unethical things, but you're, you're going to your competitive nature, is going to take in, into effect there and you want to do your best and if you want to provide for your team and for yourself, so when there was the, you know, the quantitative metrics there of hitting planning and hitting assets and stuff, you know, there was maybe a little bit, a little bit more of a, you know, these, these CDs that we recommended here to you, you know, we made the recommendation on these and they're sitting in the account, so you should be paying a fee on those. Versus, hey, we've got no intention to sell these. Maybe they should be in a non PCA account, where you're not paying a fee and then as they mature, then maybe we decide what we want to do. I think there can be a little, a little bit of that, but for the sense of not making unsuitable recommendations based on pay I really like that aspect of Private Client, right?

And so, I, you know, for my clients, every practice is different, but you know, for mine, or why clients are doing covered calls. They want more individual stocks in your portfolio, and they find their way to me and I'm the only one that will do it, or there's not a lot of people that will do it with clients. They don't care as much about planning it's not where they see value and see value in customizing your portfolio, trying to push planning down their throat when they don't want it, so I can get my tick mark.

And the 'check the box' thing has one thing though, that I think we do run into, is that we are asked to do; when, when you're being measured on numerical metrics, someone's gonna find a way to get over that hurdle in a way that might not be the most, they might not fit, they'll get the desired, desired response, without the required steps. Because of the fact that, if you're planning numbers says this, well, I'm gonna run some plans that maybe, I don't think ethically incur unethical, but they're, I don't know they're productive either. It's just I need to get a number. And so, I'm going to do my Investment Policy Statements – 100 in one day to get them off. Does that create any quality? No. But it 'checks the box' to say we're, we're done.

I thought it was interesting that we got really into planning at the height of a bull market, you know, and it's like, okay, so how do we make sure we don't lose clients? Well, we say that performance doesn't really matter as much and we have to talk about other things to obfuscate, you know, what we're doing.

I mean, we talk, PCA talks all the time about how profitable their clients are, right? But one of the main, I think the biggest reason, one of the biggest reasons I have to think clients leave their advisors is just because they don't feel like they hear from them, right? So, to me, that's really clear logic. Like you've got a vested interest in keeping clients happy, right? When clients are paying at least, what, between four to 10 grand a year on average in fees, like if you need to, to press pause for a bit and just work your existing book without having to worry about how branch reps perceive you, you know? Because I think that's the real problem. The real, one of the big concerns,

I mean, you know, the whole, I mean the other dumb thing is, is 'everybody needs a plan'. No, everyone doesn't need a plan. Everyone should need help.

We all know that we have some of that, you know, looking at capacity again, with asked to do more, and then come back and said, okay, then how does that fit into trying to do a quality job for each individual when the conveyor belts moving faster than it ever has before in the industry?

You know, when you kind of have that sprocket spinning and you're like, okay, this one doesn't belong here, the stress kind of goes up. And, you know, you don't feel like it's going to be a good working relationship. But you can't be as honest you would like to be if you own the firm, and, you know, either little "No" up front that it's not gonna be a good fit or just not accept the assignment.

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So, a couple of years ago we still wanted to do financial plans for clients, but we were told, you know, update the plan every three to five years or unless something major changes. You know, then, then we'll revisit it. And we had let the client know, let us, you know, we'd get the client agreement to do a financial plan. But now to meet, to meet numbers, I'm getting the message, refresh it every year. And really try and force it on the clients who haven't had one done before. So, you know that, that's, that's kind of frustrating.

Probably most recently it's the goal of planning penetration and I get the sense that, you know, and just look at clients who've had plans done in the last year or two, and just send it out, you know, update the assets and send it out. You don't even need to talk to the client before you send it out. And I'm uncomfortable with that. Maybe a handful of clients I can do that with because they have very simple plans, you know, they're retired and they only have Social Security and a pension, that's it. So that's easy enough. But otherwise, I want to make sure that the information in the plan that I'm sending them is correct and still, still relevant. So, you know, trying to get plans out to get my planning penetration numbers up, I don't necessarily like that.

I still think the one area that that needs, there needs some refining is, is meeting those, those, planning numbers and what is considered delivering a plan versus just having planning conversations that are meaningful and helpful to a client? I think that's where you're gonna see a lot of boxes checked. In the sense that we have to complete this plan. Well, let's just go on ahead and Hey, what's your what's your monthly spending? What's your income? You know, what's your Social Security, and then we throw together this plan. Here's your Monte Carlo simulation. There you go. We checked the box, right? It's not real, detailed, meaningful planning. You know, what are some concerns that you have? Are you putting in those stress factors of here's what, you know, two years of long-term care went with due to your plan or just asking them those questions have left concerning you versus just throwing these numbers into a planning software and projecting some numbers

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Statements / Phrases Coded to Aggressive Sales - Pressure from Clients Logic

Yeah, so to give an example from the other day: Market, as of today is, what, about twenty-nine-five on the Dow? I got a call from one of my clients who said he wanted to sell some of his high-quality bond funds, put more money in tech stocks and emerging market bonds and multi sector bond funds that you take on a lot of risk and I wasn't comfortable with that.

You know, sometimes I ask myself that in a non-discretionary offer, we can't tell clients no.

But I have trouble sort of figuring out a better model where, you know, if something was not in the client's best interests that you could tell them no and not risk losing them. I don't think such a model exists.

I have 150 now, I'm considered, you know, a teenager. You know, some people have more mature books than mine, mine's only a teenager level. But anything, even at that level, it's not, it's not, not, not efficient, not feasible. So, you get, you, I think by default, you end up falling into that rut of every quarter, you know, every three months, you've got to have this call and you gotta talk about the market. You've got to place some trades! You gotta have some trades! You know, I've been getting better at not having trades. And that's going well with clients. But, you know, I think client and PC getting this, right? It's like, it's kind of, it comes to this.

You know, the IPS and getting the fact-finder information there from them. Because realistically, it's, it's a little backwards in the way that, that, that we sometimes approached this in the sense that they want to make sure that their investments are lined up, you know, what's kind of their preferences and needs. But until we actually run that plan, and identify what those needs are, and maybe they're taking more risks than what's really warranted for the success for the plan, if you kind of, be like a little, a little backwards the way that we approach it and, and I think what the clients want as well.

I, I don't, I, I'm, I'm very much a dyed-in-the-wool of kind of what we do. And so, I try really hard. You know, occasionally there is there is the, I will, I will bend. But I won't break. So, if it's something that somebody wants something ... I absolutely can't recommend things beyond what we're allowed to recommend. But if it's something where a client wants to do something that I think is, is not 100% within what we're trying to do, but maybe is 75% what we're trying to do, then I will try to find a way to make that then work for them. Because I just get, I honestly, I get tired of trying to fight them on it.

Keep in mind that clients equate activity with progress and then the sister statement that; inactivity is the advisor being asleep at the wheel.

Often there are some clients that are too obsessed with, they're never going to be happy unless they're beating whatever arbitrary index they've decided as their benchmark.

I think, I think one of the hardest things is contact strategy. And this is something that, as an advisor that has really only been in the industry during a bull market, realistically. I've yet to see this happen. And I don't know what's going to happen at PCA, but what happens when we have a year when the S&P is down 20%? Like, so these clients, because we preach asset allocation and hopefully people are, that's resonating. But I would assume that if we do have a year where the market crashes, so to speak. Those clients are going to want to be talked to all the time about their portfolio and they're going to expect proactive outreach. And I don't, even like on a book of 175 clients, unless everybody, maybe I'm, maybe I'm not giving clients enough credit, but my, my assumption is they're all gonna want to get a phone call to talk about it and they're going to want to make changes that they would perceive as activity. That's what I'm paying for.

END OF SECTION

Statements / Phrases Coded to Aggressive Sales - Pressure from FCs Logic

Or we could tell them, no. But we can't block them from doing something that's not in their best interest. All we can do is say, I don't think this is a great idea. And try and move them. And in this case, I was able to compromise a little bit, but I still think increasing risk at these levels is a bad idea. And I, I felt some pressure to sugar-coat it, because I didn't want to leave, because I didn't want the FC to stop sending me business.

I've never really shared the number of clients issue because I think that creates a barrier of them; scratching their head as to, "Ok, can she handle these new clients?" And that's the challenge is that, you know, you have so many clients already, but you still have an NSF goal.

I know that it hurts them when a client leaves and they know that it hurts me when a client leaves and there is an understanding there.

Touchy subject. Because you don't want to just kick somebody out of your practice without working in conjunction with your FC because that FC is your business partner. And you don't want to burn bridges with your business partners.

With the FC, I will say I hold back a little bit, right? Look, I'm hesitant to, like, maybe sometimes push back more, just because of the way that, even though I don't have a large target, asset target- I've got a big practice. I mean, they're really the ones that close the business, right?

And a lot of younger guys that are relatively new, it's, "I feel like I have to say yes to anything that comes my way, even though I feel like it's a dubious fit or it's maybe not appropriate or the investment philosophy that the client, maybe explicitly, you know, maybe explicit or implicit is not a strategy that I'm fully on board with, but I can't turn it away, right?"

I have a few instances of that, you know, transition client that I got from somebody and not once have they taken any recommendations. In fact, they've, you know, won't meet with me. So, you know, how can you justify charging them? He's a CFA. I'm not exactly sure why he's in Private Client. He's on his mom's account as power of attorney. So, he's been managing his mom's account. So why are they in private client? But if I say anything, that's a million-dollar un-enrollment, and you know, then I gotta justify that. I can't even get them on the calendar.

You know, we always say that you were supposed to do what's right for the client, but we're really, it's, I feel like there is a lot of pressure to keep clients enrolled simply because it impacts Financial Consultant money, you know, FCs compensation. And, you know, furthermore you know, because then they gotta, they got to make that up right? It rolls up into, into their sales figures which puts pressure on them with their manager. So, it's like you're on the front line and you do everything to manage. Remember that, that was in the environment of I need this Financial Consultant to send me business and if a hack him off, is he going to send me business because I'm unenrolling clients? Yeah, I really think that, that's, that's the predominant reason why we do that and is that really in the best interest of clients? I don't know.

Statements / Phrases Coded to Aggressive Sales - Pressure from FCs Logic

I think for the most part, The Organization is an ethical firm, I do think they act as an advocate for clients. I got to say a lot of my frustrations have been about, you know that our acting is salespeople, that think that that's going to go away even though we're not incented on it anymore think that, that pressure still going to be there from the Financial Consultants, we're just not going to be rewarded or punished for it come bonus time. And you know that, that's one more thing. So, it's so ridiculous. They set these ridiculous targets that are almost inhuman to me. And so, you've got a few superstars- good for them. But you can hit your target, you can do everything that you're supposed to do, and, you know, they, management, throughout the course of the year says, you know, you got to hit these targets, got to hit these targets, you've got to hit them. And then you do that. And when it comes around to evaluation, you're like, well, somebody, somebody hit those targets just a little bit better than us. So, we're going to take from you and give to somebody else. You're just like, really, if I live, this is what you said I needed to do, and I did it, and yet I'm still being punished. So, because somebody else either, you know, has a super relationship with you, you know, has tied or connected to a particular region that does well. So, you know, if you tell me that I need to do this and I do that, don't punish me, because you want to reward somebody else. Because to me in my mind, then I always have this moving target. You can tell me what I'm supposed to do. It doesn't, it doesn't have any meaning or validity to me because it's always moving.

Or, or suggest them not working with me. Maybe another portfolio, a Private Client Advisor instead. You may get kind of that pushback or there's that, I mean, that may suggest you're difficult to do business with, you're kind of high maintenance or so there could be some of those where it's kind of feel like you need to take almost anything on. Or it could ultimately, you run the risk where people may not like you or they say, yeah, and they'll just find someone else to give business to.

So, it varies. But I think for the most part, clients are pretty well qualified. Of course, you're going to get the ones that are just not on the same page and they're, they're, the FCs is really trying to force something. You often find, like, like options is a great example of what they might throw in last minute to save a relationship. But I've been in that situation a few times now where it's just not the right fit. And then the client might vocalize that, and the FC just jumps in that, you know, oh, well, we can, we can do options for you, right? And then, you know, we bring in Jay in the conversation, and just like falls flat, you know? But luckily, those are few and far between.

I mean, that's a great question. I don't know if it's like an implied, it seems like it's almost implied in Private Client. Like, people don't fire, PCs don't fire clients.

But you know, you kind of danced that fine line there of saying no, I'm, I'm not going to take this client because I don't think that they're actually a right fit to an FC because, essentially, you know, our FCs are our biggest clients, right - where, where our business comes from. So, to sit there and say, no, I don't think this is a great fit. I'll say, personally, Brad and myself, with us still having capacity and getting up to, to that point, we're not necessarily in the position to do too much as far as our picking and choosing - just to not burn any of those bridges with, with FCs.

Yes, so that definitely happens. That's happened since day one. That, that I think will, because it's never... their, their role in some ways is in contrast to our role, not in contrast, but, but in more of, it's just, it's different. And because of that, they're going to be incented to get people through the door and hope it works. And if it doesn't, they're going to get a little bit of a sting. But their hope is, they get it to us and we then wrangle the wild horse and get it in the pen. And if we can do that, then we're gonna, then they appreciate us and they like us, and you know they'll give us, you know, they'll keep bringing it to us. And so that's where, for what we do, it's so vital for us to try and figure out, even if it's somebody who might be a bad fit. And I guess maybe this isn't an ethical as much as it's just awkward, to try and find a way to make that client who doesn't necessarily fit, how can we keep them in? Because it's it hurts everybody. It helps everybody on the way in and hurts everybody on the way out and we're the ones who work the back door. So, we've got to try and do everything we can to keep him in that place.

Statements / Phrases Coded to Aggressive Sales - Pressure from FCs Logic

I'm still sometimes totally unclear on who my real client is, whether it's the client or the FC. You know what I mean? And who I should make happy first and whose needs matter more. I mean, I know at the end of the day, theoretically, it should be the person that is doing business with the firm, the client. You know, all too often there's just, there's always this, maybe pressure is too heavy handed of a word, but maybe it's not on the branch optics on a situation and how the branch views what we say and what we do.

But that's a really challenging thing to do when the sales business, who you solely rely on for incoming business, incoming clients, has sat in a meeting prior to you saying, oh, you only got 9% last year? I'm sure Private Client can do better than that. And I've been on phone calls when I've heard that said and that is the polar opposite of how we think about investing. So, I don't, and that's not fair to a client to, like, sign them up to something and then pivot the investment approach. I mean, we all get frustrated with performance driven clients, but to a degree, like, the frustration should be with our model, because if a client wants to go out-perform, they should go, you know, buy some active mutual funds or go find somebody else that wants to do that, because I know very few people in Private Client, that want, or are interested in doing that.

END OF SECTION

Statements / Phrases Coded to Service Logic

I help people sort of take control of their financial destiny, and I think that's important. People get divorced over money issues. People get anxiety over money issues. It's something that we can alleviate to some degree for folks and I, I'm going to take personal pride in being able to do that for folks.

It's just it's just they're concerned about quantity, whether or not too much quantity means too little quality...

Is, is this an advice, advised offer? Or, you know, kind of that. I struggle with why we have a sales component in our structure.

Do we have to have some type of incentive structure? Yes. Is it on retention? Is it on client service? Is it keeping the client's content? Is it, maybe, you know, some asset consolidation? What we are capable of doing there. But I think it's very hard to have those two roles both have a sales component.

So, I think from, you know, talking to other PCAs, I think that the, the clients, the number of clients that we're asked to manage is, you know, it's a, it's a hard, hard thing to do.

I have to look at them as my customers. If they're not giving me business, I'm not able to hit my NSF target.

I, it's kind of nice for us to have autonomy, like we don't really have anybody really second guessing us. But, I mean, that's where I think the value is for clients. When you have like a think tank of people who really, like, really try to think through what's best for the client. That is one person coming up with the solution. It's like, OK, this is what (I) proposed, but maybe this other professional has a different opinion.

But yeah, it just seems a little bit burdensome, you know, and it's in, you know, when the when the expectation is, you know, you just do Suitability, you just check the box, and you move on. You know, it's like it's the last of my priorities.

I'd say kind of the reason why I got into this Private Client as a whole and that was more to develop relationships with clients and really help them with their ongoing wealth management.

Statements / Phrases Coded to Service Logic

I still think the one area that that needs, there needs some refining is, is meeting those, those planning numbers and what is considered delivering a plan versus just having planning conversations that are meaningful and helpful to a client. I think that's where you're gonna see a lot of boxes checked. In the sense that we have to complete this plan. Well, let's just go on ahead and "Hey, what's your, what's your monthly spending? What's your income? You know, what's your Social Security," and then we throw together this plan. " Here's your Monte Carlo simulation. There you go." We checked the box, right? It's not real detailed, meaningful planning. You know, what are some concerns that you have? Are you putting in those stress factors of here's what, you know, two years of long-term care event will do to your plan or just asking them those questions have left concerning you versus just throwing these numbers into a planning software and projecting some numbers

I think the most challenging is we have too many clients, we really need a deeper dive with each client. You know, I think maybe with some other RIAs they have you know, less clients or more defined roles. You know, planners can do a better job of, you know, looking at maybe a client's tax situation and analysing other assets that they have pulling that all together to give them deeper financial advice. Advice outside of just going to more of a portfolio. I don't think that we can do that very well with the number of clients that we have. It's just not possible.

And the 'check the box' thing has one thing though, that I think we do run into, is that we are asked to do; when, when you're being measured on numerical metrics, someone's gonna find a way to get over that hurdle in a way that might not be the most, they might not fit, they'll get the desired, desired response, without the required steps. Because of the fact that, if you're planning numbers says this. Well, I'm gonna run some plans that maybe, I don't think ethically incur unethical, but they're, I don't know they're productive either. It's just I need to get a number. And so, I'm going to do my Investment Policy Statements - 100 in one day to get them off. Does that create any quality? No. But it 'checks the box' to say we're, we're done.

It's hard for me to pick a specific one, but like, it's awkward when a client asks how often do you review my investments because they have an assumption that we're constantly looking at them adjusting things and it's more like four times a year at most.

Because of my workload, I feel I worry about the possibility of important things falling through the cracks.

Statements / Phrases Coded to Service Logic

I think, I think one of the hardest things is contact strategy. And this is something that, as an advisor that has really only been in the industry during a bull market, realistically. I've yet to see this happen. And I don't know what's going to happen at Private Client, but what happens when we have a year when the S&P is down 20%? Like, so these clients, because we preach asset allocation and hopefully people are, that's resonating. But I would assume that if we do have a year where the market crashes, so to speak, those clients are going to want to be talked to all the time about their portfolio and they're going to expect proactive outreach. And I don't, even like on a book of 175 clients, unless everybody, maybe I'm, maybe I'm not giving clients enough credit, but my, my assumption is they're all gonna want to get a phone call to talk about it and they're going to want to make changes that they would perceive as activity. That's what I'm paying for.

Quality of interaction. And to me, that's just book size. It goes back to the matter of your workload, the amount of clients you have, but the quality of your notes and what you're detailing is going to suffer. Which this means, which means, again, when you go to think about this person again for the first time in three months, you know, to touch base with them, you look back at that last interaction, you, boy, you didn't really talk about much, even though you may have, right? To write, because your notes, you were just under the gun to try to get that done. That's one small example.

END OF SECTION

Statements / Phrases Coded to Self-Determination Theory

I help people sort of take control of their financial destiny, and I think that's important. People get divorced over money issues; people get anxiety over money issues. It's something that we can alleviate to some degree for folks, and I I'm going to take personal pride in being able to do that for folks.

So as far as most gratifying, is just the relationships that I have felt with the clients over the years getting to know them their family, their personal situation.

I mean the main challenge is just the, the, the, the load itself. You know I'm one person to 215 clients

I think, you know, if we're all professionals and we're being asked to manage a practice, you know, how best to manage that practice as an individual,

And I don't think that they have preached to us that everybody has to be using it in the same way, necessarily. But, you know, yeah. Is there a, are there things that are a checkbox? You know, we spend the money on it so let's check the box and make sure that we're showing use of it. Yeah, I think that that exists.

I think the main thing is the practice sizes. Among most of them we've never really, you know, they started saying this was an ideal practice size and we don't hear anything about that anymore. So it's really, you know, from my understanding, they are not, they are not concerned about decreasing your practice size.

But I think, you know, you reach a certain level that you should just be able to try to maintain that, you know, plus or minus three or five clients, or what have you, you know, and try to make, because you know when you're at 210 clients, you know, and you're working 55 - 60 hours a week, can you really add 20 more clients to that? And, you know, without at some point just completely burning out. And do that year after year after year. No, I don't think you can.

Like, it's just like, you put the client in front of me, I'll do what I can to help them achieve what they need to achieve, right? I don't care how many video conference calls you want me to do, like that's your call. That's your decision, right? I'm not comfortable doing them.

So, I do remember one of the questions was, as a fiduciary do I have too many clients to serve them all well? I definitely would say in the affirmative. I absolutely agree with that. I think we; I think the 'God of scale' - that the firm worships that, right? I think in a relationship business, there's a finite number, right? And I think, I don't remember exactly the order, but I know that I have a strong feeling. But I think the idea of 200 households, my perspective is really absurd, right?

I think I probably also disagreed on having performance targets for financial planning, and topic solutions as a desirable way to motivate. Because just let me do, let me develop a relationship, in that if you have a good relationship with the client, you're going to address those issues in time rather than being forced to do it in a particular range.

So I love the idea of control in the sense that, let me, let me work with a size that I'm comfortable working with and I'll get to a point where I'm not comfortable anymore. And I'll know that, you know, if I'm getting too many, I'll maybe start looking for options, for alternatives.

Statements / Phrases Coded to Self-Determination Theory

I think what's gratifying about it is that at least where we work, right? It really does allow you to get to know a client on a very personal level and to really understand their circumstances, which I think I know it sounds silly, but I mean, it really is true that the more you know somebody, the more you tend to have a better grasp of their situation.

I think the some of the technology gets in the way, all these 'checky-checky' box, box stuff. I think if you really just had to simply manage your portfolio, do the financial planning. You know, update the record all that stuff. I think if you just simply had to do that task, it's certainly manageable, at least in my mind. To the extent that I have, you know, I can, I can scale up mentally from where I'm at to where what that goal number looks like. But I think what gets in the way, and I don't care about this, don't care about this. But I guess I think in my mind that all the technology and all the reporting and all that sense that goes on, in, in theory in support of these behaviours and, the, you know, the actual work that you're supposed to be doing all that kind of ancillary stuff is what causes practice sizes to become unmanageable.

Oh, sure, financial planning. Yeah, cuz there's a way you can even, you can push out a plan pretty quick. I mean, there's a way to do that. You just say, all right, well, what's the portfolio look like? If you know you only take out your RMDs, right. You know, we, we have a term for that internally, like internally. We've named it within our practice. And, you know, you just, you leave all the other planning out of it. So, it really just looks like what's that withdrawal rate, that draw down on the portfolio? Very simple. But does that really, is that beneficial to the client? Maybe? Maybe not. Do I feel that I've done an adequate job of financial planning for the client? Not at all. Not in the least bit.

I have a few instances of that, you know, transition client that I got from somebody and not once have they taken any recommendations. In fact, they've, you know, won't meet with me. So, you know, how can you justify charging them? He's a CFA. I'm not exactly sure why he's in Private Client. He's on his mom's account as power of attorney. So, he's been managing his mom's account. So why are they in Private Client? But if I say anything, that's a million-dollar un-enrolment, and you know, then I gotta justify that. I can't even get them on the calendar.

You know, we always say that you were supposed to do what's right for the client, but we're really, it's, I feel like there is a lot of pressure to keep clients enrolled simply because it impacts Financial Consultant money, you know, FCs compensation. And, you know, furthermore you know, because then they gotta, they got to make that up right? It rolls up into, into their sales figures which puts pressure on them with their manager. So, it's like you're on the front line and you do everything to manage. Remember that, that was in the environment of, I need this Financial Consultant to send me business and if a hack him off, is he going to send me business because I'm unenrolling clients? Yeah, I really think that, that's, that's the predominant reason why we do that and is that really in the best interest of clients? I don't know.

Or, or suggest them not working with me. Maybe another Portfolio, a Private Client Advisor instead. You may get kind of that pushback or there's that, I mean, that may suggest you're difficult to do business with, you're kind of high maintenance or so there could be some of those where it's kind of feel like you need to take almost anything on. Or it could ultimately, you run the risk where people may not like you or they say, yeah, and they'll just find someone else to give business to.

Statements / Phrases Coded to Self-Determination Theory

So, I think it's different for everybody. But for me, I've always really enjoyed the personal side. I mean, I, I'm a nerd. I can nerd-out with the best of them and with regard to markets and everything else. But I've come to realize, you know, it's my, my 11th, 12th year of doing this, that most clients, they all don't want to know how the sausage is made. They just, you know, they don't want to get that granular, right? So, I've learned to be a bit more, just relationship based. And I really, I really like that. You know, for me, I am very fortunate in the fact that I have a fairly large Indianapolis-based clientele. You know, as I'm often, like this week, I've been in the branches three times. Yes. That's not unusual for me. So, I, I personally thrive off that face-to-face personal interaction. So, I find that to be the most gratifying is, is just really getting know, getting to know my client on a more personal level, that, that's what I, that's what keeps me going.

So it varies. But I think for the most part, clients are pretty well qualified. Of course, you're going to get the ones that are just not on the same page and they're, they're, the FC is really trying to force something. You often find, like, like options is a great example of what they might throw in last minute to save a relationship. But I've been in that situation a few times now where it's just not the right fit. And then the client might vocalize that, and the FC just jumps on that, you know, oh, well, we can, we can do options for you, right? And then, you know, we bring in Jay in the conversation, and just like falls flat, you know? But luckily, those are few and far between.

But yeah, the IPSs and the Suitability, I'm sure it's probably, to some degree, regardless of which firms you go to, I think at Morgan, it was something similar. But yeah, it just seems a little bit burdensome, you know, and it's in, you know, when the, when the expectation is, you know, you just do Suitability, you just check the box, and you move on. You know, it's like it's the last of my priorities. You know, if the expectation really was for you to use Suitability as a way to, to have a conversation and meaningful conversation with the client? Then that's different. But that would be overly burdensome. I mean, that would be almost impossible, in my view. Every time, every time, every year, you'd have to, have a, you know, run down this laundry list to really be able to, to cross your T's and dot your I's. But you'd have to ask about a slew of issues, which just, I think if you did it every year, it would just seem so, so non-sequitur to the client.

I'd say kind of the reason why I got into this Private Client as a whole and that was more to develop relationships with clients and really help them with their ongoing wealth management.

But you know, you kind of danced that fine line there of saying no, I'm, I'm not going to take this client because I don't think that they're actually a right fit to an FC because, essentially, you know, our FCs are our biggest clients, right - where, where our business comes from. So, to sit there and say, no, I don't think this is a great fit. I'll say, personally, Brad and myself, with us still having capacity and getting up to, to that point, we're not necessarily in the position to do too much as far as our picking and choosing - just to not burn any of those bridges with, with FCs.

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I still think the one area that that needs, there needs some refining is, is meeting those, those planning numbers and what is considered delivering a plan versus just having planning conversations that are meaningful and helpful to a client? I think that's where you're gonna see a lot of boxes checked. In the sense that we have to complete this plan. Well, let's just go on ahead and "Hey, what's your what's your monthly spending? What's your income? You know, what's your Social Security," and then we throw together this plan. "Here's your Monte Carlo simulation. There you go." We checked the box, right? It's not real detailed, meaningful planning. You know, what are some concerns that you have? Are you putting in those stress factors of here's what, you know, two years of long-term care event would do to your plan or just asking them those questions have left concerning you versus just throwing these numbers into a planning software and projecting some numbers

And so, I, you know, for my clients, every practice is different, but you know for mine, or why clients are doing covered calls. They want more individual stocks in your portfolio, and they find their way to me and I'm the only one that will do it, or there's not a lot of people that will do it with clients. They don't care as much about planning. It's not where they see value and see value in customizing your portfolio. Trying to push planning down their throat when they don't want it, so I can get my tick mark.

I think they should treat us a little bit more as professionals and trust that we're providing the level of service for the clients that's working for us, not arbitrarily tell us.

And the 'check the box' thing has one thing though, that I think we do run into, is that we are asked to do; when, when you're being measured on numerical metrics, someone's gonna find a way to get over that hurdle in a way that might not be the most, they might not fit, they'll get the desired, desired response, without the required steps. Because of the fact that, if you're planning numbers says this, well, I'm gonna run some plans that maybe, I don't think ethically incur unethical, but they're, I don't know they're productive either. It's just I need to get a number. And so, I'm going to do my Investment Policy Statements - 100 in one day to get them off. Does that create any quality? No. But it 'checks the box' to say we're, we're done.

Yes, so that definitely happens. That's happened since day one. That, that I think will, because it's never... their, their role in some ways is in contrast to our role, not in contrast, but, but in more of, it's just, it's different. And because of that, they're going to be incented to get people through the door and hope it works. And if it doesn't, they're going to get a little bit of a sting. But their hope is, they get it to us and we then wrangle the wild horse and get it in the pen. And if we can do that, then we're gonna, then they appreciate us and they like us, and you know they'll give us, you know, they'll keep bringing it to us. And so that's where, for what we do, it's so vital for us to try and figure out, even if it's somebody who might be a bad fit. And I guess maybe this isn't an ethical as much as it's just awkward, to try and find a way to make that client who doesn't necessarily fit, how can we keep them in? Because it's it hurts everybody. It helps everybody on the way in and hurts everybody on the way out and we're the ones who work the back door. So, we've got to try and do everything we can to keep him in that place.

Statements / Phrases Coded to Self-Determination Theory

It's, it's tough because I feel like a lot of, over the years and having been doing this for as long as I have, the vast majority of things, the bigger themes that they, that they work on us with, are, they are, they kind of bring out in terms of, you know, CPS or IPS or planning or whatever it might be, I feel like it's 75% good. And I feel like it is trending us in a direction that is, that is better at, at the end. Because I do think that things like planning are more holistic, because I've got so many times where I meet somebody, and I have three things to do in their portfolio. So, it is nice to have a broader conversation, to have other things to work on. So, I get the idea behind it. The issue is always, here is a number. And it is not ... What they're trying to do is find a way to evaluate what the behaviors they want to have done. And it's really hard to evaluate a behavior without some sort of numeric to put through. Unless you're just sitting with them all the time and listening to the conversations or not. So, you have to put a number to say, well, you need to do this many things. Well, since you put a number on it, well now, it's not that I'm trying to get the behaviors that you're trying to do, I'm trying to get that number. And that's where I think the struggle comes in. So, I don't know how you get, I definitely see my calls differently now than I did three years ago, than six years ago, 10 years ago because of these different themes that we've been adding to it and doing different things. But at the end of it all, it still says, OK, well, I get to 50% planning. So, I'm going to try something in here just to shoehorn a plan in. I can talk about the bigger, what we want to do as we manage this. We want to talk about how are we going as planned. But if literally I did a plan 10 months ago. And the markets have just kind of been along the line of a 5% growth over that 10 months. Zero has changed on that plan. We build a plan to say what happens when the markets are good? What happens when the markets are bad? And it almost makes it seem like it to me, I feel like we're almost invalidating what we're doing by saying, well, every year we have to do another one, because every five years maybe I could see, every three years. But it's just, we're like, saying to clients, we do this to see what happens in different financial situations. And then we're saying, let's do it again or let's do it again, let's do it again. And that's where I think the conflict comes in, saying, 'This is what we'd like you to do - this is how we'd like it to look.' And by making it, the way we get you to do that is by putting a number in place. But it always ends up being, you know, 'Here is, here is the cheese, find it!' The rat will always get to it. But, not in the path that they necessarily want. And then they say, well, to put the cheese over here, OK. We'll always find a way to get those numbers. It's just not the behavior sometimes they want to get out of it.

Quality of interaction. And to me, that's just book size. It goes back to the matter of your workload, the amount of clients you have, but the quality of your notes and what you're detailing is going to suffer. Which this means, which means, again, when you go to think about this person again for the first time in three months, you know, to touch base with them, you look back at that last interaction, you, boy, you didn't really talk about much, even though you may have, right? To write, because your notes, you were just under the gun to try to get that done. That's one small example.

I mean, you know, the whole, I mean the other dumb thing is, is 'everybody needs a plan'. No, everyone doesn't need a plan. Everyone should need help.

So, a couple of years ago we still wanted to do financial plans for clients, but we were told, you know, update the plan every three to five years or unless something major changes. You know, then, then we'll revisit it. And we had let the client know, let us, you know, we'd get the client agreement to do a financial plan. But now to meet, to meet numbers, I'm getting the message, refresh it every year. And really try and force it on the clients who haven't had one done before. So, you know that that's, that's kind of frustrating.

Statements / Phrases Coded to Self-determination Theory - Intrinsic Motivation

I help people sort of take control of their financial destiny, and I think that's important. People get divorced over money issues. People get anxiety over money issues. It's something that we can alleviate to some degree for folks and I I'm going to take personal pride in being able to do that for folks.

I think I probably also disagreed on having performance targets for financial planning, and topic solutions as a desirable way to motivate. Because just let me do, let me develop a relationship, in that if you have a good relationship with the client, you're going to address those issues in time rather than being forced to do it in a particular range.

So as far as most gratifying is just the relationships that I have felt with the clients over the years getting to know them their family their personal situation.

I think what's gratifying about it is that at least where we work, right? It really does allow you to get to know a client on a very personal level and to really understand their circumstances, which I think I know it sounds silly, but I mean, it really is true that the more you know somebody, the more you tend to have a better grasp of their situation.

My main motivation for working is to help as many investors succeed as possible.

So, I think it's different for everybody. But for me, I've always really enjoyed the personal side. I mean, I, I'm a nerd. I can nerd-out with the best of them and with regard to markets and everything else. But I've come to realize, you know, it's my, my 11th, 12th year of doing this, that most clients, they all don't want to know how the sausage is made. They just, you know, they don't want to get that granular, right? So, I've learned to be a bit more, just relationship based. And I really, I really like that. You know, for me, I am very fortunate in the fact that I have a fairly large Indianapolis-based clientele. You know, as I'm often, like this week, I've been in the branches three times. Yes. That's not unusual for me. So, I, I personally thrive off that face-to-face personal interaction. So, I find that to be the most gratifying is, is just really getting know, getting to know my client on a more personal level, that, that's what I, that's what keeps me going.

I'd say kind of the reason why I got into this Private Client as a whole and that was more to develop relationships with clients and really help them with their ongoing wealth management.

END OF SECTION

Statements / Phrases Coded to Self-determination Theory - Professional Autonomy

I mean the main challenge is just the, the, the, the load itself. You know I'm one person to 215 clients

I think, you know, if we're all professionals and we're being asked to manage a practice, you know, how best to manage that practice as an individual

And I don't think that they have preached to us that everybody has to be using it in the same way, necessarily. But, you know, yeah, is there a, are there things that are a checkbox? You know, we spend the money on it so let's check the box and make sure that we're showing use of it. Yeah, I think that, that exists.

I think the main thing is the practice sizes. Among most of them we've never really, you know, they started saying this was an ideal practice size and we don't hear anything about that anymore. So, it's really, you know, from my understanding, they are not, they are not concerned about decreasing your practice size.

But I think, you know, you reach a certain level that you should just be able to try to maintain that, you know, plus or minus three or five clients, or what have you, you know, and try to make, because you know when you're at 210 clients, you know, and you're working 55-60 hours a week, can you really add 20 more clients to that? And, you know, without at some point just completely burning out. And do that year after year after year. No, I don't think you can.

Like, it's just like, you put the client of front of me, I'll do what I can to help them achieve what they need to achieve, right? I don't care how many video conference calls you want me to do, like that's your call. That's your decision, right? I'm not comfortable doing them.

So, I do remember one of the questions was, as a fiduciary do I have too many clients to serve them all well? I definitely would say in the affirmative. I absolutely agree with that. I think we; I think the 'God of scale' - that the firm worships that, right? I think in a relationship business, there's a finite number, right? And I think I don't remember exactly the order, but I know that I have a strong feeling. But I think the idea of 200 households, my perspective is really absurd, right?

I think I probably also disagreed on having performance targets for financial planning, and topic solutions as a desirable way to motivate. Because just let me do, let me develop a relationship, in that if you have a good relationship with the client, you're going to address those issues in time rather than being forced to do it in a particular range.

So, I love the idea of control in the sense that, let me, let me work with a size that I'm comfortable working with and I'll get to a point where I'm not comfortable anymore. And I'll know that, you know, if I'm getting too many, I'll maybe start looking for options, for alternatives.

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I think what's gratifying about it is that at least where we work, right? It really does allow you to get to know a client on a very personal level and to really understand their circumstances, which I think I know it sounds silly, but I mean, it really is true that the more you know somebody, the more you tend to have a better grasp of their situation.

I think the some of the technology gets in the way, all these 'checky-checky' box, box stuff. I think if you really just had to simply manage your portfolio, do the financial planning. You know, update the record all that stuff. I think if you just simply had to do that task, it's certainly manageable, at least in my mind. To the extent that I have, you know, I can, I can scale up mentally from where I'm at to where what that goal number looks like. But I think what gets in the way, and I don't care about this, don't care about this. But I guess I think in my mind that all the technology and all the reporting and all that sense that goes on, in, in theory in support of these behaviors and the, you know, the actual work that you're supposed to be doing all that kind of ancillary stuff is what causes practice sizes to become unmanageable.

Oh, sure, financial planning, yeah, cuz there's a way you can even, you can push out a plan pretty quick. I mean, there's a way to do that. You just say, all right, well, what's the portfolio look like? If you know you only take out your RMDs right. You know, we, we have a term for that internally, like internally. We've named it within our practice. And, you know, you just, you leave all the other planning out of it. So, it really just looks like what's that withdrawal rate, that draw down on the portfolio? Very simple. But does that really, is that beneficial to the client? Maybe? Maybe not. Do I feel that I've done an adequate job of financial planning for the client? Not at all. Not in the least bit.

I have a few instances of that, you know, transition client that I got from somebody and not once have they taken any recommendations. In fact, they've, you know, won't meet with me. So, you know, how can you justify charging them? He's a CFA. I'm not exactly sure why he's in Private Client. He's on his mom's account as power of attorney. So, he's been managing his mom's account. So why are they in Private Client? But if I say anything, that's a million-dollar un-enrollment, and you know, then I gotta justify that. I can't even get them on the calendar.

You know, we always say that you were supposed to do what's right for the client, but we're really, it's, I feel like there is a lot of pressure to keep clients enrolled simply because it impacts Financial Consultant money, you know, FCs compensation. And, you know, furthermore you know, because then they gotta, they got to make that up right? It rolls up into, into their sales figures which puts pressure on them with their manager. So, it's like you're on the front line and you do everything to manage. Remember that, that was in the environment of I need this Financial Consultant to send me business and if a hack him off, is he going to send me business because I'm unenrolling clients? Yeah, I really think that, that's, that's the predominant reason why we do that and is that really in the best interest of clients? I don't know.

I mean, for sure, the sheer quantity of clients I have is really high over 220.

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Or, or suggest them not working with me. Maybe another Portfolio, a Private Client Advisor instead. You may get kind of that pushback or there's that, I mean, that may suggest you're difficult to do business with, you're kind of high maintenance or so there could be some of those where it's kind of feel like you need to take almost anything on. Or it could ultimately, you run the risk where people may not like you or they say, yeah, and they'll just find someone else to give business to.

So, it varies. But I think for the most part, clients are pretty well qualified. Of course, you're going to get the ones that are just not on the same page and they're, they're, the FCs is really trying to force something. You often find, like, like options is a great example of what they might throw in last minute to save a relationship. But I've been in that situation a few times now where it's just not the right fit. And then the client might vocalize that, and the FC just jumps on that, you know, oh, well, we can, we can do options for you, right? And then, you know, we bring in Jay in the conversation, and just like falls flat, you know? But luckily, those are few and far between.

But yeah, the IPSs and the Suitability, I'm sure it's probably, to some degree, regardless of which firms you go to, I think at Morgan, it was something similar. But yeah, it just seems a little bit burdensome, you know, and it's in, you know, when the when the expectation is, you know, you just do Suitability, you just check the box and you move on. You know, it's like it's the last of my priorities. You know, if the expectation really was to you use Suitability as a way to, to have a conversation and meaningful conversation with the client? Then that's different. But that would be overly burdensome. I mean, that would be almost impossible, in my view. Every time, every time, every year, you'd have to, have a, you know, run down this laundry list to really be able to, to cross your T's and dot your I's. But you'd have to ask about a slew of issues, which just, I think if you did it every year, it would just seem so, so non-sequitur to the client.

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It's, it's tough because I feel like a lot of, over the years and having been doing this for as long as I have, the vast majority of things, the bigger themes that they, that they work on us with, are, they are, they kind of bring out in terms of, you know, CPS or IPS or planning or whatever it might be, I feel like it's 75% good. And I feel like it is trending us in a direction that is, that is better at, at the end. Because I do think that things like planning are more holistic, because I've got so many times where I meet somebody and I have three things to do in their portfolio. So, it is nice to have a broader conversation, to have other things to work on. So, I get the idea behind it. The issue is always, here is a number. And it is not ... What they're trying to do is find a way to evaluate what the behaviors they want to have done. And it's really hard to evaluate a behavior without some sort of numeric to put through. Unless you're just sitting with them all the time and listening to the conversations or not. So, you have to put a number to say, well, you need to do this many things. Well, since you put a number on it. Well, now, it's not that I'm trying to get the behaviors that you're trying to do, I'm trying to get that number. And that's where I think the struggle comes in. So, I don't know how you get, I definitely see my calls differently now than I did three years ago, than six years ago, 10 years ago because of these different themes that we've been adding to it and doing different things. But at the end of it all, it still says, OK, well, I get to 50% planning. So, I'm going to try something in here just to shoehorn a plan in. I can talk about the bigger, what we want to do as we manage this. We want to talk about how are we going as planned. But if literally I did a plan 10 months ago. And the markets have just kind of been along the line of a 5% growth over that 10 months. Zero has changed on that plan. We build a plan to say what happens when the markets are good? What happens when the markets are bad? And it almost makes it seem like it to me, I feel like we're almost invalidating what we're doing by saying, well, every year we have to do another one, because every five years maybe I could see, every three years. But, it's just, we're like, saying to clients, we do this to see what happens in different financial situations. And then we're saying, let's do it again or let's do it again, let's do it again. And that's where I think the conflict comes in, saying, 'This is what we'd like you to do - this is how we'd like it to look.' And by making it, the way we get you to do that is by putting a number in place. But it always ends up being, you know, 'Here is, here is the cheese, find it!' The rat will always get to it. But, not in the path that they necessarily want. And then they say, well, to put the cheese over here, OK. We'll always find a way to get those numbers. It's just not the behavior sometimes they want to get out of it.

Quality of interaction. And to me, that's just book size. It goes back to the matter of your workload, the amount of clients you have, but the quality of your notes and what you're detailing is going to suffer. Which this means, which means, again, when you go to think about this person again for the first time in three months, you know, to touch base with them, you look back at that last interaction, you, boy, you didn't really talk about much, even though you may have, right? To write, because your notes, you were just under the gun to try to get that done. That's one small example.

I mean, you know, the whole, I mean the other dumb thing is, is 'everybody needs a plan'. No, everyone doesn't need a plan. Everyone should need help.

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So, a couple of years ago we still wanted to do financial plans for clients, but we were told, you know, update the plan every three to five years or unless something major changes. You know, then, then we'll revisit it. And we had let the client know, let us, you know, we'd get the client agreement to do a financial plan. But now to meet, to meet numbers, I'm getting the message, refresh it every year. And really try and force it on the clients who haven't had one done before. So, you know that, that's, that's kind of frustrating.

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Statements / Phrases Coded to Self-determination Theory - Professional Autonomy - Required but Perfunctory Activity

And I don't think that they have preached to us that everybody has to be using it in the same way, necessarily. But, you know, yeah. Is there a, are there things that are a checkbox? You know, we spend the money on it so let's check the box and make sure that we're showing use of it. Yeah. I think that that exists.

Like, it's just like, you put the client in front of me, I'll do what I can to help them achieve what they need to achieve, right? I don't care how many video conference calls you want me to do, like that's your call. That's your decision, right? I'm not comfortable doing them.

I think the some of the technology gets in the way, all these 'checky-checky' box, box stuff. I think if you really just had to simply manage your portfolio, do the financial planning. You know, update the record all that stuff. I think if you just simply had to do that task, it's certainly manageable, at least in my mind. To the extent that I have, you know, I can, I can scale up mentally from where I'm at to where what that goal number looks like. But I think what gets in the way, and I don't care about this, don't care about this. But I guess I think in my mind that all the technology and all the reporting and all that sense that goes on, in, in theory in support of these behaviors and the, you know, the actual work that you're supposed to be doing all that kind of ancillary stuff is what causes practice sizes to become unmanageable.

Oh, sure, financial planning. Yeah, cuz there's a way you can even, you can push out a plan pretty quick. I mean, there's a way to do that. You just say, all right, well, what's the portfolio look like? If you know you only take out your RMDs right. You know, we, we have a term for that internally, like internally. We've named it within our practice. And, you know, you just, you leave all the other planning out of it. So, it really just looks like, what's that withdrawal rate, that draw down on the portfolio? Very simple. About does that really, is that beneficial to the client? Maybe? Maybe not. Do I feel that I've done an adequate job of financial planning for the client? Not at all. Not in the least bit.

But yeah, the IPSs and the Suitability, I'm sure it's probably, to some degree, regardless of which firms you go to, I think at Morgan, it was something similar. But yeah, it just seems a little bit burdensome, you know, and it's in, you know, when the, when the expectation is, you know, you just do Suitability, you just check the box, and you move on. You know, it's like, it's the last of my priorities. You know, if the expectation really was for you to use Suitability as a way to, to have a conversation and meaningful conversation with the client? Then that's different. But that would be overly burdensome. I mean, that would be almost impossible, in my view. Every time, every time, every year, you'd have to, have a, you know, run down this laundry list to really be able to, to cross your T's and dot your I's. But you'd have to ask about a slew of issues, which just, I think if you did it every year, it would just seem so, so non-sequitur to the client.

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I still think the one area that that needs, there needs some refining is, is meeting those, those, planning numbers and what is considered delivering a plan versus just having planning conversations that are meaningful and helpful to a client? I think that's where you're gonna see a lot of boxes checked. In the sense that we have to complete this plan. Well, let's just go on ahead and "Hey, what's your what's your monthly spending? What's your income? You know, what's your Social Security," and then we throw together this plan. "Here's your Monte Carlo simulation. There you go." We checked the box, right? It's not real detailed, meaningful planning. You know, what are some concerns that you have? Are you putting in those stress factors of here's what, you know, two years of long-term care event will to your plan or just asking them those questions have left concerning you versus just throwing these numbers into a planning software and projecting some numbers

And so, I, you know, for my clients, every practice is different, but you know for mine, or why clients are doing covered calls. They want more individual stocks in your portfolio and they find their way to me and I'm the only one that will do it, or there's not a lot of people that will do it with clients. They don't care as much about planning. It's not where they see value and see value in customizing your portfolio, trying to push planning down their throat when they don't want it, so I can get my tick mark.

And the 'check the box' thing has one thing though, that I think we do run into, is that we are asked to do; when, when you're being measured on numerical metrics, someone's gonna find a way to get over that hurdle in a way that might not be the most, they might not fit, they'll get the desired, desired response, without the required steps. Because of the fact that, if you're planning numbers says this, well I'm gonna run some plans that maybe, I don't think ethically incur unethical, but they're, I don't know they're productive either. It's just I need to get a number. And so, I'm going to do my Investment Policy Statements - 100 in one day to get them off. Does that create any quality? No. But it 'checks the box' to say we're, we're done.

What they're trying to do is find a way to evaluate what the behaviors they want to have done. And it's really hard to evaluate a behavior without some sort of numeric to put through. Unless you're just sitting with them all the time and listening to the conversations or not. So, you have to put a number to say, well, you need to do this many things. Well, since you put a number on it. Well, now, it's not that I'm trying to get the behaviors that you're trying to do, I'm trying to get that number. And that's where I think the struggle comes in.

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Quality of interaction. And to me, that's just book size. It goes back to the matter of your workload, the amount of clients you have, but the quality of your notes and what you're detailing is going to suffer. Which this means, which means, again, when you go to think about this person again for the first time in three months, you know, to touch base with them, you look back at that last interaction, you, boy, you didn't really talk about much, even though you may have, right? To write, because your notes, you were just under the gun to try to get that done. That's one small example.

END OF SECTION

Wellbeing

I help people sort of take control of their financial destiny, and I think that's important. People get divorced over money issues; people get anxiety over money issues. It's something that we can alleviate to some degree for folks and I'm going to take personal pride in being able to do that for folks.

It's just it's just they're concerned about quantity, whether or not too much quantity means too little quality.

I still feel like I haven't quite put my arms around how I, how I continue to support this whole practice and give them what they're paying for.

I think they appreciate the fact that I'm not pushing them products and I'm on a salary basis. So, I think that, for the clients sake, I think that's, that's preferable to them.

I think the main thing is the practice sizes. Among most of them we've never really, you know, they started saying this was an ideal practice size and we don't hear anything about that anymore. So, it's really, you know, from my understanding, they are not, they are not concerned about decreasing your practice size.

I think that's, that's probably what I'm always thinking of when I come in, you know, over a weekend is what am I going to come into, an email of maybe who have I missed. Or who's, who, you know, dropped. You know, if there was a ball dropped.

I look at practice size really more as a time management concern. You know, I mean, you have so many clients, you know, only so many clients can be touched in the course of a day's time before you run out of energy, and you need to go home and recharge your batteries.

As far as devoting more time to some clients than others, well I don't think that every client, you know, should get the exact same amount of time. Because their needs are different, number one, and certainly someone that's paying you fifteen thousand dollars a year probably deserves a little more of your time than someone is paying you four thousand dollars a year, you know. So, the larger clients that, I think it's just the nature of the business, larger clients will tend to get more of your, your focus, more of your time, because they've got more complex situations and it hurts more when they leave.

I know that it hurts them when a client leaves and they know that it hurts me when a client leaves and there is an understanding there.

But I think, you know, you reach a certain level that you should just be able to try to maintain that, you know, plus or minus three or five clients, or what have you, you know, and try to make, because you know when you're at two hundred and ten clients, you know, and you're working 55 60 hours a week, can you really add 20 more clients to that? And, you know, without at some point just completely burning out. And do that year after year after year. No, I don't think you can.

Wellbeing

So, I do remember one of the question was, as a fiduciary do I have too many clients to serve them all well? I definitely would say in the affirmative. I absolutely agree with that. I think we; I think the 'God of scale' - that the firm worships that, right? I think in a relationship business, there's a finite number, right? And I think I don't remember exactly the order, but I know that I have a strong feeling. But I think the idea of 200 households, my perspective is really absurd, right?

I remember thinking, well, like, would I say that I serve all of them well? Yes, but I guess the way you would say it is, is it well enough, right? Not... You could do so much more if you had fewer, right? You could have such deeper relationships. I think this ties-in the firms concerned that they're tied to you less to the firm interest. Because it makes me wonder if there's some intentionality about it.

I think what's gratifying about it is that at least where we work, right? It really does allow you to get to know a client on a very personal level and to really understand their circumstances, which I think I know it sounds silly, but I mean, it really is true that the more you know somebody, the more you tend to have a better grasp of their situation.

Are we say, are we what we say we are? Which is wealth managers. Because I think we were talking out of both sides of our mouth. I think we were marketing ourselves as wealth managers, but all of our energy was focused on sales. So, to me that was, that was a huge pit in my stomach. And it just, I just thought it was in congruent with all the marketing and you know how we position private client to prospects, right?

Oh, sure. Financial Planning. Yeah, cuz there's a way you can even you can push out a plan pretty quick. I mean, there's a way to do that. You just say, all right, well, what's the portfolio look like? If you know you only take out your rids right. You know, we, we, have a term for that in turn like internally. We've named it within our To practice. And, you know, you just, you leave all the other planning out of it. So, it really just looks like what's that withdrawal rate that draw down on the portfolio? Very simple. About does that really, is that beneficial to the client? Maybe? Maybe not. Do I feel that I've done an adequate job of financial planning for the client? Not at all. Not in the least bit.

So, I'm just saying I think that there are, there are obvious error areas that we overlook. And I think a lot of times we just assume that the client situation has remained the same. I mean, when we set up the appointments, we say is anything changed? The client will say yes or no. And we truly don't know. Like, I just had a client that I don't know she's in her 80s and scheduled her meeting. And Has anything changed? Well, no. Any cash needs? No. I mean, we asked the same questions over and over again. But turns out, you know, she's, she's, she's lives on a 21-acre farm in Georgia. And you know, her kids don't want her living there on her own anymore. And so, unbeknownst to me, she's, you know, she sold her house and bought a townhouse and she's been mulling it for a while. And You know, not any real. I mean, that's, that's, a planable event, right? That's something that maybe we perhaps should have explored in financial planning. What does that mean? What does that look like? And did we do that? No. One because it happens so quickly, but two, we were unaware. And I think that gets down to because we, you know, we've, we've got, you've got, especially in my mind, it's very similar to what family physicians and medical field looks like right now. They book 15-minute appointments. That's what you get out. That's what they're allocated, you get 15 minutes. So how much can you really understand about a person's you know, total physical wellbeing in 15 minutes, right, you know, five, 5-10 minutes that was probably just Hey, how you doing? What's going on in your world? And then you got five minutes left? It's just simply not realistic. And I think similarly, with financial planning with, with the portfolio. Oftentimes, my meetings go way over. And do I worry about that? As my practice continues to grow? Yeah, for sure. I worry that in order to be efficient, I need to scale back the length of my meetings. But I fear there's a losses not just relationship, but really understanding what's going on in the client's world and which trend has so many different translations? And then, you know, so let's say your appointment goes beyond what the expectation. Because I think management has the expectation that your meeting should be about 40-45 minutes with 15 minutes for wrap up documentation, etc., etc. So it might easily go beyond that. And I feel like I'm gonna get in trouble at some point, but I don't feel like I'm doing the client service. If you look at how much these clients are charged from, you know, from a basis point perspective, a lot, right? It's not a lot. But when you see the actual debit, hit your account, and you really start reflecting. So I really think I got \$25,000 worth of value this year. Hmm. You know, when my portfolio consultant kind of blew in blew out, making a couple changes. made small talk and then you know, I don't know,

I have a few instances of that, you know, transition client that I got from somebody and not once have they taken any recommendations. In fact, they've, you know, won't meet with me. So, you know, how can you justify charging them? He's a CFA. I'm not exactly sure why he's in private client. He's on his mom's account as power of attorney. So, he's been managing his mom's account. So why are they in private client? But if I say anything, that's a million-dollar un-enrollment, and you know, then I gotta justify that. I can't even get them on the calendar.

Wellbeing

You know, we always say that you were supposed to do what's right for the client, but we're really, it's, I feel like there is a lot of pressure to keep clients enrolled simply because it impacts Financial Consultant money, you know, FCs compensation. And, you know, furthermore you know, because then they gotta, they got to make that up right? It rolls up into, into their sales figures which puts pressure on them with their manager. So, it's like you're on the front line and you do everything to manage. Remember that that was in the environment of I need this financial consultant to send me business and if a hack him off, is he going to send me business because I'm unenrolling clients? Yeah, I really think that that's, that's the predominant reason why we do that and is that really in the best interest of clients? I don't know.

I think for the most part, The Organization is an ethical firm, I do think they act as an advocate for clients. I got to say a lot of my frustrations have been about, you know that our acting is sales, people that think that that's going to go away even though we're not incented on it anymore think that that pressure still going to be there from the financial consultants, we're just not going to be rewarded or punished for it come bonus time. And you know that that's one more thing. So, it's so ridiculous. They set these ridiculous targets that are almost inhuman to me. And so, you've got a few superstars good for them. But you can hit your target, you can do everything that you're supposed to do, and You know, they management, throughout the course of the year says, you know, you got to hit these targets got to hit these targets, you've got to hit them. And then you do that. And when it comes around to evaluation, you're like, well, somebody, somebody hit those targets just a little bit better than us. So, we're going to take from you and give to somebody else. You're just like, really, if I live, this is what you said I needed to do, and I did it, and yet I'm still being punished. So, because somebody else either, you know, has a super relationship with or you know, has tied or connected to a particular region that does well. So, you know, if you tell me that I need to do this and I do that, don't punish me, because you want to reward somebody else. Because to me in my mind, then I always have this Moving Target, you can tell me what I'm supposed to do. It doesn't. It doesn't have any meaning or validity to me because it's always moving.

And you aren't robbing from Peter to pay Paul. Yeah. Which I think from a morale perspective, you know, people get a little bit jaded. Because when you, you know, when, when it comes time for your annual review, you're like, you know, I, everybody walks, not everybody but you know, a lot of people walked into the meetings thinking, you know, how am I going to get screwed?

I mean, for sure, the sheer quantity of clients I have is really high over 220.

I think it's a while, just kind of in within the team there is kind of competition in the same markets and then sometimes you have other teams that are trying to vie for those same markets. Too many people chasing too few FCs? Yeah.

You know, the IPS and getting the factfinder information there from them. Because realistically, it's, it's a little backwards in the way that that that we sometimes approach this in the sense that they want to make sure that their investments are lined up, you know, what's kind of their preferences in And needs. But until we actually run that plan, and identify what those needs are, and maybe they're taking more risks than what's really warranted for the success for the plan, if you kind of be like a little a little backwards the way that we approach it and, and I think what the clients want as well.

I, it's kind of nice for us to have autonomy, like we don't really have anybody really second guessing us. But, I mean, that's where I think the value is for clients. When you have like a think tank of people who really, like, really try to think through what's best for the client. That is one person coming up with the solution. It's like, OK, this is what Vincent proposed, but maybe this other professional has a different opinion.

Wellbeing

I still think the one area that that needs, there needs some refining is, is meeting those, those planning numbers and what is considered delivering a plan versus just having planning conversations that are meaningful and helpful to a client? I think that's where you're gonna see a lot of boxes checked. In the sense that we have to complete this plan. Well, let's just go on ahead and Hey, what's your what's your monthly spending? What's your income? You know, what's your Social Security, and then we throw together this plan. Here's your Monte Carlo simulation. There you go. We checked the box, right? It's not real, detailed, meaningful planning. You know, what are some concerns that you have? Are you putting in those stress factors of here's what, you know, two years of long-term care went with due to your plan or just asking them those questions have left concerning you versus just throwing these numbers into a planning software and projecting some numbers

I think when you put numbers to anything, there's going to be, you know, not necessarily unethical things, but you're, you're going to your competitive nature, is going to take in into effect there and you want to do your best and if you want to provide for your team and for yourself, so when there was the, you know, the quantitative metrics there of hitting planning and hitting assets and stuff, you know, there was maybe a little bit, a little bit more of a, you know, these, these CDs that we recommended here to you, you know, we made the recommendation on these and they're sitting in the account, so you should be paying a fee on those. Versus, hey, we've got no intention to sell these. Maybe they should be in a non PCA account, where you're not paying a fee and then as they mature, then maybe we decide what we want to do. I think there can be a little, a little bit of that, but for the sense of not making unsuitable recommendations based on pay I really like that aspect of The Organization Private Client, right?

I think the most challenging is we have too many clients, we really need a deeper dive with each client. You know, I think maybe with some other RIAs they have you know less clients or more defined roles. You know, planners can do a better job of, you know, looking at maybe a client's tax situation and analyzing other assets that they have pulling that all together to give them deeper financial finance. Advice outside of just going to more of a portfolio. I don't think that we can do that very well with the number of clients that we have it's just not possible.

It is, it's a-amazing, again. But what we're running into right now is a perfect example of how, if you stretch everything to capacity and then anything comes along to disrupt that a little bit, you are now beyond capacity. You can't, you can't keep it going. I had a co-worker say that, but every year it's like you work so hard all year to fill up the bucket and then the first day of the year they come by and kick the bucket over and say, fill it up again. And that's, that's the thing that's so difficult, is you feel like you've got it, you've done it, and then what happened last year, in some ways feels like it's no longer of consequence. And it's only what you do from this point on. And then it gets harder, obviously. And I think that's harder in an FC role than ours, but it's that constant, you know, you just run a little bit faster even when you're running as fast as possible.

Wellbeing

And the 'check the box' thing has one thing though, that I think we do run into, is that we are asked to do; when, when you're being measured on numerical metrics, someone's gonna find a way to get over that hurdle in a way that might not be the most, they might not fit, they'll get the desired, desired response, without the required steps. Because of the fact that, if you're planning members says this. Well, I'm gonna run some plans that maybe, I don't think ethically incur unethical, but they're, I don't know they're productive either. It's just I need to get a number. And so, I'm going to do my Investment Policy Statements - 100, in one day, to get them off. Does that create any quality? No. But it 'checks the box' to say we're, we're done.

Yes, so that definitely happens. That's happened since day one. That, that I think will, because it's never... their, their role in some ways is in contrast to our role, not in contrast, but, but in more of, it's just, it's different. And because of that, they're going to be incented to get people through the door and hope it works. And if it doesn't, they're going to get a little bit of a sting. But, their hope is, they get it to us and we then wrangled the wild horse and get it in the pen. And if we can do that, then we're gonna, then they appreciate us and they like us, and you know they'll give us, you know, they'll keep bringing it to us. And so that's where, for what we do, it's so vital for us to try and figure out, even if it's somebody who might be a bad fit. And I guess maybe this isn't an ethical as much as it's just awkward, to try and find a way to make that client who doesn't necessarily fit, how can we keep them in? Because it's it hurts everybody. It helps everybody on the way in and hurts everybody on the way out and we're the ones who work the back door. So, we've got to try and do everything we can to keep him in that place.

I, I don't, I, I'm, I'm very much a dyed-in-the-wool of kind of what we do. And so, I try really hard. You know, occasionally there is there is the, I will, I will bend. But I won't break. So, if it's something that somebody wants something ... I absolutely can't recommend things beyond what we're allowed to recommend. But if it's something where a client wants to do something that I think is, is, not 100 percent within what we're trying to do, but maybe is 75 percent what we're trying to do, then I will try to find a way to make that then work for them. Because I just get, I honestly, I get tired of trying to fight them on it.

It's hard for me to pick a specific one, but like it's awkward when a client asks how often do you review my investments because they have an assumption that we're constantly looking at them adjusting things and it's more like four times a year at most.

Because of my workload, I feel I worry about the possibility of important things falling through the cracks.

Wellbeing

It's, it's tough because I feel like a lot of, over the years and having been doing this for as long as I have, the vast majority of things, the bigger themes that they, that they work on us with, are, they are, they kind of bring out in terms of, you know, CPS or IPS or planning or whatever it might be, I feel like it's 75 percent good. And I feel like it is trending us in a direction that is, that is better at, at the end. Because I do think that things like planning are more holistic, because I've got so many times where I meet somebody, and I have three things to do in their portfolio. So it is nice to have a broader conversation, to have other things to work on. So, I get the idea behind it. The issue is always, here is a number. And it is not ... What they're trying to do is find a way to evaluate what the behaviors they want to have done. And it's really hard to evaluate a behavior without some sort of numeric to put through. Unless you're just sitting with them all the time and listening to the conversations or not. So, you have to put a number to say, well, you need to do this many things. Well, since you put a number on it. Well, now, it's not that I'm trying to get the behaviors that you're trying to do, I'm trying to get that number. And that's where I think the struggle comes in. So, I don't know how you get, I definitely see my calls differently now than I did three years ago, than six years ago, 10 years ago because of these different themes that we've been adding to it and doing different things. But at the end of it all, it still says, OK, well, I get to 50 percent planning. So, I'm going to try something in here just to shoehorn a plan in. I can talk about the bigger, what we want to do as we manage this. We want to talk about how are we going as planned. But if literally I did a plan 10 months ago. And the markets have just kind of been along the line of a 5 percent growth over that 10 months. Zero has changed on that plan. We build a plan to say what happens when the markets are good? What happens when the markets are bad? And it almost makes it seem like it to me, I feel like we're almost invalidating what we're doing by saying, well, every year we have to do another one, because every five years maybe I could see, every three years. But, it's just, we're like, saying to clients, we do this to see what happens in different financial situations. And then we're saying, let's do it again or let's do it again, let's do it again. And that's where I think the conflict comes in, saying, 'This is what we'd like you to do - this is how we'd like it to look.' And by making it, the way we get you to do that is by putting a number in place. But, it always ends up being, you know, 'Here is, here is the cheese, find it!' The rat will always get to it. But, not in the path that they necessarily want. And then they say, well, to put the cheese over here, OK. We'll always find a way to get those numbers. It's just not the behavior sometimes they want to get out of it.

But that's a really challenging thing to do when the sales business, who you solely rely on for incoming business, incoming clients, has sat in a meeting prior to you saying, oh, you only got 9% last year? I'm sure PC can do better than that. And I've been on phone calls when I've heard that said and that is the polar opposite of how we think about investing. So, I don't, and that's not fair to a client to, like, sign them up to something and then pivot the investment approach. I mean, we all get frustrated with performance driven clients, but to a degree, like, the frustration should be with our model, because if a client wants to go out-perform, they should go, you know, buy some active mutual funds or go find somebody else that wants to do that, because I know very few people in PCA, that want, or are interested in doing that.

I mean, we talk, PC talks all the time about how profitable their clients are, right? But one of the main, I think the biggest reason, one of the biggest reasons I have to think clients leave their advisors is just because they don't feel like they hear from them, right? So, to me, that's really clear logic. Like you've got a vested interest in keeping clients happy, right? When clients are paying at least, what, between four to 10 grand a year on average in fees, like if you need to, to press pause for a bit and just work your existing book without having to worry about how branch reps perceive you, you know? Because I think that's the real problem. The real, one of the big concerns,

Wellbeing

Quality of interaction. And to me, that's just book size. It goes back to the matter of your workload, the amount of clients you have, but the quality of your notes and what you're detailing is going to suffer. Which this means, which means, again, when you go to think about this person again for the first time in three months, you know, to touch base with them, you look back at that last interaction, you, boy, you didn't really talk about much, even though you may have, right? To write, because your notes, you were just under the gun to try to get that done. That's one small example.

We're not free of conflict. No one is free. But, I think we do a good job of minimizing some of the issues that are out there in the industry with conflicts. I think no one's perfect. I think we do a good job of serving the client. I think we do a good job of, if there's issues with the client. I think from that standpoint we do a really good job.

Having integrity when you deal with people of all walks of life and such. And that's where I struggle because we don't seem to apply that. We apply that to the client, but we don't necessarily apply it to our own business our own internal partners who, in theory, we have the same goal in mind.

I go to the other issues of how we are incentivized to provide that, you know, the, the deal or the illusion that we have to create for the client and for the FC of our time constraints, right? And how we are incented in reality.

It's when we get into that kind of question of, how many clients we are responsible for, whether being a client or an FC. That's really where you can't tell them. You can't tell the truth! You can't tell them you have 200 million or two hundred and six clients.

We all know that we have some of that, you know, looking at capacity again, with asked to do more, and then come back and said, Okay, then how does that fit into trying to do a quality job for each individual when the conveyor belts moving faster than it ever has before in the industry?

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Compensation should be competitive just because of the fiduciary responsibilities we have. You know having the knowledge and experience to make suitable recommendations, give prudent advice. That's, that's important to avoid legal issues in the future. But as the role has turned more to sales, that's where it's, uh, it's more difficult, you know, to spend the time and effort to go out to market, to sell yourself to FCs. To bring in more business takes away from serving the clients you have. And if compensation is being moved towards sales then, you know, I think that's a little bit of a disservice.

I never bring up, yeah, I don't bring up performance either. I think when you bring it up with a client you don't want to get focused on performance - short term performance. So typically, performance is talked about more when the markets are doing good.

Wellbeing

Probably most recently it's the goal of planning penetration and I get the sense that, you know, and just look at clients who've had plans done in the last year or two, and just send it out, you know, update the assets and send it out. You don't even need to talk to the client before you send it out. And I'm uncomfortable with that. Maybe a handful of clients I can do that with because they have very simple plans, you know, they're retired and they only have Social Security and a pension, that's it. So that's easy enough. But otherwise, I want to make sure that the information in the plan that I'm sending them is correct and still, still relevant. So, you know, trying to get plans out to get my planning penetration numbers up, I don't necessarily like that.

END OF SECTION

Advisor Wellbeing

I think the main thing is the practice sizes. Among most of them we've never really, you know, they started saying this was an ideal practice size and we don't hear anything about that anymore. So, it's really, you know, from my understanding, they are not, they are not concerned about decreasing your practice size.

I think that's, that's probably what I'm always thinking of when I come in, you know, over a weekend is what am I going to come into, an email of maybe who have I missed. Or who's, who, you know, dropped. You know, if there was a ball dropped.

I look at practice size really more as a time management concern. You know, I mean, you have so many clients, you know, only so many clients can be touched in the course of a day's time before you run out of energy, and you need to go home and recharge your batteries.

But I think, you know, you reach a certain level that you should just be able to try to maintain that, you know, plus or minus three or five clients, or what have you, you know, and try to make, because you know when you're at two hundred and ten clients, you know, and you're working 55 60 hours a week, can you really add 20 more clients to that? And, you know, without at some point just completely burning out. And do that year after year after year. No, I don't think you can.

I think what's gratifying about it is that at least where we work, right? It really does allow you to get to know a client on a very personal level and to really understand their circumstances, which I think I know it sounds silly, but I mean, it really is true that the more you know somebody, the more you tend to have a better grasp of their situation.

Are we say, are we what we say we are? Which is wealth managers. Because I think we were talking out of both sides of our mouth. I think we were marketing ourselves as wealth managers, but all of our energy was focused on sales. So, to me that was, that was a huge pit in my stomach. And it just, I just thought it was in congruent with all the marketing and you know how we position private client to prospects, right?

Oh, sure. Financial Planning. Yeah, cuz there's a way you can even you can push out a plan pretty quick. I mean, there's a way to do that. You just say, all right, well, what's the portfolio look like? If you know you only take out your rids right. You know, we, we, have a term for that in turn like internally. We've named it within our To practice. And, you know, you just, you leave all the other planning out of it. So, it really just looks like what's that withdrawal rate that draw down on the portfolio? Very simple. About does that really, is that beneficial to the client? Maybe? Maybe not. Do I feel that I've done an adequate job of financial planning for the client? Not at all. Not in the least bit.

Advisor Wellbeing

I think for the most part, The Organization is an ethical firm, I do think they act as an advocate for clients. I got to say a lot of my frustrations have been about, you know that our acting is sales, people that think that that's going to go away even though we're not incented on it anymore think that that pressure still going to be there from the financial consultants, we're just not going to be rewarded or punished for it come bonus time. And you know that that's one more thing. So, it's so ridiculous. They set these ridiculous targets that are almost inhuman to me. And so, you've got a few superstars good for them. But you can hit your target, you can do everything that you're supposed to do, and you know, they management, throughout the course of the year says, you know, you got to hit these targets got to hit these targets, you've got to hit them. And then you do that. And when it comes around to evaluation, you're like, well, somebody, somebody hit those targets just a little bit better than us. So, we're going to take from you and give to somebody else. You're just like, really, if I live, this is what you said I needed to do, and I did it, and yet I'm still being punished. So, because somebody else either, you know, has a super relationship with or you know, has tied or connected to a particular region that does well. So, you know, if you tell me that I need to do this and I do that, don't punish me, because you want to reward somebody else. Because to me in my mind, then I always have this Moving Target, you can tell me what I'm supposed to do. It doesn't. It doesn't have any meaning or validity to me because it's always moving.

And you aren't robbing from Peter to pay Paul. Yeah. Which I think from a morale perspective, you know, people get a little bit jaded. Because when you, you know, when, when it comes time for your annual review, you're like, you know, I, everybody walks, not everybody but you know, a lot of people walked into the meetings thinking, you know, how am I going to get screwed?

I think it's a while, just kind of in within the team there is kind of competition in the same markets and then sometimes you have other teams that are trying to vie for those same markets.

I, it's kind of nice for us to have autonomy, like we don't really have anybody really second guessing us. But, I mean, that's where I think the value is for clients. When you have like a think tank of people who really, like, really try to think through what's best for the client. That is one person coming up with the solution. It's like, OK, this is what Vincent proposed, but maybe this other professional has a different opinion.

It is, it's a-amazing, again. But what we're running into right now is a perfect example of how, if you stretch everything to capacity and then anything comes along to disrupt that a little bit, you are now beyond capacity. You can't, you can't keep it going. I had a co-worker say that, but every year it's like you work so hard all year to fill up the bucket and then the first day of the year they come by and kick the bucket over and say, fill it up again. And that's, that's the thing that's so difficult, is you feel like you've got it, you've done it, and then what happened last year, in some ways feels like it's no longer of consequence. And it's only what you do from this point on. And then it gets harder, obviously. And I think that's harder in an FC role than ours, but it's that constant, you know, you just run a little bit faster even when you're running as fast as possible.

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Client Wellbeing

I help people sort of take control of their financial destiny, and I think that's important. People get divorced over money issues. People get anxiety over money issues. It's something that we can alleviate to some degree for folks and I'm going to take personal pride in being able to do that for folks.

It's just it's just they're concerned about quantity, whether or not too much quantity means too little quality.

I still feel like I haven't quite put my arms around how I, how I continue to support this whole practice and give them what they're paying for.

I think they appreciate the fact that I'm not pushing them products and I'm on a salary basis. So I think that, for the clients sake, I think that's, that's preferable to them.

I think the main thing is the practice sizes. Among most of them we've never really, you know, they started saying this was an ideal practice size and we don't hear anything about that anymore. So it's really, you know, from my understanding, they are not, they are not concerned about decreasing your practice size.

I think that's, that's probably what I'm always thinking of when I come in, you know, over a weekend is what am I going to come into, an email of maybe who have I missed. Or who's, who, you know, dropped. You know, if there was a ball dropped.

As far as devoting more time to some clients than others, well I don't think that every client, you know, should get the exact same amount of time. Because their needs are different, number one, and certainly someone that's paying you fifteen thousand dollars a year probably deserves a little more of your time than someone is paying you four thousand dollars a year, you know. So the larger clients that, I think it's just the nature of the business, larger clients will tend to get more of your, your focus, more of your time, because they've got more complex situations and it hurts more when they leave.

I know that it hurts them when a client leaves and they know that it hurts me when a client leaves and there is an understanding there.

So, I do remember one of the question was, as a fiduciary do I have too many clients to serve them all well? I definitely would say in the affirmative. I absolutely agree with that. I think we, I think the 'God of scale' - that the firm worships that, right? I think in a relationship business, there's a finite number, right? And I think I don't remember exactly the order, but I know that I have a strong feeling. But I think the idea of 200 households, my perspective is really absurd, right?

Client Wellbeing

I remember thinking, well, like, would I say that I serve all of them well? Yes, but I guess the way you would say it is, is it well enough, right? Not... You could do so much more if you had fewer, right? You could have such deeper relationships. I think this ties-in the firms concerned that they're tied to you less to the firm interest. Because it makes me wonder if there's some intentionality about it.

Oh, sure. Financial Planning. Yeah, cuz there's a way you can even you can push out a plan pretty quick. I mean, there's a way to do that. You just say, all right, well, what's the portfolio look like? If you know you only take out your rids right. You know, we, we have a term for that in turn like internally. We've named it within our To practice. And, you know, you just, you leave all the other planning out of it. So, it really just looks like what's that withdrawal rate that draw down on the portfolio? Very simple. About does that really, is that beneficial to the client? Maybe? Maybe not. Do I feel that I've done an adequate job of financial planning for the client? Not at all. Not in the least bit.

So, I'm just saying I think that there are, there are obvious error areas that we overlook. And I think a lot of times we just assume that the client situation has remained the same. I mean, when we set up the appointments, we say is anything changed? The client will say yes or no. And we truly don't know. Like, I just had a client that I don't know she's in her 80s and scheduled her meeting. And Has anything changed? Well, no. Any cash needs? No. I mean, we asked the same questions over and over again. But turns out, you know, she's, she's, she's lives on a 21-acre farm in Georgia. And you know, her kids don't want her living there on her own anymore. And so, unbeknownst to me, she's, you know, she sold her house and bought a townhouse and she's been mulling it for a while. And You know, not any real. I mean, that's, that's, a planable event, right? That's something that maybe we perhaps should have explored in financial planning. What does that mean? What does that look like? And did we do that? No. One because it happens so quickly, but two, we were unaware. And I think that gets down to because we, you know, we've, we've got, you've got, especially in my mind, it's very similar to what family physicians and medical field looks like right now. They book 15-minute appointments. That's what you get out. That's what they're allocated, you get 15 minutes. So how much can you really understand about a person's you know, total physical wellbeing in 15 minutes, right, you know, five, 5-10 minutes that was probably just Hey, how you doing? What's going on in your world? And then you got five minutes left? It's just simply not realistic. And I think similarly, with financial planning with, with, the portfolio. Oftentimes, my meetings go way over. And do I worry about that? As my practice continues to grow? Yeah, for sure. I worry that in order to be efficient, I need to scale back the length of my meetings. But I fear there's a losses not just relationship, but really understanding what's going on in the client's world and which trend has so many different translations? And then, you know, so let's say your appointment goes beyond what the expectation. Because I think management has the expectation that your meeting should be about 40-45 minutes with 15 minutes for wrap up documentation, etc., etc. So, it might easily go beyond that. And I feel like I'm gonna get in trouble at some point, but I don't feel like I'm doing the client service. If you look at how much these clients are charged from, you know, from a basis point perspective, a lot, right? It's not a lot. But when you see the actual debit, hit your account, and you really start reflecting. So I really think I got \$25,000 worth of value this year. Hmm. You know, when my portfolio consultant kind of blew in blew out, making a couple changes. made small talk and then you know, I don't know,

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I have a few instances of that, you know, transition client that I got from somebody and not once have they taken any recommendations. In fact, they've, you know, won't meet with me. So, you know, how can you justify charging them? He's a CFA. I'm not exactly sure why he's in private client. He's on his mom's account as power of attorney. So, he's been managing his mom's account. So why are they in private client? But if I say anything, that's a million-dollar un-enrollment, and you know, then I gotta justify that. I can't even get them on the calendar.

You know, we always say that you were supposed to do what's right for the client, but we're really, it's, I feel like there is a lot of pressure to keep clients enrolled simply because it impacts Financial Consultant money, you know, FCs compensation. And, you know, furthermore you know, because then they gotta, they got to make that up right? It rolls up into, into their sales figures which puts pressure on them with their manager. So, it's like you're on the front line and you do everything to manage. Remember that that was in the environment of I need this financial consultant to send me business and if a hack him off, is he going to send me business because I'm unenrolling clients? Yeah, I really think that that's, that's the predominant reason why we do that and is that really in the best interest of clients? I don't know.

I mean, for sure, the sheer quantity of clients I have is really high over 220.

You know, the IPS and getting the factfinder information there from them. Because realistically, it's, it's a little backwards in the way that that that we sometimes approach this in the sense that they want to make sure that their investments are lined up, you know, what's kind of their preferences in And needs. But until we actually run that plan, and identify what those needs are, and maybe they're taking more risks than what's really warranted for the success for the plan, if you kind of be like a little a little backwards the way that we approach it and, and I think what the clients want as well.

I still think the one area that that needs, there needs some refining is, is meeting those, those planning numbers and what is considered delivering a plan versus just having planning conversations that are meaningful and helpful to a client? I think that's where you're gonna see a lot of boxes checked. In the sense that we have to complete this plan. Well, let's just go on ahead and Hey, what's your what's your monthly spending? What's your income? You know, what's your Social Security, and then we throw together this plan. Here's your Monte Carlo simulation. There you go. We checked the box, right? It's not real, detailed, meaningful planning. You know, what are some concerns that you have? Are you putting in those stress factors of here's what, you know, two years of long-term care went with due to your plan or just asking them those questions have left concerning you versus just throwing these numbers into a planning software and projecting some numbers.

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I think when you put numbers to anything, there's going to be, you know, not necessarily unethical things, but you're, you're going to your competitive nature, is going to take in into effect there and you want to do your best and if you want to provide for your team and for yourself, so when there was the, you know, the quantitative metrics there of hitting planning and hitting assets and stuff, you know, there was maybe a little bit, a little bit more of a, you know, these, these CDs that we recommended here to you, you know, we made the recommendation on these and they're sitting in the account, so you should be paying a fee on those. Versus, hey, we've got no intention to sell these. Maybe they should be in a non PCA account, where you're not paying a fee and then as they mature, then maybe we decide what we want to do. I think there can be a little, a little bit of that, but for the sense of not making unsuitable recommendations based on pay I really like that aspect of The Organization Private Client, right?

I think the most challenging is we have too many clients, we really need a deeper dive with each client. You know, I think maybe with some other RIAs they have you know less clients or more defined roles. You know, planners can do a better job of, you know, looking at maybe a client's tax situation and analyzing other assets that they have pulling that all together to give them deeper financial finance. Advice outside of just going to more of a portfolio. I don't think that we can do that very well with the number of clients that we have it's just not possible.

And the 'check the box' thing has one thing though, that I think we do run into, is that we are asked to do; when, when you're being measured on numerical metrics, someone's gonna find a way to get over that hurdle in a way that might not be the most, they might not fit, they'll get the desired, desired response, without the required steps. Because of the fact that, if you're planning members says this. Well, I'm gonna run some plans that maybe, I don't think ethically incur unethical, but they're, I don't know they're productive either. It's just I need to get a number. And so, I'm going to do my Investment Policy Statements - 100, in one day, to get them off. Does that create any quality? No. But it 'checks the box' to say we're, we're done.

Yes, so that definitely happens. That's happened since day one. That, that I think will, because it's never... there, their role in some ways is in contrast to our role, not in contrast, but, but in more of, it's just, it's different. And because of that, they're going to be incented to get people through the door and hope it works. And if it doesn't, they're going to get a little bit of a sting. But, their hope is, they get it to us and we then wrangled the wild horse and get it in the pen. And if we can do that, then we're gonna, then they appreciate us and they like us, and you know they'll give us, you know, they'll keep bringing it to us. And so that's where, for what we do, it's so vital for us to try and figure out, even if it's somebody who might be a bad fit. And I guess maybe this isn't an ethical as much as it's just awkward, to try and find a way to make that client who doesn't necessarily fit, how can we keep them in? Because it's it hurts everybody. It helps everybody on the way in and hurts everybody on the way out and we're the ones who work the back door. So we've got to try and do everything we can to keep him in that place.

I, I don't, I, I'm, I'm very much a dyed-in-the-wool of kind of what we do. And so, I try really hard. You know, occasionally there is there is the, I will, I will bend. But I won't break. So, if it's something that somebody wants something ... I absolutely can't recommend things beyond what we're allowed to recommend. But if it's something where a client wants to do something that I think is, is, not 100 percent within what we're trying to do, but maybe is 75 percent what we're trying to do, then I will try to find a way to make that then work for them. Because I just get, I honestly, I get tired of trying to fight them on it.

It's hard for me to pick a specific one, but like it's awkward when a client asks how often do you review my investments because they have an assumption that we're constantly looking at them adjusting things and it's more like four times a year at most.

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But that's a really challenging thing to do when the sales business, who you solely rely on for incoming business, incoming clients, has sat in a meeting prior to you saying, oh, you only got 9 percent last year? I'm sure PCA can do better than that. And I've been on phone calls when I've heard that said and that is the polar opposite of how we think about investing. So, I don't, and that's not fair to a client to, like, sign them up to something and then pivot the investment approach. I mean, we all get frustrated with performance driven clients, but to a degree, like, the frustration should be with our model, because if a client wants to go out-perform, they should go, you know, buy some active mutual funds or go find somebody else that wants to do that, because I know very few people in PCA, that want, or are interested in doing that.

I mean, we talk, PC talks all the time about how profitable their clients are, right? But one of the main, I think the biggest reason, one of the biggest reasons I have to think clients leave their advisors is just because they don't feel like they hear from them, right? So, to me, that's really clear logic. Like you've got a vested interest in keeping clients happy, right? When clients are paying at least, what, between four to 10 grand a year on average in fees, like if you need to, to press pause for a bit and just work your existing book without having to worry about how branch reps perceive you, you know? Because I think that's the real problem. The real, one of the big concerns,

Quality of interaction. And to me, that's just book size. It goes back to the matter of your workload, the amount of clients you have, but the quality of your notes and what you're detailing is going to suffer. Which this means, which means, again, when you go to think about this person again for the first time in three months, you know, to touch base with them, you look back at that last interaction, you, boy, you didn't really talk about much, even though you may have, right? To write, because your notes, you were just under the gun to try to get that done. That's one small example.

We're not free of conflict. No one is free. But, I think we do a good job of minimizing some of the issues that are out there in the industry with conflicts. I think no one's perfect. I think we do a good job of serving the client. I think we do a good job of, if there's issues with the client. I think from that standpoint we do a really good job.

I never bring up, yeah, I don't bring up performance either. I think when you bring it up with a client you don't want to get focused on performance - short term performance. So typically, performance is talked about more when the markets are doing good.

Probably most recently it's the goal of planning penetration and I get the sense that, you know, and just look at clients who've had plans done in the last year or two, and just send it out, you know, update the assets and send it out. You don't even need to talk to the client before you send it out. And I'm uncomfortable with that. Maybe a handful of clients I can do that with because they have very simple plans, you know, they're retired and they only have Social Security and a pension, that's it. So that's easy enough. But otherwise, I want to make sure that the information in the plan that I'm sending them is correct and still, still relevant. So, you know, trying to get plans out to get my planning penetration numbers up, I don't necessarily like that.

END OF SECTION